

ASSESSMENT OF ECONOMIES OF SCALE AND TECHNICAL CHANGE ALONG THE FOOD CHAINS - EFFICIENCY AND TECHNICAL CHANGE -

PROJECT
REPORT
D5.6

VALUMICS - UNDERSTANDING FOOD VALUE
CHAINS AND NETWORK DYNAMICS

OCTOBER 2020

Food Systems Dynamics

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727243

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ABOUT

VALUMICS stands for value chain dynamics and is a research project funded by the EU H2020 programme. VALUMICS will enable decision makers to evaluate policy impact on food value chains

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CITATION TO THIS REPORT

Cechura, L., Žakova Kroupova, Z., Rumankova, L., Jaghdani, T.J., Samoggia, A., Thakur, M. (2020). Assessment of Economics of scale and technical change along the food chain. The VALUMICS project funded by EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 727243. Deliverable: D5.6, Czech University of Life Sciences, Prague, 169 pages. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.5161347

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Grant Agreement number: 727243

VALUMICS

Understanding food value chains and network dynamics

Start date of project: 01/06/2017

Duration: 48 Months

Deliverable: D5.6

Assessment of Economies of scale and technical change along the food chains

- Efficiency and technical change -

Food Systems Dynamics

Project co-funded by European Commission within the H2020 Programme		
Dissemination level of this deliverable		
PU	Public	X
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CI	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC.	

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727243”

Document Status Sheet

Due date of deliverable:	Month no. 37
Actual submission date:	Actual month no. 41
Partner in charge of the WD and contributing partners	Czech University of Life Sciences Prague (CZU) Leibniz Institute of Agricultural Development in Transition Economies (IAMO); University of Bologna (UNIBO); SINTEF Ocean
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Version	3.0
Document Status	final

Change history:

Version	Date	Details (additions, changes, reviews, performed by whom)
1.0	15.10.2020	Initial version circulated for comments by task team
2.0	26.10.2020	Version sent to consortium for inputs / comments
3.0	30.10.2020	Final version for submission

Disclaimer:

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Citation:

Cechura, L., Žáková Kroupová, Z., Rumánková, L., Jaghdani, T.J., Samoggia, A., Thakur, M. (2020). Assessment of Economics of scale and technical change along the food chain. The VALUMICS project funded by EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 727243. Deliverable: D5.6, Czech University of Life Sciences, Prague, 169 pages.

"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 727243"

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ABBREVIATIONS

AR	Autoregression process
AWU	Annual Work Unit
DEA	Data Envelopment Analysis
EE	Excluded from Estimation
EU	European Union
EUROSTAT	Statistical Office of the European Union
FADN	Farm Accountancy Data Network
GLS	Generalized Least Squares
GMM	Generalized Method of Moments
GTRE	Generalized True Random Effect
IDF	Input Distance Function
LNO	Low Number of Observations
NACE	Statistical Classification of Economic Activities in the European Community
OTE	Overall Technical Efficiency
R&D	Research and Development
RTS	Returns to Scale
SEC	Scale Effect
SFA	Stochastic Frontier Analysis
TC	Technical Change
TEC	Technical Efficiency Effect
TFP	Total Factor Productivity
TTI	Törnqvist-Theil Index
UAA	Utilised Agricultural Area

Executive Summary

This study provides the findings on technical efficiency, firm heterogeneity, the exploitation of economies of scale, the impact of technical change, as well as total factor productivity development on both agricultural and processing levels of the selected European agri-food supply chains. The analysis is based on two-stage stochastic frontier modelling. The first stage uses country-specific input-distance function models to estimate the economies of scale, persistent and transient technical efficiency, as well as the impact of technical change and the development of total factor productivity in selected countries. In the second stage, meta-frontier approach is used to compare the technical efficiency and the total factor productivity levels among the countries in the European agri-food chains. Afterwards, the impact of technological change on the prices and quantities as well as on the rents and welfare effects is evaluated and main actors in innovation processes are discussed.

The study covers 12 European countries: Austria, Belgium, the Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Romania, Spain, Sweden, and the United Kingdom. It is focused on the analysis of cereals, milk and salmon production, and five food processing sectors: processing and preserving of meat and production of meat products, manufacture of dairy products, manufacture of grain mill products, manufacture of bakery and farinaceous products and Italian tomato processing. The research is based on the individual firms/farms data and covers the period 2006-2018.

Country's input distance function estimates reveal differences in food-producing and processing technologies among the countries but no significant inter-sectoral heterogeneity on the country level. While the agricultural level is characterized by predominantly increasing returns to scale, food processors in general do not exhibit significant economies of scale. In addition, the results indicate that large companies have optimal size on both agriculture and food-processing levels. On the other hand, small and middle-sized companies have a substantial potential to improve their productivity by increasing scales of operations, leading to lower unit costs and increasing profitability.

The technical change significantly positively contributes to the production possibilities in food processing industry in majority of the countries as well as in the salmon production. On agriculture level, the technological regress is revealed especially in milk production in the majority of analyzed countries. Biased technical change is pronounced in the half of the analyzed countries and is predominantly labour-saving in the food-processing industry and the cereals production, and capital-using in the milk production.

The overall efficiency is high in agriculture as well as in food processing. However, significant differences among the countries in the efficiency of inputs use were revealed. In particular, the overall technical efficiency estimates are between 77% and 95% in agriculture, 73 and 95% in food processing industry and about 84% in salmon production. That is, farmers may reduce their costs from 5% up to 27%, firms in the food processing industry from 5% up to 23%, and salmon producers by 16% to produce the same volume of output. The decomposition of overall technical efficiency

reveals that many farmers are falling behind the most efficient ones in the long-term in the majority of analyzed countries. The developments in technical efficiency are rather stochastic in the analyzed countries. Thus, idiosyncratic developments in technical efficiency are observed in agriculture as well as in food-processing industry. The technical efficiency fluctuations may result from shocks associated with the introduction of new technologies, changes in human capital as well as shocks connected with weather conditions and climatic changes.

The meta-frontier analysis did not reveal any significant differences in overall technical efficiency among the countries. This holds for food processing as well as for agricultural level. That is, the most efficient farmers and food processors in the analyzed countries have similar level of technical efficiency.

The total factor productivity (TFP) estimates show significant differences among countries. However, the predominantly negative total factor productivity change is observed in the analyzed period in agriculture as well as food processing industry. The manufacture of bakery products, where the productivity is followed the positive development path in the majority of analyzed countries, is the exception. The scale effect represents the main source of the total factor productivity change in the majority of analyzed sectors and countries. Changes improving scale efficiency and bringing technological progress are required to change this negative TFP development and consequently to generate further economic growth and to increase consumers' welfare. Finally, the meta-frontier analysis shows that TFP differences among the countries exist on both agricultural as well as food processing level. The scale efficiency component is the main source of these differences.

The technical change has positive impact on output quantities. Moreover, it reduces the average costs in food processing industry. The opposite is true for agriculture where the technological regress was estimated. However, the price developments and estimated figures on technical change in the analyzed food chains suggest that the total welfare effects increased in analyzed period. Finally, large companies were identified as the main actors of food chains development.

1. INTRODUCTION

A functional, sustainable, competitive, and structurally balanced agri-food sector has an irreplaceable position in the European economy. The importance of this sector in modern society is emphasized by global trends, among which population explosions, migration waves, and climate change can be highlighted. Additionally, the coronavirus pandemic has strengthened the role of national food security.

Agriculture provides key primary ingredients for the food processing industry represented 1.5 % of the total European Union value added in 2017 and contributes approximately by 4 % to the total employment in the EU-28 (EUROSTAT). The cereal and milk sectors, each representing more than 12 % of total agricultural output, are traditionally the biggest agricultural sectors in the EU (EUROSTAT, 2019). Therefore, these sectors are also in the interest of research analysing the competitiveness and its sources – economies of scale, technical change, and technical efficiency (e.g., Baležentis and Sum, 2020; Pisulewski and Marzec, 2019; Skevas et al., 2018; Madau et al., 2017; Latruffe et al., 2017; Bokusheva and Čechura, 2017; Čechura et al., 2017; Žáková Kroupová, 2016; Labajova et al., 2016; Shortall and Barnes, 2013; Zhu et al., 2012; Latruffe et al., 2012; Zhu and Lansink, 2010).

The food processing industry is one of the most important sectors of the European economy. According to EUROSTAT, it is the largest manufacturing sector in the European Union (EU-28), representing 14 % of total manufacturing employment and 13 % of total manufacturing turnover and 10 % of value added in 2017. The food processing industry encompasses a variety of products. The most important subsectors concerning employment are: manufacture of bakery and farinaceous products (34 % of total employment in the food sector in 2017), meat processing and production of meat products (23 %), and manufacture of dairy products (10 %). Although bakery manufacturing leads in terms of employment, the main turnover producing sector is meat manufacturing (Kapelko, 2019).

The European Commission (2016) as well as Kapelko (2019) show that several economic, social, and technological trends and challenges have affected the development of the European agri-food sector in the last decades: the globalization and liberalization of food markets, the global financial crisis, the change in consumer preferences towards healthy foods, socially responsible consumption, and organic foods, the implementations of EU regulations, especially focusing on food safety and an environmental issue. These trends connected with a high level of market saturation and concentration of food retailing sector (Allendorf and Hirsch, 2015) contribute to a highly competitive environment. To enhance the competitiveness of companies/sectors, managers and policymakers deal with factors determining productivity, that is, the technology in use, the quality of inputs, the ability to efficiently use inputs in the production of outputs, and the exploitation of economies of scale (Čechura et al., 2014).

Wimmer and Sauer (2016) suggest that one way to increase competitiveness is to reduce average costs per unit of output by capturing economies of scale. According to Panzar and Willing (1977), the economies of scale exist in the case of non-constant

returns to scale (RTS). In particular, a technology exhibits increasing/decreasing returns to scale if a proportional increase in all inputs results in a larger/lower than a proportional increase in output. Applied to the cost framework, economies of scale are present if costs increase by a smaller rate than output. Conversely, diseconomies of scale exist when costs increase by a larger rate (Baumole et al., 1982). De Roest et al. (2017) added that economies of scale are related to capital-intensive technological development. The introduction of technological innovation increases productivity and reduces the input costs per unit of product. However, according to previous research, there is no clear evidence of the existence of economies of scale in the European agri-food sector. According to Čechura et al. (2014a) and Čechura et al. (2017) who offer the most comprehensive description of the situation in the European production of cereals, milk, and pork, based on FADN data from the period 2004-2012, the average crop and pork farm in the majority of EU-15 countries exhibits increasing returns to scale but there exist decreasing or constant RTS in the rest of the EU countries. Moreover, the average European dairy farm can be characterized by constant returns to scale. Findings on cereal production were confirmed by Bokusheva and Čechura (2017). Then, previous empirical studies of food processing sector (e.g., Rudinskaya, 2017; Čechura et al., 2014; Soboh et al., 2014) tend to conclude that on average European food processing companies did not benefit from the economies of scale in the last two decades.

The competitiveness could be also increased by the improvement in the producer's ability to produce more with a given vector of inputs (or, to produce the same amount of output using fewer inputs) due to the shift of transformation function over time (Chambers, 1988). This progressive technical change embodies the effect of innovation on production technology. According to Čechura et al. (2014a), technical change was the important factor that contributed predominantly positively to total factor productivity (TFP) development in cereal, milk as well as pork production in majority of the EU countries. However, a lot of empirical studies focused on the European food processing sector found out the presence of technical regress in the last two decades, and e.g., Kapelko (2019), Soboh et al. (2014), Čechura et al. (2014b). Soboh et al. (2014) deduced that the technical regress was probably caused by the tightening of government regulations regarding, e.g. food safety, and packaging, requiring processing firms to take costly additional measures. Kapelko (2019) also suppose that technical regress might be a direct consequence of government regulation.

The induced innovation can lead to a factor-biased technical change that directs the change towards the scarcer and hence more expensive production factor (Hayami and Ruthan, 1970). Depending on changes in relative input prices, technical change can take different directions. For example, in the food processing industry, Čechura et al. (2014b) reveal that the material-saving technical change was pronounced in majority of the European countries in 2005-2012.

The technical efficiency was originally defined by Koopmans (1951) as the situation when an increase in any output is impossible without a reduction in at least one other output or an increase in at least one input, and if a reduction in any input requires an increase in at least one other input or a reduction in at least one output. Debreu (1951) and Farrell (1957) introduced radial measures of technical inefficiency. Fried et al.

(2008) suggested an input-conserving orientation. Their measure is defined as the maximum equi-proportionate reduction in all inputs that is feasible with a given technology and outputs. With an output-augmenting orientation, the measure is defined as the maximum equi-proportionate expansion in all outputs that is feasible with a given technology and inputs. A value of unity indicates the technical efficiency because no radial adjustment is feasible, and a value different from unity indicates the severity of technical inefficiency.

According to Coelli et al. (2005), different methods have been considered for the estimation of technical inefficiency of the production plan. Two widely used approaches are the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA), which is non-parametric and deterministic, and the Stochastic Frontier Analysis (SFA), which is, on the contrary, parametric and stochastic. Each approach owns pros and cons (e.g. Kumbhakar et al., 2015). The DEA approach is computationally simple, but it is sensitive to outliers since the model ignores the measurement error and other sources of statistical noise – all deviations from the frontier are interpreted as the results of technical inefficiency (Coelli et al., 2005).

The stochastic modelling of technical efficiency introduced independently by Meeusen and van den Broeck (1977) and Aigner et al. (1977) is based on a decomposition of error term into a symmetric random error and one-sided technical inefficiency. Since the introduction of this frontier modelling within the context of the panel-data models, there has been considerable research done in order to extend it to generate consistent and unbiased estimates. As mentioned Alem (2018) and Greene (2014), several models have been developed based on assumptions about the temporal behaviour of the inefficiency and accounting for heterogeneity that can be, according to Fried et al. (2008), divided into two categories: observed, which is reflected in measured variables, and unobserved, which is typically interpreted as the effect of unobservable factors on the outcome of interest (Bartolucci et al., 2015).

Initial studies considering the heterogeneity assumed that the time-invariant part in the model represents inefficiency, and the time-varying part represents the firm-specific heterogeneity. Later, the firm-specific heterogeneity was assumed as time-invariant, while the time-variant part was considered as inefficiency (Kumbhakar et al., 2015). The latest approach emphasizes the importance of considering latent heterogeneity to generate an unbiased estimate of time-invariant technical inefficiency, as well as the possibility of efficiency improvement (Tsionas and Kumbhakar, 2011; Badunenko and Kumbhakar, 2016). In this approach, the overall technical inefficiency of a producer can be decomposed to transient and persistent parts. The transient technical inefficiency arises as a result of non-systematic managerial failures that can be resolved in the short term. According to Pisulewski and Marzec (2019) as well as Njuki and Bravo-Ureta (2015), the transient part of inefficiency relates to shocks associated with new production technologies and human capital. Kumbhakar and Lien (2017) add that transient technical efficiency can represent the managerial ability to learning-by-doing. The persistent technical inefficiency, according to Filippini and Greene (2016), represents structural problems in the organization of the production process or a systematic lack of managerial skills. Moreover, it can be an indicator of non-competitive market condition. Badunenko and Kumbhakar (2016) state that persistent inefficiency could not exist in a competitive market, i.e., persistently inefficient firms

would not survive in the business. According to Kumbhakar et al. (2015), the distinction between persistent and transient technical inefficiency has significant political implications because the persistent part of technical inefficiency is unchangeable without a new policy or fundamental change in ownership and management of companies. The transient technical inefficiency can be adjusted over time without a major policy change.

The properties of the abovementioned models are described e.g. by Kumbhakar et al. (2015). Comparison of the majority of SFA panel-data models proving the sensitivity of technical efficiency estimates to the model specification is presented by Alem (2018) and Rashidghalam et al. (2016). Moreover, Badunenko and Kumbhakar (2016) provide the judgement of the reliability of transient and persistent technical efficiency estimates.

Technical efficiency and productivity, as important factors determining the competitiveness, have received special attention in the research of agri-food sector over the last decade, e.g. for agriculture Addo and Salhofer (2019), Pisulewski and Marzec (2019), Rudinskaya et al. (2019), Skevas et al. (2018), Bokusheva and Čechura (2017), Čechura et al. (2017), Madau et al. (2017), Latruffe et al. (2017), Nowak et al. (2016), Rasmussen (2010), and for food processing industry Kapelko (2019); Kapelko et al. (2017); Čechura and Hockmann (2017); Rudinskaya (2017); Kapelko et al. (2015); Allendorf and Hirsch (2015); Špička (2015); Soboh et al. (2014); Čechura et al. (2014b); Čechura (2012); Setiawan et al. (2012); Dimara et al. (2008). These studies confirmed that intra- and inter-sectoral heterogeneity are important characteristics in European agriculture as well as the food processing industry. As far as the technical efficiency is concerned, most of these studies analyzed only one type of technical efficiency, especially time-varying one, and reveal that on average the farms and food processing companies highly exploit their production possibilities. However, the substantial differences between the best and the worst producers were found out. The approach considering persistent as well as transient technical efficiency was empirically applied by Addo and Salhofer (2019), Pisulewski and Marzec (2019), Bokusheva and Čechura (2017). All these authors analyzed the technical efficiency of European crop production and observed that a high number of crop producers lag behind best practices in the long-term compared to the representation of the producers that are lagging behind in the short-time period.

This deliverable complements the research by the estimation of input distance functions using the stochastic frontier approach to obtain information on technical efficiency, heterogeneity, technological change and economies of scale exploited in selected sectors of the European agri-food supply chain. To our knowledge, this is the first study analyzing the transient and persistent efficiency of food processing industry in the EU considering an endogeneity due to both potential sources, i.e. a) firm heterogeneity and b) simultaneity of input use decisions and technical efficiency.

Moreover, we will use the results in the analysis and discussion on the impact of technical change on consumer and producer rents and the total welfare effects, as an indirect measure of economic sustainability. Finally, we will identify the main actors and main innovations driving the development of the food sectors.

This study addresses the following research questions:

- (i) The first question relates to the efficiency of input use. In particular, we will evaluate how well the firms/farms employ the inputs in the transformation process. We will distinguish two components of technical efficiency - the transient technical efficiency representing short-term deviations from frontier and persistent technical efficiency that captures systematic deviations from frontier technology.
- (ii) The second question deals with technological change. We will provide evidence on the shift of frontier technology (increase in the input productivity) due to the technological progress.
- (iii) Then, the third question aims to address the question whether the firm/farm exploit the economies of scale. That is, whether the firm/farm has an optimal size. On the other hand, diseconomies of scale represent the production with increasing or decreasing returns to scale, i.e. the situation when the proportionate increase in all inputs results in larger or less than proportionate increase in the output, respectively (Baumol et al., 1982).
- (iv) The fourth question relates to the levels and developments of efficiency and productivity measures in analyzed EU member states – intra as well as cross-country comparison.
- (v) The last question deals with the impact of technological change on the rents and total welfare effects in the food value chains.

The study is organized as follows: Chapter 2 presents the estimation strategy; Chapter 3 describes the data set; Chapter 4 presents (a) results for the country input distance function estimates, compares the estimated technology, economies of scale, and technical change, and analysis of the technical efficiency, as well as total factor productivity, (b) results of meta-frontier analysis for selected sectors of agri-food supply chain. Chapter 5 provides findings and implications on the impact of technological change on prices, quantities, the rents and total welfare effects in the food value chains. Chapter 6 presents concluding remarks.

2. METHODOLOGY

In this section, we introduce the methodological framework used in the analysis of the technical efficiency, firm heterogeneity, the exploitation of economies of scale, as well as the impact of technical changes on both agricultural and processing levels of the selected European agri-food supply chains.¹

The research questions will be dealt with (1) estimation of country-specific input distance function (IDF) for the sectors on producer level (agriculture) using the FADN database and on processor level (food processing industry) using the Amadeus database for slaughtering, dairy, milling and bakery industry and the combination of KONTALI salmon industry report³ and 'Purehelp'⁴ for salmon production. In addition, using the IDF estimates we provide calculation of the productivity index in both agri-food chain levels; (2) Then, based on the IDF parameters the efficient input level will be calculated and further used in a meta-frontier approach to compare technical efficiency and total factor productivity. (3) Finally, we will use the results in the analysis and discussion on the impact of technical change on prices, quantities, consumer and producer rents and the total welfare effects.

2.1 INPUT DISTANCE FUNCTION

The analysis is based on an assumption that the transformation process is well approximated by an input-distance function (IDF) that measures the largest factor of proportionality ρ by which the input vector \mathbf{x} can be scaled down in order to produce a given output vector \mathbf{y} with the technology existing at a particular time t (Caves et al., 1982). The IDF is formally defined as:

$$D^I(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x}, t) = \max \{ \rho : \mathbf{x}/\rho \in L(\mathbf{y}) \}, \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{x} denotes the input vector, \mathbf{y} denotes the output vector, t is a time variable, and $L(\mathbf{y})$ represents the input requirement set. For any input-output combination (\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) belonging to the technology set, the input distance function takes a value no smaller than unity. Figure 1 presents that when x_{1A} and x_{2A} are used to produce output \mathbf{y} , then $\rho = OA/OB > 1$. According to Karagiannis et al. (2004), a value of unity simply indicates that the input-output combination (\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) belongs to the input isoquant which represents the minimum input quantities that are necessary to produce a given output vector \mathbf{y} (see points B and C in Figure 1).

In other words, if $D^I(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x}, t) = 1$, the given output vector \mathbf{y} is produced with the minimum amount of inputs at a given time and with the given technology and a firm is technically efficient (Caves et al., 1982). That is, the IDF provides a measure of technical efficiency since its reciprocal to the Farrell (1957) input-based technical efficiency: $TE^I = \frac{1}{D^I(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x}, t)}$.

¹ The selection of the countries covers EU member states involved in the project.

Figure 1 - Input distance function for two inputs. (Source: Coelli et al., 2015)

The IDF exhibits the following properties (Greene, 2005): symmetry, monotonicity, linear homogeneity, and concavity in inputs and quasi-concavity in outputs. For the interpretation of the empirical estimates, the duality between the cost and input distance functions is another important property: $C(w, y, t) = \min_x \{wx : D^I(y, x, t) \geq 1\}$, where w denotes a vector of input prices. The minimisation problem provides the relation between the derivatives of the IDF and the cost function (Irz and Thirtle, 2005).

In particular, the derivative with respect to j^{th} input gives: $\frac{\partial D^I(x^*(w,y,t),y,t)}{\partial x_j} = \frac{w_j}{C(w,y,t)} = r_j^*(x, y, t)$. That is, the derivative of the input distance function with respect to a particular input is equal to the cost-deflated shadow price of that input. More conveniently, in terms of the log derivative of the distance function, we can rewrite this expression to $\frac{\partial \ln D^I(x^*(w,y,t),y,t)}{\partial \ln x_j} = \frac{w_j x_j^*(w,y,t)}{C(w,y,t)} = S_{j,t}$, where $S_{j,t}$ is a cost-share of the particular input.

With respect to the output vector y , application of the envelope theorem to the minimisation problem $C(w, y, t) = \min_x \{wx : D^I(y, x, t) \geq 1\}$ leads to: $\frac{\partial \ln D^I(x^*(w,y,t),y,t)}{\partial \ln y_m} = -\frac{\partial \ln C(w,y,t)}{\partial \ln y_m} = e_{mit}$. Hence, the elasticity of the IDF with respect to m^{th} output is therefore equal to the negative of the cost elasticity of that output and as such it informs about the importance of m^{th} output in terms of cost. In other words, the negative of this elasticity ($-e_{mit}$), conditioned by the inputs and outputs in the IDF, represents the percentage input expansion required for a 1% increase in y_m , holding all input ratios and the other output constant (Singbo and Larue, 2016).

In our analysis, the IDF is estimated in a translog functional form. This second-order local approximation of any twice-differentiable function satisfied Diewert's minimum flexibility requirement for flexible form (see Pisulewski & Marzec, 2019). The translog input distance function for M-outputs (y), J-inputs (x), and time (t) is defined as:

$$\ln D_{it}^I = \alpha_0 + \sum_{m=1}^M \alpha_m \ln y_{m,it} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^M \alpha_{mn} \ln y_{m,it} \ln y_{n,it} + \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^J \gamma_{mj} \ln y_{m,it} \ln x_{j,it} + \sum_{j=1}^J \beta_j \ln x_{j,it} +$$

$$+ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^J \sum_{k=1}^K \beta_{jk} \ln x_{j,it} \ln x_{k,it} + \delta_t t + \frac{1}{2} \delta_{tt} t^2 + \sum_{m=1}^M \delta_{mt} \ln y_{m,it} + \sum_{j=1}^J \delta_{jt} \ln x_{j,it} t, \quad (2)$$

where subscripts i , with $i=1,2,\dots,N$, and t , with $t=1,\dots,T$, refer to a certain firm/farm and time (year), respectively. α , β , γ , and δ are vectors of the parameters to be estimated. The symmetry restrictions imply that $\beta_{jk} = \beta_{kj}$ and $\alpha_{mn} = \alpha_{nm}$. The time trend included in the IDF allows for capturing the joint effects of embedded knowledge, technology improvements and learning-by-doing in input quality improvements (see Čechura et al., 2017). Here, δ_t and δ_{tt} capture the global effect of technical change on the IDF (see Figure 2), while δ_{mt} and δ_{jt} measure the bias of technical change.

Figure 2 - Technical change. (Source: Chambers, 1988)

The IDF is homogenous of degree 1 in inputs. According to Sipiläinen (2007), it requires:

$$\sum_{j=1}^J \beta_j = 1; \sum_{j=1}^J \beta_{jk} = 0; \sum_{j=1}^J \gamma_{mj} = 0; \sum_{j=1}^J \delta_{jt} = 0. \quad (3)$$

Implying the homogeneity property of the IDF (Knox Lovell et al., 1994) that is imposed by normalising all the inputs by one input, we can rewrite the IDF as:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln D_{it}^I - \ln x_{1,it} &= \alpha_0 + \sum_{m=1}^M \alpha_m \ln y_{m,it} + \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N \alpha_{mn} \ln y_{m,it} \ln y_{n,it} + \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{j=2}^J \gamma_{mj} \ln y_{m,it} \ln \tilde{x}_{j,it} + \sum_{j=2}^J \beta_j \ln \tilde{x}_{j,it} + \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=2}^J \sum_{k=2}^K \beta_{jk} \ln \tilde{x}_{j,it} \ln \tilde{x}_{k,it} + \delta_t t + \frac{1}{2} \delta_{tt} t^2 + \sum_{m=1}^M \delta_{mt} \ln y_{m,it} + \sum_{j=2}^J \delta_{jt} \ln \tilde{x}_{j,it} t, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $\ln \tilde{x}_{j,it} = \ln x_{j,it} - \ln x_{1,it}$.

Moreover, we normalize all variables in logarithm by their sample mean. In this case, we may interpret the first-order parameters as output elasticities and input cost shares, evaluated on the sample mean, respectively.

After introducing statistical error term (v_{it}), latent heterogeneity (μ_i), and replacing $\ln D_{it}^I$ with inefficiency terms: persistent technical inefficiency (η_i) and transient technical inefficiency (u_{it}), that is $\eta_i + u_{it} = \ln D_{it}^I$, the IDF takes the form of a Generalized True Random Effect model (GTRE, see Kumbhakar and Tsionas, 2012):

$$\begin{aligned}
 -\ln x_{1it} = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{m=1}^M \alpha_m \ln y_{m,it} + \\
 & + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N \alpha_{mn} \ln y_{m,it} \ln y_{n,it} + \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{j=2}^J \gamma_{mj} \ln y_{m,it} \ln \tilde{x}_{j,it} + \sum_{j=2}^J \beta_j \ln \tilde{x}_{j,it} + \\
 & + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=2}^J \sum_{k=2}^K \beta_{jk} \ln \tilde{x}_{j,it} \ln \tilde{x}_{k,it} + \delta_t t + \frac{1}{2} \delta_{tt} t^2 + \sum_{m=1}^M \delta_{mt} \ln y_{m,it} t + \\
 & + \sum_{j=2}^J \delta_{jt} \ln \tilde{x}_{j,it} t - \eta_i - u_{it} + v_{it},
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

where $v_{it} \sim N(0, \sigma_v^2)$, $u_{it} \sim N^+(0, \sigma_u^2)$, $\eta_i \sim N^+(0, \sigma_\eta^2)$.

To sum up, the elasticities of the IDF with respect to inputs equal to the cost shares and reflect the relative importance of the inputs in the production process. The elasticities of outputs correspond to the negative of the cost elasticities of each output and reflect the relative importance of the outputs. Furthermore, the returns to scale can be quantified from the IDF elasticities with respect to outputs based on Rasmussen (2010):

$$RTS = -[\sum_{m=1}^M e_{mit}]^{-1}, \tag{6}$$

where $e_{mit} = \frac{\partial \ln D_{it}^I}{\partial \ln y_{m,it}}$ is the IDF elasticity with respect to output m .

Figure 3 - Economies and diseconomies of scale. (Source: Sloman and Wride, 2009)

2.2 HETEROGENEITY IN TECHNOLOGY

The literature provides broad evidence on significant heterogeneity in both agricultural as well as processing technology. The heterogeneity in agriculture technology is captured by a latent heterogeneity (μ_i) component in (5).

Since we estimate a joint country input distance function for all analyzed processing industries (due to the data limitation)² we need to consider two types of heterogeneity of processing technology, i.e. the potential existence of inter- and intra-sector heterogeneity. To capture the inter-sector heterogeneity, first-order parameters in (5) are expanded based on dummy variables for analyzed food processing industries:

² The low number of observations in an industry does not allow to estimate country IDF for each processing sector in majority of countries.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \alpha_{ms} &= \alpha_m + \sum_s \alpha_s d_s, \forall m \\
 \beta_{js} &= \beta_j + \sum_s \beta_s d_s, \forall j \\
 \delta_{ts} &= \delta_t + \sum_s \delta_s d_s,
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

where d represents dummy variables which account for inter-sectoral differences in technology.

The intra-sector heterogeneity is captured by μ_i in (5). Analogically to the random effect model, the GTRE assumes that μ_i are independent of explanatory variables. The violation of this assumption can originate from the heterogeneity bias as a kind of omitted variable bias that is a typical problem of hierarchical data. To deal with this heterogeneity bias, we apply the Mundlak's (1978) formulation and add group-means for each time-varying explanatory variable in first-order level as an alternative to GMM estimates (see Chapter 2.3).

2.3 ESTIMATION STRATEGY

The estimation strategy involves new advances in productivity and efficiency analysis. We introduced a model with 4 components: two components of technical efficiency, heterogeneity effect and statistical noise. Then, since the endogeneity problem usually frustrates the researchers in productivity and efficiency analysis and leads to inconsistent estimates, we will use the methods which controls for the potential endogeneity of netputs and thereby allows to obtain consistent estimates of technology, as well as productivity and efficiency measures. We address two potential sources of endogeneity (due to the heterogeneity and due to simultaneity of input with technical efficiency) by using system GMM estimator. In particular, GMM estimator allows to deal with endogeneity bias that arises when one or more explanatory variables are correlated with the error term. This correlation can have different origins, e.g. measurement errors, omitted variables bias, and simultaneity (see Ullah et al., 2018).

However, if the GMM estimator does not provide valid estimates, our second choice is the GTRE model with Mundlak's adjustment that address the endogeneity due to the heterogeneity. Finally, GTRE model estimate serves as a baseline for model comparisons. If we get the valid GMM model estimates for all IDF estimates in the analyzed sector, we present only these preferable results.

Estimation procedure with GTRE, GTRE with Mundlak and GMM models

The estimation of the GTRE model and the GTRE model with Mundlak's adjustment is undertaken as a multistep procedure. We follow Kumbhakar et al. (2014) and rewrite the model in (5) as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 -\ln x_{1it} &= \alpha_0^* + \sum_{m=1}^M \alpha_{ms} \ln y_{m,it} + \\
 &+ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{n=1}^N \alpha_{mn} \ln y_{m,it} \ln y_{n,it} + \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{j=1}^J \gamma_{mj} \ln y_{m,it} \ln \tilde{x}_{j,it} + \sum_{j=1}^J \beta_{js} \ln \tilde{x}_{j,it} + \\
 &+ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^J \sum_{k=1}^K \beta_{jk} \ln \tilde{x}_{j,it} \ln \tilde{x}_{k,it} + \delta_{ts} t + \frac{1}{2} \delta_{tt} t^2 + \sum_{m=1}^M \delta_{mt} \ln y_{m,it} t + \\
 &+ \sum_{j=1}^J \delta_{jt} \ln \tilde{x}_{j,it} t + \alpha_i + \varepsilon_{it}, \tag{8}
 \end{aligned}$$

where $\alpha_0^* = \alpha_0 - E(\eta_i) - E(u_{it})$, $\alpha_i = \mu_i - (\eta_i - E(\eta_i))$ and $\varepsilon_{it} = v_{it} - (u_{it} - E(u_{it}))$.

This specification ensures that α_i and ε_{it} have zero mean and constant variance. The multistep procedure consists of three steps. In step 1, the standard random effect panel regression is used to estimate β , γ , δ , α_m , and theoretical values of α_i and ε_{it} , denoted by $\hat{\alpha}_i$ and $\widehat{\varepsilon}_{it}$. In step 2, the transient technical inefficiency, u_{it} , is estimated using $\widehat{\varepsilon}_{it}$ and the standard stochastic frontier technique with assumptions: $v_{it} \sim N(0, \sigma_v^2)$, $u_{it} \sim N^+(0, \sigma_u^2)$. In step 3, the persistent technical inefficiency, η_i , is estimated using $\hat{\alpha}_i$ and the stochastic frontier model with the following assumptions: $\mu_i \sim N(0, \sigma_\mu^2)$, $\eta_i \sim N^+(0, \sigma_\eta^2)$. These steps are done in the SW STATA 14.0.

Furthermore, the total technical efficiency (OTE) is quantified based on Kumbhakar et al. (2014):

$$OTE_{it} = \exp(-\hat{\eta}_i) * \exp(-\hat{u}_{it}). \tag{9}$$

The GMM model extends this estimation procedure. We follow Bokusheva and Čechura (2017) four-steps procedure. In step 1, the two-step System Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) estimator (Arellano and Bover, 1995; Blundell and Bond, 1998) is used to obtain consistent estimates of the IDF parameters. The Arellano and Bover(1995)/Blundell and Bond (1998) approach builds a system of two equations – the original equation (in levels) and the transform one (in differences) and employs two types of instruments: the level instruments for the differenced equations and the lagged differences for the equations in levels (Roodman, 2009). The validity of these instruments is tested by the Hansen J test (Hansen, 1982), which analyses the joint validity of the instruments, and Arellano-Bond (1991) test to analyze the autocorrelation in the idiosyncratic disturbance term (v_{it}) that could render some lags invalid as instruments. In step 2, residuals are used from the system GMM level equations to estimate a random effects panel model employing the Generalized Least Squares (GLS) estimator. The transient and persistent technical inefficiency is estimated in steps 3 and 4 based on the same procedure as is described above. These estimates are done also in the SW STATA 14.0.

2.4 TOTAL FACTOR PRODUCTIVITY AND ITS DECOMPOSITION

Productivity is commonly defined as a ratio of a volume measure of output to a volume measure of input use (O'Donnell, 2012). Productivity can be measured at different levels, as partial measures (e.g. labour productivity) or as a multifactor measure. The most comprehensive measure is total factor productivity (TFP), which is a ratio of aggregated outputs and inputs. Our analysis measures firm-level TFP change employing the Törnqvist-Theil index (TTI), which is defined as the ratio of the revenue-share weighted geometric mean of individual outputs to the cost-share weighted geometric mean of individual inputs (Coelli et al., 2015). According to Bokusheva and Čechura (2017), the logarithmic form of TTI is given by:

$$\ln\left(\frac{TFP_{it}}{TFP_{i(t-1)}}$$

where $R_m = \frac{p_m y_m}{\sum_{m=1}^M p_m y_m}$ are output revenue shares and $S_j = \frac{w_j x_j}{\sum_{j=1}^J w_j x_j}$ are input cost shares.

As was shown by Diewert (1976), the TTI exactly determines changes in production that result from input adjustments when the underlying production technology is described using translog functional form. Consequently, the TTI can be derived based on parameter estimates of the translog IDF in (8) as the sum of three components: scale effect (SEC = $\ln l_{it}$), technical efficiency effect (TEC = $\ln v_{it}$) and technical change (TC = $\ln \tau_{it}$) effect:

$$\ln TFP_{it} = \ln l_{it} + \ln v_{it} + \ln \tau_{it}. \quad (11)$$

The scale effect captures the contribution of economies of scale and, according to Bokusheva and Čechura (2017), it is measured as the difference between two output indices: the one measured assuming constant returns to scale and the other calculated under the assumption that the underlying technology is characterized by varying returns to scale. After accounting for deviations from the sample means, this results in the following expression:

$$\ln l_{it} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{m=1}^M [(\zeta_{it,m} + \bar{\zeta}_m) (\ln y_{it,m} - \overline{\ln x_m}) + \bar{\zeta}_m \overline{\ln y_m} - \overline{\zeta_{it,m} \ln y_{it,m}}], \quad (12)$$

where $\zeta_{it,m} = (1 - RTS^{-1}) \frac{\partial \ln D^I(x_{it}^*, y_{it}, t)}{\partial \ln y_{it,m}}$ and $RTS^{-1} = \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{\partial \ln D^I(x_{it}^*, y_{it}, t)}{\partial \ln y_{it,m}}$.

The technical efficiency effect is associated with movements towards (away from) the frontier and can be measured as a derivation from the sample mean:

$$\ln v_{it} = \ln TE_{it} - \overline{\ln TE_{it}}, \quad (13)$$

where $TE_{it} = \exp(-\hat{u}_{it})$.

Finally, the technical change component captures the shift of frontier and similarly to technical efficiency change can be measured as a derivation from the sample mean:

$$\ln \tau_{it} = \varphi_{it} - \overline{\varphi_{it}}, \quad (14)$$

where $\varphi_{it} = -\frac{\partial \ln D^I(x_{it}^*, y_{it}, t)}{\partial \ln t}$.

2.5 META-FRONTIER ANALYSIS

The technical efficiencies of firms/farms estimated from a country-specific input distance function are not comparable with those of firms/farms operating in a different country, exactly operating under different technologies. As explain O'Donnell et al. (2008), technology sets in European countries differ “because of differences in available stocks of physical, human, and financial capital, economic infrastructure, resources endowments, and other characteristics of the physical, social and economic environment in which production takes place”.

The calculation of comparable technical efficiencies for firms/farms operating under different technologies is in our analysis, analogically to Battese et al. (2004), enabled by a meta-frontier model that is defined in line with Ruttan et al. (1978) as the envelope of the production points of the most efficient countries. That is, the stochastic meta-frontier is based on the fitted country-frontier estimates. In particular, we follow Huang's et al. (2014) two-step stochastic frontier approach to estimate the country-specific frontier and the meta-frontier. In the first step, we calculate the efficient inputs based on estimates of the country input distance function (more precisely based on estimates of overall technical efficiency) and use them to estimate a stochastic meta-frontier input distance function in the second step.

The estimation strategy of meta-frontier models is the same as for the country IDF models. The estimations are done in the SW STATA 14.0 and further employed to compute a country-level TFP change employing the Törnqvist-Theil index (see Chapter 2.4).

3. DATA

3.1 FOOD PROCESSING INDUSTRY

The panel data set is drawn from the Amadeus database collected by Bureau van Dijk - Moody's Analytics company. The database contains information on around 21 million European companies and provides detailed information about company financials in a standard format, financial strength indicators, sectoral activities, and corporate structures. Our analysis uses information from the final accounts of companies whose main activity is food processing (Division C10: Manufacture of food products according to the Statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community, abbreviated as NACE) in the period from 2006 till 2018. Moreover, we concentrated on the analysis of four food processing sectors (the NACE classification):

- C10.1 Processing and preserving of meat and production of meat products (including subgroups: 10.11, 10.12, 10.13);
- C10.5 Manufacture of dairy products (including subgroups: 10.51, 10.52);
- C10.6 Manufacture of grain mill products, starches, and starch products (including subgroups: 10.61, 10.62);
- C10.7 Manufacture of bakery and farinaceous products (including subgroups: 10.71, 10.72, 10.73).

Table 1 - Structure of the data set – food processing. (Source: Amadeus database and own calculations)

	NACE									
	10.1		10.5		10.6		10.7		Total	
Country	I	N	I	N	I	N	I	N	I	N
Austria	15	120	15	131	4	17	8	53	92	677
Belgium	91	720	40	336	23	197	67	538	492	3,641
Czechia	194	1,466	58	498	49	382	335	2,372	1,245	8,828
Finland	98	747	36	285	33	263	229	1,656	742	5,317
France	659	5,997	211	1,940	129	1,184	929	8,033	3,048	26,911
Germany	125	674	80	658	26	199	100	536	663	4,140
Ireland	18	114	2	14	3	22	8	48	48	302
Italy	400	3,769	97	915	63	586	212	1,910	1,689	15,436
Romania	468	3,831	314	2,564	383	2,876	2,408	18,263	4,559	34,885
Spain	462	4,498	114	1,108	71	690	307	2,849	1,937	18,203
Sweden	171	1,229	22	150	23	155	301	1,896	847	5,616
United Kingdom	132	1,012	62	496	28	273	90	687	802	5,932
Total	2,833	24,177	1,051	9,095	835	6,844	4,994	38,841	16,164	129,888

Note: I is the total number of firms, N is the total number of observations; the column Total represents also data from the rest sectors of division C10.

Since not all companies in the database have the complete information, we exclude observations of those companies with negative and zero values of the variables of interest. Moreover, companies with fewer than at least three consecutive observations were rejected from the dataset. This procedure decreases the problem associated with the entry and exit of producers from the database and allows the use of GMM estimator

with sufficient number of lagged instruments³. Thus, we were constrained to the use of an unbalanced panel data set containing 16,164 food processing companies with 129,888 observations. The structure of the data set is presented in Table 1.

For the estimation of the IDF in this study, we use the following outputs and inputs: Output (y), Labour (xL), Capital (xC) and Material (xM). The output is represented by operating revenue (Turnover) deflated by the sectoral index of food processing prices (EU level or country level if it was disposable, respectively; 2010 = 100) and changes in company's stock. Labour is represented by the cost of employees deflated by the index of producer prices in the industry (country level; 2010 = 100). Capital is the book value of fixed assets deflated by the index of producer prices in the industry (country level; 2010 = 100). Finally, Material is the total cost of materials and energy deflated by the index of producer prices in the industry (country level; 2010 = 100). The source of price indexes is EUROSTAT database. Table 2 provides the sample descriptive statistics.

Table 2 - Descriptive statistics – food processing. (Source: Amadeus database and own calculations)

Country	Output		Labour		Capital		Material	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Austria	134,372	287,839	15,689	21,729	35,333	61,595	69,752	97,967
Belgium	72,488	171,197	7,083	14,953	56,389	484,062	48,874	136,966
Czechia	11,622	36,663	1,152	3,386	4,129	19,637	7,559	21,815
Finland	24,942	151,551	3,970	27,956	7,356	48,804	14,561	91,981
France	20,834	112,196	2,334	9,931	5,272	31,639	12,357	77,836
Germany	148,952	442,922	14,828	48,951	38,320	208,665	103,538	315,380
Ireland	81,257	304,112	7,090	26,613	23,103	110,578	59,899	224,163
Italy	24,521	105,345	2,515	13,432	9,776	59,451	16,271	71,800
Romania	2,615	14,114	236	1,155	1,160	6,823	1,675	8,691
Spain	23,398	98,955	2,460	12,656	9,582	56,264	15,562	67,418
Sweden	12,298	44,531	1,918	6,516	4,474	45,935	7,510	28,519
United Kingdom	150,343	524,553	20,448	72,532	80,455	671,243	88,764	217,128

3.2 AGRICULTURE

3.2.1 CEREALS AND MILK PRODUCTION

The analysis of agriculture uses a panel data set drawn from the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN) database provided by the European Commission. The database contains information on approximately 80.000 agricultural holdings across the European Union and provides harmonised microeconomic data (physical as well as financial data). Our dataset involves 12 selected countries and covers the period from 2004 to 2017. These country samples of farms consist of specialised cereals, field

³ In this case, we compromised between the number of observations in particular processing industry and minimum requirements of GMM estimator.

crops, mixed crops, and mixed crops and livestock farms according to the FADN farm typology. Similarly to the food processing industry, observations of those farms with negative and zero values of the variables of interest are excluded from the data set and the data set is generated by keeping in the sample only farms with at least five (three in the case of Belgium and four in the case of Ireland) consecutive years of observations.⁴ The final sample size is presented in Table 3.

Table 3 - Structure of the data set - agriculture. (Source: FADN database and own calculation)

Country	Cereals		Milk	
	I	N	I	N
Austria	847	7,875	1,086	11,651
Belgium	349	1,615	405	3,903
Czechia	633	5,886	500	4,671
Finland	386	3,084	385	3,913
France	1,349	10,262	2,025	18,225
West Germany	1,717	12,302	1,946	15,193
East Germany	556	4,290	492	3,988
Ireland	191	1,504	363	3,375
Italy	527	3,599	1,055	7,939
Romania	479	2,898	425	2,603
Spain	275	1,950	655	5,515
Sweden	545	4,636	380	3,078
United Kingdom	342	2,484	415	3,553
Total	8,196	62,385	10,132	87,607

Note: I is the total number of firms, N is the total number of observations.

For the estimation of the IDF in this study, we define the following vectors of outputs and inputs.

Cereal production:

Cereals output is defined as the value of cereals production; other crops output, measured as the difference between the value of total crops output minus cereals output; and other farm output, calculated as the difference between the value of farm total output and the value of total crops output. The vector of inputs consists of: capital, represented by the sum of contract work and capital depreciation; land, expressed in hectares of farm Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA); labour, measured in AWU; and materials, defined as total intermediate consumption (the sum of farm total crop and livestock production specific costs and total farming overheads without contract work). Material was used to normalize the three other input variables.

Milk production:

Milk output is defined as the value of milk production; other livestock production, measured as the difference between the value of livestock output minus milk output; and other farm output, calculated as the difference between the value of farm total output and the value of total livestock output. The vector of inputs consists of: capital,

⁴ In the case of Belgium and Ireland, we again compromised between the number of observations and minimum requirements of GMM estimator. 5 consecutive observations for other countries provide more flexibility for the selection of valid set of instruments.

represented by the sum of contract work and capital depreciation; land, expressed in hectares of farm Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA); labour, measured in AWU; and materials, defined as total intermediate consumption (the sum of farm total crop and livestock production specific costs and total farming overheads without contract work). Material was used to normalize the three other input variables.

Monetary variables are deflated using the price indices from the EUROSTAT database (2010 = 100). The price index for crop and milk output and agricultural goods output (Eurostat, 2019) were used to deflate output variables. The price index for machinery and other equipment was used to adjust the capital input and the price index for goods and services currently consumed in agriculture was employed to deflate materials. The sample descriptive statistics of the variables of interest are provided in Table 4 and Table 5.

Table 4 - Descriptive statistics – cereal production. (Source: FADN database and own calculation)

Cereals	Cereals		Other crops output		Other farm output		Land		Labour		Capital		Material	
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.
Austria	15,417	20,028	16,737	32,002	52,987	46,401	45	31	2	1	24,585	13,059	42,770	28,115
Belgium	17,089	18,411	21,473	36,696	105,970	84,899	77	40	2	1	32,720	20,423	84,253	53,677
Czechia	248,464	311,635	286,862	377,956	535,011	726,231	892	888	27	30	165,803	189,964	887,039	1,016,550
Finland	21,605	20,528	21,014	36,388	80,314	107,819	91	57	2	1	45,277	39,160	106,453	91,292
France	52,108	44,601	34,662	62,388	96,997	105,475	155	93	2	1	56,960	39,316	119,669	80,473
West Germany	24,401	23,206	24,283	66,459	96,032	89,538	77	50	2	1	32,497	23,617	96,019	67,978
East Germany	229,806	292,821	200,803	283,160	680,657	1,090,987	705	764	13	17	195,453	237,536	796,778	1,104,694
Ireland	24,538	27,941	14,234	20,445	74,099	85,655	81	47	2	1	23,015	16,990	74,770	59,681
Italy	11,451	20,062	20,840	32,859	49,307	67,007	47	61	2	1	15,066	18,026	42,111	49,118
Romania	15,174	66,626	16,812	56,402	21,845	77,854	58	205	3	8	6,549	26,133	30,999	124,992
Spain	29,490	30,816	17,804	26,344	61,276	90,510	115	105	2	1	17,228	21,317	73,388	79,755
Sweden	26,610	36,199	40,905	52,807	119,762	155,523	119	104	2	1	40,245	41,893	140,484	135,649
United Kingdom	38,336	44,355	31,741	44,102	107,915	106,672	154	120	2	1	40,357	29,960	134,717	93,772

Table 5 - Descriptive statistics – milk production. (Source: FADN database and own calculation)

Milk	Milk		Other animal production		Plant production		Land		Labour		Capital		Material	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
Austria	43,069	32,850	14,359	11,814	22,111	23,586	36	30	2	1	24,228	13,109	40,747	24,442
Belgium	106,147	71,886	56,360	62,633	45,620	52,642	69	40	2	1	42,748	25,660	114,508	68,474
Czechia	481,302	442,284	200,250	260,303	729,055	823,571	1,108	924	37	33	198,178	199,892	1,148,982	1,123,097
Finland	132,894	103,088	12,344	12,150	26,739	31,007	72	45	2	1	58,128	50,825	136,274	96,237
France	122,814	73,548	40,478	43,967	48,730	62,290	121	76	2	1	63,947	39,195	127,260	80,847
West Germany	107,930	91,658	32,516	34,689	33,435	38,566	71	44	2	1	36,401	25,701	109,656	74,463
East Germany	767,098	845,925	205,465	369,172	905,450	1,232,835	932	865	20	23	297,245	301,271	1,302,281	1,491,043
Ireland	108,158	73,090	35,304	34,676	12,007	14,550	64	34	2	1	15,157	19,134	120,637	121,051
Italy	86,564	107,141	17,221	23,138	29,921	49,432	40	58	2	1	17,017	17,361	73,517	90,356
Romania	15,547	56,065	6,083	22,486	34,335	181,641	57	239	3	8	6,502	34,994	32,366	146,738

Spain	132,696	131,132	19,071	24,814	14,741	18,061	32	44	2	1	15,157	19,134	120,637	121,051
Sweden	153,291	155,422	23,681	29,048	69,439	78,549	109	105	2	2	47,417	48,410	179,945	171,093
United Kingdom	228,476	239,705	49,302	44,077	39,291	56,536	108	84	3	2	45,965	34,117	211,422	206,848

3.3 SALMON PRODUCTION

In the case of salmon industry, the dataset, covers the period 2008-2018 and is drawn from two main sources. The list of enterprises is selected from the KONTALI salmon industry report³. These are the large enterprises in salmon industry of Norway. Later on, the financial data which is reported by this enterprise are extracted from 'Purehelp'⁴. It is a major Norway business search engine. They pile reported financial data from companies. Moreover, the size of salmon harvest and number of licenses are extracted from KONTALI reports for different years. By using the data explained above, we use the following variables in IDF model: output which is total revenue. Labour costs are represented by the costs of employees and material costs by product consumption per company. Output is deflated by the sectoral index of food processing prices (2015 = 100). Capital is represented by total fixed assets. Material and Capital are deflated by the index of producer prices in the industry (2015 = 100) and Labour by the consumer price index (2015 = 100). Material and labour are normalized by capital.

We excluded producers with fewer than four observations to comply with the requirements of applied system GMM estimator. Moreover, we decrease the problem with the use of unbalanced panel data this way.

3.4 ITALIAN TOMATO PROCESSING

The data we use in the analysis is drawn from the Amadeus database. The data were selected in the desk research identifying only the tomato processors among other processors in NACE - C10.3 (Processing and preserving of fruit and vegetables). That is, the panel data set that we use in our analysis contains companies whose main activity is tomato food processing according to the NACE classification and desk investigation of each company website. It is a panel data set which represents the period from 2006 to 2018 and contains 97 companies, processing only tomato or processing mainly tomato.

The variables used in the analysis are analogical to the variables that we use for other analyzed food processing industries with data source in Amadeus database. Moreover, we rejected processors with fewer than four observations to comply with the requirements of applied system GMM estimator.

4. RESULTS

4.1 FOOD PROCESSING INDUSTRY

4.1.1 COUNTRY INPUT DISTANCE FUNCTION ESTIMATES

4.1.1.1 MODEL COMPARISON

We initiate the analysis with the comparison of model alternatives. Based on both economic, and statistical criteria, we compare three models – GTRE, GTRE with Mundlak, and GMM model. Economic criterion represents the requirement that the model meets the theoretical assumptions of the input distance function. Once those assumptions are met, the statistical significance of fitted parameters is tested, and, in case of GMM model, also the validity of model must be proved by AR(2) and Hansen J-tests.

Table 6 summarizes the main properties of the estimates of given alternative specifications. The estimates in detail of the country input distance functions and the results of statistical tests are provided in Annex I Table A1-A12.

The IDF estimates should satisfy the properties of monotonicity and concavity in inputs. The violation of these assumptions may result in misleading values of computed elasticities and technical efficiency scores. The monotonicity assumption is met if the IDF is non-increasing in output and non-decreasing in inputs. In order to verify this property, it is sufficient (see Kumbhakar et al., 2008) that the first-order parameters are negative for the output ($\beta_m \leq 0$) and positive for the inputs ($\beta_j \geq 0$ for $j=L,K$) and $\beta_L + \beta_M < 1$, where L stands for labour and M represents material. The concavity in inputs requires that the Hessian matrix of second-order derivatives of the IDF of function with respect to the inputs is negatively semidefinite, according to Diewert and Wales (1987). This is fulfilled on the sample mean, if $\beta_{jj} + \beta_j^2 - \beta_j \leq 0$ $j=L,M$. These conditions hold for almost all model specifications and countries. The assumption of concavity is violated only in the case of Austrian GMM model and Irish GTRE model - probably due to the low number of observations.

The results show that majority of estimated parameters are highly statistically significant, even at the 1% significance level in all model specifications and all countries. This also holds for technical change. The statistical significance of persistent technical inefficiency, tested by the log-likelihood test, is more pronounced in GMM models. However, the presence of persistent technical inefficiency is not statistically significant in majority of the countries. Moreover, the obtained values of Hansen test and the Arellano-Bond autocorrelation test confirm the validity of country GMM estimates in all cases.

The Annex I shows that the values of the fitted parameters differ in the three model specifications. For example, a general feature of “GMM” model estimate is higher first-order parameter of material and lower labour cost share compared to the “GTRE” model. That would indicate that, the cost-share of material seems to be underestimated and the cost-share of labour overestimated due to the potential

endogeneity. Since the GMM estimator addresses the endogeneity problem, and provides unbiased and consistent parameter estimates, and since the GMM IDF estimates meet the economic as well as statistical requirements, we use them in the analysis of technology, efficiency and productivity.

Table 6 - Comparison of estimated models. (Source: Own calculation)

Properties	Country	GTRE	GTRE and Mundlak	GMM	Country	GTRE	GTRE and Mundlak	GMM
Monotonicity	Austria	Yes	Yes	Yes	Italy	Yes	Yes	Yes
Concavity in inputs		Yes	Yes	No		Yes	Yes	Yes
Significance of technical change chi2[5] , chi2[6], F[5,91]/chi2[5]		Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE		42.52***	54.25***	4.20***		481.59***	636.24***	100.85***
		0.00	0.00	62.48***		0.00	0.00	188.99***
Properties	Country	GTRE	GTRE and Mundlak	GMM	Country	GTRE	GTRE and Mundlak	GMM
Monotonicity	Belgium	Yes	Yes	Yes	Romania	Yes	Yes	Yes
Concavity in inputs		Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes
Significance of technical change chi2[5] , chi2[6], F[5,491]/F[5,4558]		Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE		14.75**	17.87***	2.33**		410.8***	338.11***	131.24***
		0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00	31.24***
Properties	Country	GTRE	GTRE and Mundlak	GMM	Country	GTRE	GTRE and Mundlak	GMM
Monotonicity	Czechia	Yes	Yes	Yes	Spain	Yes	Yes	Yes
Concavity in inputs		Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes
Significance of technical change chi2[5] , chi2[6], F[5,1244]/chi2[5]		Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE		50.65***	62.08***	9.01***		269.19***	364.66***	160.63 ***
		0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	351.17***	0.00
Properties	Country	GTRE	GTRE and Mundlak	GMM	Country	GTRE	GTRE and Mundlak	GMM
Monotonicity	Finland	Yes	Yes	Yes	Sweden	Yes	Yes	Yes
Concavity in inputs		Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes
Significance of technical change chi2[5] , chi2[6], F[5,741]/F[5,1399]		Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE		64.31***	75.08***	6.91***		121.36***	127.62***	10.99***
		0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00
Properties	Country	GTRE	GTRE and Mundlak	GMM	Country	GTRE	GTRE and Mundlak	GMM
Monotonicity	France	Yes	Yes	Yes	United Kingdom	Yes	Yes	Yes
Concavity in inputs		Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes
Significance of technical change chi2[5] , chi2[6], chi2[5]/F[5,801]		Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE		852.01***	908.38***	222.60***		102.96***	114.41***	7.11***
		0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00
Properties	Country	GTRE	GTRE and Mundlak	GMM	Country	GTRE	GTRE and Mundlak	GMM
Monotonicity	Germany	Yes	Yes	Yes	Ireland	Yes	LNO	LNO
Concavity in inputs		Yes	Yes	Yes		No		
Significance of technical change chi2[5] , chi2[6], F[5,662]		Yes	Yes	Yes		No		
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE		79.07***	81.60***	6.16***		8.90		
		5.98***	0.00	0.00		303.79***		

4.1.1.2 TECHNOLOGY AND ECONOMIES OF SCALE

This chapter presents the parameter estimates of four-component model in GMM specification and a technology comparison among the countries as well as an evaluation of the exploitation of economies of scale. Instead of investigating on each country estimate separately, we evaluate and compare the results for all analyzed countries together. This strategy helps us to better understand the common and individual specifics of food processing industry in selected European countries with respect to technology, efficiency and productivity. We start with the results of the fitted first-order parameters and the significance of heterogeneity in production structure (Table 7). Then, we proceed with economies of scale (Table 8) and technical change evaluation (Chapter 4.1.1.3). Annex I – Table A1-A12 provides the whole sets of fitted parameters of the country input distance functions.

Table 7 - First-order parameters (food processing industry). (Source: Own calculation)

Coeff.	Austria	Belgium	Czechia	Finland	France	Germany	Ireland	Italy	Romania	Spain	Sweden	United Kingdom
α_y	-0.9509 ***	-0.9821 ***	-0.9556 ***	-1.0245 ***	-0.9766 ***	-0.9979 ***	LNO	-0.9619 ***	-0.9152 ***	-0.9816 ***	-1.0288 ***	-0.9902 ***
$\alpha_{y_{101}}$		-0.0939	-0.0048	0.0991 **	0.0175	0.0101	LNO	-0.0503 ***	-0.0524 **	0.0116	0.0129	-0.0336 *
$\alpha_{y_{105}}$		-0.0283	0.0103	0.0356	-0.0063	-0.0345	LNO	-0.0257	-0.0262	-0.0525 *	0.0492	0.0011
$\alpha_{y_{106}}$		0.0420	0.0023	0.0027	0.0039	0.0387	LNO	0.0331	-0.0261	0.0491 **	0.0144	-0.0823 **
$\alpha_{y_{107}}$		-0.0385	-0.0234	0.0913 **	0.0048	0.0050	LNO	-0.0058	-0.0584 ***	0.0294	0.0133	-0.0421
β_L	0.2752 ***	0.3188 ***	0.3033 ***	0.3572 ***	0.3826 ***	0.2581 ***	LNO	0.2873 ***	0.3817 ***	0.3101 ***	0.3582 ***	0.3356 ***
$\beta_{L_{101}}$		-0.0195	-0.0331	0.0769	0.0711	0.0064	LNO	-0.1557 ***	-0.0238	-0.0649 **	0.0540	-0.0566
$\beta_{L_{105}}$		0.1100	0.0205	0.0654	-0.0037	-0.0298	LNO	0.0174	-0.0090	-0.1729 **	0.1026 **	-0.0509
$\beta_{L_{106}}$		0.0994	0.0263	0.0595	0.0240	0.0280	LNO	0.0723	0.0222	0.0069	0.0311	-0.0558
$\beta_{L_{107}}$		-0.0594	-0.1657 ***	0.0130	-0.0306	0.0126	LNO	0.0667 *	-0.1610 ***	-0.0124	0.0253	0.0004
β_M	0.6131 ***	0.6137 ***	0.6271 ***	0.5732 ***	0.5073 ***	0.6350 ***	LNO	0.6039 ***	0.5826 ***	0.6239 ***	0.5688 ***	0.5974 ***
$\beta_{M_{101}}$		-0.0863 *	-0.0289	-0.1798 **	-0.0647	0.0458	LNO	0.1464 ***	-0.0354	0.0080	-0.0090	0.0288
$\beta_{M_{105}}$		-0.0105	0.0492	-0.0771	-0.0017	0.0597 *	LNO	0.1240 ***	-0.0398	0.1729 ***	-0.0927 **	0.0619 **
$\beta_{M_{106}}$		-0.0451	-0.0325	-0.0672	-0.0193	0.0817	LNO	0.0162	-0.0319	-0.0351	0.0053	-0.1036
$\beta_{M_{107}}$		0.1350 **	0.1466 ***	-0.0427	0.1844 ***	0.0326	LNO	0.2024 ***	0.0891	0.1033 ***	-0.0026	0.0643 **

Note: ***, **, * denotes significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively.

The first order parameters of inputs represent the cost-shares and reflect the relative importance of the inputs in the production process. The fitted cost shares are highly statistically significant even at the 1% significance level in all analyzed countries. As expected, and in line with the information provided by the dataset, the highest cost shares have material inputs, between 0.50 and 0.64. The labour cost share represents

approximately 30 %, with the lowest cost share in Germany (25.8 %) and highest in Romania (38.2 %). The rest is represented by the share of capital.

The elasticities of output, which correspond to the negative value of the cost elasticities, are also highly statistically significant, even at the 1% significance level in all analyzed countries. These elasticities reveal whether the technology exhibits increasing, constant or decreasing returns to scale – if a proportionate increase in all inputs results in a larger, equal or less than proportionate increase in the aggregate output, respectively (Baumol et al., 1982). In other words, they inform us whether producers exploit economies of scale, or, whether they are characterized by diseconomies of scale.

Table 7 shows that the absolute value of output elasticity is close to one in the majority of countries, evaluated on the sample mean. The deflection towards a higher absolute value than one is a characteristic of the Nordic countries (Finland and Sweden). In Romania, the elasticity of IDF with respect to the output is the lowest from all the investigated countries. That is, Romanian food processing firms exhibit moderate economies of scale, evaluated on country sample mean. Moreover, statistically significant (at the 1% level) and negative parameter α_{yy} implies that the cost elasticity becomes smaller as output increase in Romania. In other words, larger companies are closer to the optimal size.

As far as the heterogeneity is concerned, the results do not reveal any significant heterogeneity effect on output elasticities in the majority of countries. In other words, inter-sectoral heterogeneity in cost elasticity is not a common feature of European food processing sectors. The exceptions can be found in sectors 10.1 (Processing and preserving of meat and meat products) in Finland, Romania, Italy, and the United Kingdom, 10.5 (Manufacture of dairy products) in Spain, 10.6 (Manufacture of grain mill products, starches and starch products) in Spain and the United Kingdom and in 10.7 (Manufacture of bakery and farinaceous products) in Finland and Romania. These exceptions have no common patterns. While in Italy, for example, the value of the heterogeneity parameter of sector 10.1 is the lowest, from the values of heterogeneity parameters, the value of the meat heterogeneity parameter is the highest in Finland. That is, the cost elasticity of meat processing is higher than the rest of food processing sectors in Italy and lower in Finland. In addition, the values of statistically significant heterogeneity parameters are low, which, together with estimated cost elasticities, does not indicate existence of economies/diseconomies of scale in the selected sectors.

Inter-sectoral heterogeneity is not a statistically significant feature of food processing industries even in the case of cost shares. This fact especially holds for labour. The heterogeneity parameters of labour are statistically significant at the 10% level only in the Italian and Spanish meat processing sector (both indicate lower cost-shares of labour as compared to the rest of food processing sector), in the Spanish and Swedish dairy industry (without common pattern) and in the Czech, Italian and Romanian bakeries (with lower labour cost-shares in the Post-Communist countries).

More frequent occurrence of significant inter-sectoral heterogeneity is revealed in the case of material cost shares. This is especially the case of sectors 10.5 and 10.7 where the estimates show higher material cost shares in the majority of countries.

Table 8 - Returns to scale (food processing industry). (Source: Own calculation)

Country	10.1				10.5			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Austria	1.0187	0.0764	0.8297	1.1351	1.0449	0.0861	0.8416	1.2439
Belgium	0.9322	0.0361	0.7867	1.2025	0.9887	0.0357	0.7919	1.0907
Czechia	1.0240	0.0419	0.9125	1.2403	1.0187	0.0430	0.9396	1.2141
Finland	1.0840	0.0364	0.9693	1.2216	1.0116	0.0329	0.9235	1.0871
France	1.0602	0.0319	0.9294	1.2387	1.0270	0.0261	0.9123	1.1038
Germany	1.0200	0.0384	0.8630	1.1974	0.9996	0.0362	0.8819	1.1012
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	0.9828	0.0372	0.8822	1.3007	1.0127	0.0344	0.9238	1.1221
Romania	1.0022	0.0552	0.8694	1.1775	1.0522	0.0560	0.8897	1.2418
Spain	1.0270	0.0173	0.9653	1.1255	0.9682	0.0131	0.9314	1.0191
Sweden	1.0027	0.0232	0.9483	1.0814	1.0274	0.0306	0.9773	1.1229
United Kingdom	0.9777	0.0205	0.9195	1.0297	1.0151	0.0236	0.9411	1.0721
Country	10.6				10.7			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Austria	1.0767	0.1275	0.8895	1.2268	1.0775	0.0606	0.9740	1.1842
Belgium	1.0423	0.0306	0.9170	1.1933	0.9980	0.0369	0.8420	1.3229
Czechia	1.0351	0.0509	0.9686	1.2086	1.0402	0.0341	0.9392	1.2075
Finland	0.9810	0.0379	0.8041	1.0731	1.0592	0.0268	0.9538	1.1682
France	1.0272	0.0214	0.9431	1.1003	1.0147	0.0234	0.8761	1.1602
Germany	1.0514	0.0207	1.0032	1.0999	0.9728	0.0392	0.7484	1.1094
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	1.0573	0.0395	0.9722	1.2778	1.0736	0.0303	0.9625	1.2358
Romania	1.0733	0.0588	0.8898	1.2742	1.0403	0.0423	0.8672	1.2764
Spain	1.0622	0.0206	1.0004	1.1503	1.0551	0.0143	0.9936	1.1062
Sweden	1.0083	0.0257	0.9651	1.0722	0.9817	0.0197	0.9436	1.0722
United Kingdom	0.9379	0.0171	0.9004	0.9828	0.9641	0.0195	0.9001	1.0281

Table 8 provides the information on the returns to scale for four selected sectors. Value larger than 1 indicates that food processors exhibit increasing returns to scale. That is, as stated above, a 1% proportional decrease in all inputs would cause a lower than 1% proportional decrease in the total output. The presence of increasing returns to scale signals that firms have economic incentives to increase the size of their enterprise.⁵⁵ This might be the case of German and Spanish mills. Value smaller than 1 indicates decreasing returns to scale, which means that a proportionate increase in all inputs results in less than proportionate increase in output. The British mills are characterized by slightly decreasing returns to scale suggesting that they operate with

⁵⁵ According to Rasmussen (2011), assuming homothetic production technology when proportional increases in all inputs are of the same magnitude as the change in the aggregate input use, returns to scale can be interpreted in the same manner as returns to size. The presence of increasing returns to scale signals that food processors have economic incentives to increase the size of their operations and implies the need for further structural adjustments given an adequate representation of all inputs used in the production. On the other hand, decreasing returns to scale can indicate that the size of food processing firms is above the technically optimal level. Moving to a technically optimal size would bring cost savings to food processors. Finally, the constant returns to scale signals that processors operate on optimal size.

larger than optimal scale. However, we do not observe that returns to scale are statistically different from one in the majority of countries, and so, we cannot reject constant returns to scale in majority of cases. This suggests that the firms have optimal size evaluated on the sample mean and from a static point of view. On the other hand, some firms are characterized by considerable diseconomies of scale (see the extreme values in the Table 8).

We can conclude that the technology of food processing industry does not exhibit statistically significant (at the 10% level) inter-sectoral heterogeneity in 11 European countries. The common features are found in the case of cost elasticity, as well as in the cost structure. Moreover, the food processors in general cannot largely benefit from the exploitation of economies of scale since the size seems to be optimal in majority of cases.

4.1.1.3 TECHNICAL CHANGE

Table 9 presents the estimates of parameters on technical change and biased technical change. The parameters of technical change (δ_i) are statistically significant even at the 1 % significance level in the majority of analyzed European countries and have a similar (low negative) pattern connected with the slight decrease in production costs. Moreover, this negative pattern ($\delta_i < 0$) is accelerating ($\delta_{it} < 0$) over the analyzed period at the 1% level at majority of the selected European countries. In other words, we estimated positive technical change in the most of analyzed countries which is accelerating over time.

Table 9 - Technical change parameters (food processing industry). (Source: Own calculation)

Coeff.	Austria	Belgium	Czechia	Finland	France	Germany	Ireland	Italy	Romania	Spain	Sweden	United Kingdom
δ_t	-0.0083 **	-0.0076 ***	-0.0112 ***	0.0057	-0.0124 ***	-0.0050 **	LNO	-0.0087 ***	-0.0351 ***	-0.0107 ***	-0.0117 ***	-0.0089 ***
$\delta_{t_{101}}$		0.0087	0.0033	-0.0377	0.0075 ***	-0.0039	LNO	0.0045 **	-0.0200 ***	0.0046 ***	-0.0002	0.0014
$\delta_{t_{105}}$		0.0065	0.0058	0.0143	0.0051 **	0.0066	LNO	0.0033	-0.0054	0.0084 **	-0.0074	0.0060
$\delta_{t_{106}}$		-0.0006	0.0125 **	0.0335	0.0048 *	-0.0002	LNO	0.0004	-0.0010	-0.0021	-0.0021	-0.0009
$\delta_{t_{107}}$		0.0068	0.0015	-0.0370 *	0.0037	0.0022	LNO	-0.0027	0.0032	0.0004	0.0086 **	0.0032
δ_{tt}	-0.0020	0.0002	-0.0012	-0.0059 ***	-0.0029 ***	-0.0025 ***	LNO	-0.0003	0.0318 ***	-0.0006 *	-0.0048 ***	-0.0026 ***
δ_{yt}	-0.0048	0.0002	-0.0008	0.0035 *	0.0012 *	-0.0022	LNO	0.0023 ***	-0.0049 ***	0.0005	0.0037 ***	0.0040 ***
δ_{Lt}	0.0095	-0.0068	0.0009	0.0128 *	-0.0029 **	0.0045 **	LNO	0.0039 **	-0.0073 *	-0.0012	0.0018	0.0050
δ_{Mt}	0.0057	0.0034	0.0011	-0.0123 *	0.0000	-0.0013	LNO	-0.0014	0.0169 ***	0.0015	-0.0007	-0.0013

Note: ***, **, * denotes significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively.

The heterogeneity parameters of technical change are not statistically significant even at 10% level in the most of cases. Only the parameter of sector 10.6 in the Czech Republic is interesting for the interpretation since it indicates Hicks-neutral technical

regress in this sector. This reflects the lack of modernization of Czech mill technology in the last decade.

The biased technical change is not statistically significant (at 10% level) in more than half of analyzed European countries (Table 9). Additionally, the values of statistically significant parameters δ_{jt} are low. The direction of this slight biased technical change, resulted from relative resource scarcity, differs among countries. No common pattern can be identified.

Considering a Hicksian-style definition of technical change bias based on the relative factor shares expressed as: $\delta_{jt} = \frac{\partial^2 \ln D_{jt}^I}{\partial \ln x_{jit} \partial t} = \frac{\partial S_{jt}}{\partial t}$, where S_{jt} is cost-share of j^{th} input (Irz and Thirtle, 2005), a positive value of $\delta_{L,t}$ indicates that technical change is labour-saving. This is the case of Finland, Germany, and Italy where the decrease of labour cost-share is a common feature of the food processing industry in the period 2007-2015. Since 2016, the data show an expected pattern, i.e. a decrease in the cost-share of labour. The prevailing labour-using technical change indicated by a negative value of $\delta_{L,t}$ is revealed in France and Romania. In the case of material, the technical change is biased towards material (in other words, it is material-using, see Trigo Gamarra, 2008) in Finland and against material (material-saving) in Romania.

The results show that the technical change biased in favour of labour is more pronounced than the technical change biased against labour and in favour of material. Since it could be expected that labour would become scarcer in the period under investigation, this result indicates that food processors would cope with adjustment problems in the period under investigation.

According to Irz and Thirtle (2005), the elasticity of the input distance function with respect to time, that is $TC_{it} = -\frac{\partial \ln D^I(x^*(w,y,t),y,t)}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial \ln C(w,y,t)}{\partial t}$ provides a convenient dual measure of the rate of technical change. Table 10 presents these elasticities for analyzed sectors.

The technical progress is the predominant feature in the majority of European countries. Evaluated on the country sample means, a technological regress is revealed only in the sector 10.1 in Belgium, in the sector 10.5 in Belgium and Finland, in the sector 10.6 in the Czech Republic and Finland and in the sector 10.7 in Germany. This may indicate a low level of innovation (especially process one) in these sectors and countries and may imply significant structural weakness (Török et al., 2019). In general, the lack of innovation activities may result in lower competitiveness. On the contrary, successful innovation process resulting in cost diminution is an important source of competitive advantage.

Our results have important political implications. Strengthening the innovative activity of companies is unlikely to be possible without investment incentives and continued support for the building of an innovation-friendly business environment. Supporting innovation activity of food processors is an important source not only of profitability and competitiveness, but also of food security, safety and sustainability.

Table 10 - Technical change parameters (food processing industry). (Source: Own calculation)

Country	10.1				10.5			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Austria	-0.0092	0.0099	-0.0409	0.0087	-0.0071	0.0114	-0.0321	0.0197
Belgium	0.0018	0.0094	-0.0348	0.0342	0.0009	0.0108	-0.0257	0.0619
Czechia	-0.0075	0.0039	-0.0186	0.0028	-0.0043	0.0039	-0.0153	0.0042
Finland	-0.0363	0.0191	-0.1079	0.0232	0.0110	0.0214	-0.0478	0.0655
France	-0.0056	0.0088	-0.0329	0.0215	-0.0079	0.0095	-0.0356	0.0146
Germany	-0.0092	0.0067	-0.0282	0.0057	-0.0048	0.0127	-0.0715	0.0158
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	-0.0037	0.0068	-0.0231	0.0275	-0.0051	0.0081	-0.0236	0.0239
Romania	-0.0331	0.0957	-0.2655	0.2049	-0.0295	0.0888	-0.2432	0.2159
Spain	-0.0056	0.0025	-0.0151	0.0036	-0.0020	0.0027	-0.0087	0.0069
Sweden	-0.0089	0.0137	-0.0378	0.0331	-0.0207	0.0128	-0.0476	0.0193
United Kingdom	-0.0077	0.0126	-0.0343	0.0343	-0.0029	0.0137	-0.0348	0.0429
Country	10.6				10.7			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Austria	-0.0102	0.0143	-0.0328	0.0086	-0.0073	0.0091	-0.0274	0.0131
Belgium	-0.0036	0.0079	-0.0172	0.0521	-0.0042	0.0073	-0.0619	0.0292
Czechia	0.0017	0.0041	-0.0105	0.0096	-0.0100	0.0035	-0.0203	0.0009
Finland	0.0365	0.0255	-0.0104	0.1520	-0.0208	0.0168	-0.0800	0.0270
France	-0.0080	0.0089	-0.0327	0.0096	-0.0086	0.0079	-0.0357	0.0166
Germany	-0.0057	0.0076	-0.0222	0.0097	0.0006	0.0071	-0.0193	0.0164
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	-0.0085	0.0057	-0.0206	0.0093	-0.0118	0.0068	-0.0325	0.0134
Romania	-0.0393	0.0864	-0.2416	0.2253	-0.0378	0.0829	-0.2470	0.2138
Spain	-0.0115	0.0027	-0.0215	-0.0048	-0.0123	0.0024	-0.0198	-0.0039
Sweden	-0.0100	0.0155	-0.0400	0.0294	-0.0020	0.0128	-0.0408	0.0405
United Kingdom	-0.0104	0.0116	-0.0368	0.0169	-0.0058	0.0122	-0.0325	0.0383

4.1.1.4 TECHNICAL EFFICIENCY

This chapter provides the discussion of technical efficiency estimates for selected sectors in the 11 European countries. Since the technical efficiency estimates are country-specific, we concentrate predominantly on the discussion of the significance of overall technical efficiency and its components, and on the comparison of efficiency dynamics. The overall comparison of the level of technical efficiency among countries will be carried out using meta-frontier analysis in chapter 4.1.2.

Figure 4 presents the distribution of overall technical efficiency in selected sectors in analyzed countries. Annex I, Table C1 then provides the overall technical efficiency of food processing industries in these countries and their decompositions. The overall technical efficiency estimates indicate that, evaluated at the country samples means, firms in the food processing industry can reduce their costs from 5% up to 23% to produce the same volumes of outputs.

As the box-plots as well as numeric values in Annex I, Table C2 present, the selected sectors have similar median/mean values of overall technical efficiency in the majority of countries. The only exception is milling industry in Austria. Austrian mill producers may save 27% of inputs to produce the same volume of output and Austrian meat processors can save 24% of inputs, evaluated on the sample means. Lower overall

technical efficiency score for milling industry as compared to other processing industries is a common feature for other countries but the differences are considerably small.

Figure 4a - Overall technical efficiency (food processing industry, part 1). (Source: Own calculation)

Figure 4b - Overall technical efficiency (food processing industry, part 2).(Source: Own calculation)

The meat processing industry is the sector with the highest overall technical efficiency score in most of cases. In particular, the meat processing sector evaluated on sample means has the highest value of overall technical efficiency in Austria, Germany, Romania, and the United Kingdom. The manufacture of bakery and farinaceous products seems to be the most technically efficient sector of the analyzed sectors in Finland, France, and Sweden.

As far as the intra-sectoral differences are concerned, the overall technical efficiency is relatively dense around the mean/median and skewed to higher values. In the majority of analyzed countries, the interquartile ranges are quite narrow (see

Figure 4). The outliers in box-plots indicate high polarization between the most technically efficient producer and the least technically efficient one. The highest polarization is evident in the sector 10.7 in Belgium, France, Italy, and Spain; in the sector 10.1 in the Czech Republic and Finland; in the sector 10.5 in Austria and Romania and in the sector 10.6 in Germany and United Kingdom (evaluated on variation range). On the other hand, the lowest polarization is uncovered in the sector 10.6 in France, Italy, Spain, and Sweden; in the sector 10.1 in Germany and Romania; in the sector 10.5 in the Czech Republic and Finland; and in the sector 10.7 in Austria and United Kingdom.

As the overall technical efficiency is associated with cost savings, it can be assumed that sectors with the highest polarization will face structural changes in the future. That is, we can expect changes in business activities or even the cessation of production of firms with the lowest technical efficiency and resource reallocation to more successful producers.

The overall technical efficiency consists of the transient and persistent technical efficiency. The persistent part of overall technical efficiency indicates systematic failures or structural problems and unsuitable factor allocations that are difficult to change over time as well as non-competitive market conditions. However, the persistent technical efficiency is statistically significant only in the case of Austria, Italy and Romania (see table 6). Table 11 shows that the average persistent technical efficiency scores are about 90% with no significant inter-sectoral differences. Intra-sector variability of persistent technical efficiency is more pronounced. However, the variation range of persistent technical efficiency scores is considerably lower as compared to transient technical efficiency.

Table 11 - Persistent technical efficiency (food processing industry). (Source: Own calculation)

Country	10.1				10.5			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Austria	0.9083	0.0283	0.8616	0.9551	0.9066	0.0300	0.8234	0.9371
Italy	0.8980	0.0350	0.7470	0.9758	0.9095	0.0240	0.8168	0.9620
Romania	0.9216	0.0232	0.6929	0.9734	0.9177	0.0214	0.6639	0.9624
Country	10.6				10.7			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Austria	0.8915	0.0277	0.8609	0.9258	0.9004	0.0185	0.8753	0.9322
Italy	0.9066	0.0331	0.7482	0.9510	0.9047	0.0568	0.6325	0.9720
Romania	0.9175	0.0237	0.7720	0.9715	0.9194	0.0171	0.6794	0.9757

The highest variability is revealed in sector 10.7 in Italy. The Italian bakery sector is also characterized by the highest polarization between the most efficient producer and the lowest one. This suggests that relatively many firms systematically fail to catch up best practices and thus show considerable resource inefficiency as compared to firms operating on the technological frontier in the bakery industry. The variation ranges of Romanian technical efficiency scores reveal that there exist firms that face to systematic managerial failures in bakery industry as well.

Table 12 shows sector-specific transient technical efficiency scores. The inter-sectoral differences are not pronounced in the most of cases. In addition, the Figure A1 in

Annex I shows that the developments of transient technical efficiency over time have similar patterns, for example the declines in 2009 or in 2014. However, the most important feature is an increasing trend in transient technical efficiency in the analyzed period. The only exception is Romania food processing that experience decreasing trend in transient technical efficiency.

Table 12 - Transient technical efficiency (food processing industry). (Source: Own calculation)

Country	10.1				10.5			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Austria	0.8354	0.0375	0.6856	0.9293	0.8319	0.0438	0.6454	0.9153
Belgium	0.9303	0.0197	0.7687	0.9815	0.9309	0.0159	0.7949	0.9695
Czechia	0.9114	0.0260	0.3839	0.9913	0.9123	0.0185	0.7232	0.9688
Finland	0.9011	0.0342	0.4454	0.9735	0.9030	0.0219	0.7842	0.9637
France	0.9325	0.0208	0.5631	0.9851	0.9328	0.0243	0.3971	0.9954
Germany	0.9315	0.0149	0.7984	0.9852	0.9307	0.0271	0.4862	0.9851
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	0.9211	0.0326	0.3678	0.9857	0.9227	0.0279	0.6312	0.9783
Romania	0.8663	0.0342	0.4880	0.9561	0.8659	0.0340	0.3856	0.9612
Spain	0.9267	0.0275	0.4190	0.9872	0.9269	0.0249	0.6574	0.9808
Sweden	0.9503	0.0110	0.8200	0.9898	0.9483	0.0192	0.8209	0.9910
United Kingdom	0.9456	0.0173	0.7298	0.9806	0.9434	0.0266	0.7337	0.9854
Country	10.6				10.7			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Austria	0.8167	0.0363	0.7667	0.8891	0.8309	0.0300	0.7494	0.8937
Belgium	0.9318	0.0163	0.7666	0.9664	0.9291	0.0342	0.4945	0.9886
Czechia	0.9106	0.0288	0.5548	0.9869	0.9113	0.0226	0.5536	0.9854
Finland	0.8972	0.0476	0.5467	0.9682	0.9034	0.0217	0.4786	0.9842
France	0.9328	0.0223	0.7249	0.9818	0.9340	0.0207	0.1882	0.9956
Germany	0.9301	0.0551	0.2018	0.9782	0.9315	0.0246	0.5377	0.9865
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	0.9214	0.0305	0.6881	0.9817	0.9205	0.0441	0.2208	0.9910
Romania	0.8648	0.0384	0.3931	0.9576	0.8671	0.0255	0.4576	0.9660
Spain	0.9275	0.0272	0.7254	0.9824	0.9275	0.0331	0.2028	0.9905
Sweden	0.9498	0.0134	0.8865	0.9783	0.9504	0.0097	0.8454	0.9865
United Kingdom	0.9424	0.0317	0.6325	0.9812	0.9448	0.0176	0.8552	0.9834

Intra-sectorally, the greatest variability can be observed in the case of sector 10.6 in the Czech Republic, Finland, Germany, Romania, and United Kingdom; in the sector 10.7 in Belgium, Italy and Spain; and in the sector 10.5 in Austria and France. The fluctuations of technical efficiency in the short term may be the result of shocks associated with the introduction of new technologies or changes in human capital. To minimize these negative shocks, it is recommended to support managerial skills, knowledge transfer, education, and consulting services in these countries. Moreover, in the food processing industry, we can speculate about the effects of raw material input quality as a result of weather conditions.

4.1.1.5 TOTAL FACTOR PRODUCTIVITY

The previous chapters presented analyzed economies of scale, technical change, and technical efficiency separately. This chapter use the above mentioned statistics as components to construct the total factor productivity (TFP) index (in the form of Törnqvist-Theil index). We focus on TFP development in selected sectors, and compare productivity development in analyzed countries. The discussion consists of: (1) comparison of country differences in each sector; (2) analysis of inter-sectoral differences in each country; and (3) investigation of intra-sectoral differences in each country.

Table 13 - Törnqvist-Theil index of TFP (food processing industry). (Source: Own calculation)

Country	10.1				10.5			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Austria	0.0090	0.0572	-0.1369	0.2184	-0.0225	0.0718	-0.2231	0.1346
Belgium	-0.0068	0.0630	-0.3057	0.1225	-0.0058	0.0406	-0.3372	0.1264
Czechia	-0.0232	0.0730	-0.3553	0.5399	-0.0487	0.0793	-0.1516	0.4990
Finland	-0.0485	0.0594	-0.2107	0.1792	-0.0197	0.0214	-0.0742	0.0391
France	-0.0106	0.1034	-0.6639	0.1099	-0.0332	0.1304	-0.8132	0.0987
Germany	0.0089	0.0664	-0.3843	0.1145	0.0191	0.0608	-0.7748	0.1184
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	-0.0098	0.0592	-0.9184	0.2364	-0.0132	0.0823	-0.5772	0.1456
Romania	-0.0343	0.1119	-0.6611	0.3499	-0.0287	0.1264	-0.5525	0.4260
Spain	-0.0143	0.0489	-0.7454	0.2657	0.0007	0.0482	-0.3677	0.2002
Sweden	0.0090	0.0234	-0.1310	0.0654	0.0070	0.0441	-0.1523	0.0743
United Kingdom	0.0046	0.0377	-0.2227	0.1590	-0.0035	0.0380	-0.2313	0.1452
Country	10.6				10.7			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Austria	-0.0407	0.0802	-0.1607	0.0854	0.0436	0.1003	-0.1090	0.2631
Belgium	-0.0037	0.0396	-0.2679	0.0758	0.0023	0.0466	-0.5042	0.1187
Czechia	-0.0325	0.1224	-0.1660	0.5951	0.0088	0.0870	-0.2521	0.5572
Finland	-0.0506	0.0689	-0.4997	0.1828	0.0272	0.0667	-0.3836	0.4028
France	-0.0080	0.0907	-0.5441	0.0970	0.0353	0.0583	-1.5037	0.1109
Germany	0.0059	0.1173	-1.4718	0.0902	-0.0305	0.0991	-0.7189	0.0797
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	-0.0099	0.0834	-0.3998	0.3925	0.0351	0.1102	-1.3481	0.2899
Romania	0.0277	0.1513	-0.4764	0.4779	0.0109	0.1099	-0.6054	0.4113
Spain	-0.0277	0.0686	-0.2834	0.3047	0.0369	0.0836	-1.2624	0.3264
Sweden	0.0062	0.0217	-0.0745	0.0466	-0.0102	0.0258	-0.2288	0.0763
United Kingdom	-0.0013	0.0586	-0.4404	0.1473	-0.0113	0.0460	-0.1411	0.1897

Table 13 shows significant differences among analyzed countries in sector 10.1 (Processing and preserving of meat and production of meat products) productivity. While Belgium, the Czech Republic, Finland, France, Italy, Romania, and Spain can be characterized by negative TFP change, the productivity of meat processing sector was growing in Austria, Germany, Sweden, and the United Kingdom in the period

2007-2018. There was a decline of the average annual TFP from 0.7% (in Belgium) to 4.8% (in Finland). On the other hand, the TFP changed positively in Austria, Germany, Sweden and the UK, evaluated on the country sample means. This TFP growth rate suggests strengthening the competitive position in these four countries (Austria, Germany, Sweden, and the United Kingdom) in comparison to the rest of the countries.

The differences among analyzed countries also occurred in sector 10.5 (Manufacture of dairy products) where the TFP change was positive in Germany, Spain, and Sweden with an annual average rate from 0.07% (in Spain) to 1.9% (in Germany). In the rest of countries, the TFP changes were negative and the averages differ from (-0.4)% in the UK to (-4.9)% in the Czech Republic, indicating that the Czech Republic is significantly lagging behind the rest of the analyzed countries in the dairy processing industry.

Sector 10.6 (Manufacture of grain mill products, starches, and starch products) experienced TFP decline in the majority of analyzed countries in the period 2007-2018. The average annual TFP decline was from 0.1% in the UK to 5.1% in Finland. Similarly to previous sectors, there can be found exceptions from this negative trend. The exceptions are Germany, Romania, and Sweden, where the TFP was growing in rate from 0.6% (in Germany) to 2.8% (in Sweden).

As opposite to the previous sector, sector 10.7 (Manufacture of bakery and farinaceous products) can be characterized by productivity growth during the period 2007-2018 in the majority of countries (except for Germany, Sweden, and the United Kingdom; evaluated on sample mean). The annual TFP changes take values from (-2.1)% (in Germany) to 4.4% (in Austria) in this sector.

The results reveal considerable inter-sectoral differences in the TFP developments, as well (see Table 13). In line with the previous description, particularly, sector 10.7 differs from the general tendency. The most significant inter-sectoral differences are revealed in Germany and Belgium, as is obvious from the Figure B1 in Annex I. Moreover, Figure B1 shows breaks in the development of TFP. In particular, the recovery following the year 2016. This is the situation in all sectors in Austria, Belgium, the Czech Republic, Italy, Spain, and the United Kingdom. The recovery of TFP was driven by a positive technical efficiency change at the end of the analyzed period.

Intra-sectorally, a significant variation can be observed among food processors. Based on the value of standard deviation, the highest variation in the meat processing sector is revealed in Romania, in the dairy industry in Germany, in the milling industry in Romania, and in the bakery industry in Italy. The highest polarization, in other words, the highest differences between the best-performing companies and the worst-performing, can be observed in Italian bakeries, followed by French and Spanish bakeries, and in other sectors by German mills, Italian meat processors, and Romanian dairies.

Moreover, the manufacture of bakery and farinaceous products provides evidence on the relation between the TFP change and the size of a company. In the countries with the highest polarization, the negative TFP change was found in the very large companies (see Table 14). In addition, a similar situation was found in the mill industry

in Germany, as well as in the French dairy industry. This foreshadows the significance of the scale effect in TFP growth.

Table 14 - Törnqvist-Theil index of TFP in sector 10.7 in selected countries. (Source: Own calculation)

Italy	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Small	0.1032	0.1061	-1.3481	0.2899
Medium	0.0441	0.0569	-0.5820	0.2180
Large	-0.0823	0.0582	-0.3530	0.0574
Very large	-0.2137	0.1160	-0.4419	-0.0551
France	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Small	0.0407	0.0318	-0.5759	0.1109
Medium	0.0507	0.0223	-0.1736	0.1072
Large	-0.0753	0.0988	-1.5037	0.0515
Very large	-0.3285	0.1663	-0.8336	-0.0915
Spain	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Small	0.1109	0.0708	-1.1608	0.3264
Medium	0.0245	0.0575	-1.2624	0.1672
Large	-0.0586	0.0281	-0.1822	0.0750
Very large	-0.0857	0.0211	-0.1591	-0.0421

It holds for Italy, France, Spain, the scale effect (SEC) positively contributed to the TFP change in sector 10.7, according to the TFP decomposition results, in 2007-2018. This is clearly due to the changes in increasing returns to scale that is exhibited in small and medium companies. Moreover, being closer to optimal size, companies may exploit economies of scale more efficiently as they tend to have stronger bargaining power as well as better access to external finance and innovation. This is reflected in the positive contribution of technical change to TFP growth, in sector 10.7. in Italy and Spain (see Figure 5). On the other hand, the very large companies can be more confronted with structural problems in the production process, as well as less able to adapt to changes in policies and regulations, as well as in consumers' behaviour.

The scale effect represents the main source of the TFP change in the majority of analyzed sectors and countries as evaluated at the country samples averages. According to Figure 5, the technical change (TC) was found as the main source of the TFP change only in sector 10.1 in Belgium and Finland, in sector 10.5 in Belgium and Sweden, in sector 10.6 in Finland, and in sector 10.7 also in Finland. The contribution of technical efficiency (TEC), however it is positive, is the lowest from the TFP components in the majority sectors and countries. Annex I, Table D1 – Table D3 provides descriptive statistics of these TFP components.

Figure 5a - Decomposition of TFP (food processing industry, part 1). (Source: Own calculation)

Figure 5b - Decomposition of TFP (food processing industry, part 2). (Source: Own calculation)

4.1.2 META-FRONTIER ANALYSIS

This chapter presents the results of the meta-frontier analysis. It provides technical efficiency and total factor productivity comparison among countries. First, we present the results of the meta-frontier input distance function estimate in three various specifications: GTRE, GTRE with Mundlak adjustment and GMM, and subsequently, we evaluate the basic statistical characteristics of technical efficiency and productivity of 10 European countries (Ireland and Romania are excluded; Ireland due to the low number of observations and Romania due to violation of Hansen test in the country-specific IDF estimate as well as due to the different size structure).

4.1.2.1 PROCESSING AND PRESERVING OF MEAT

4.1.2.1.1 Model estimate

Table 15 provides parameter estimates of the stochastic meta-frontier input distance function models for the sector 10.1 (Processing and preserving of meat). As in the case of country IDF estimates, the theoretical assumptions about the monotonicity as well as the concavity in inputs, are met in all these specifications, evaluated on the sample mean. The first-order parameters of IDF are highly significant, even at the 1 % significance level, except for the time in GMM, and have a similar pattern. The latter holds for second-order parameters as well. Moreover, AR(2) and Hansen J test indicate the validity of GMM model specification.

Table 15 - Meta-frontier model estimates (10.1). (Source: Own calculation)

10.1 Variable	GTRE			GTRE with Mundlak			GMM		
	Coef.	St.Er.	P> z	Coef.	St.Er.	P> z	Coef.	St.Er.	P> t
ln_y	-0.9493	0.0052	0.0000	-0.8742	0.0127	0.0000	-0.9726	0.0072	0.0000
ln_xL	0.2993	0.0073	0.0000	0.3158	0.0098	0.0000	0.3118	0.0125	0.0000
ln_xM	0.6336	0.0075	0.0000	0.6179	0.0102	0.0000	0.6286	0.0128	0.0000
T	-0.0068	0.0004	0.0000	-0.0078	0.0004	0.0000	-0.0026	0.0022	0.2540
ln_y_2	-0.0234	0.0057	0.0000	-0.0124	0.0041	0.0020	-0.0155	0.0053	0.0040
ln_xL_2	0.1234	0.0092	0.0000	0.1360	0.0079	0.0000	0.1011	0.0261	0.0000
ln_xM_2	0.1400	0.0062	0.0000	0.1510	0.0047	0.0000	0.1473	0.0155	0.0000
ln_xLxM	-0.1180	0.0068	0.0000	-0.1222	0.0053	0.0000	-0.1074	0.0202	0.0000
t_2	-0.0004	0.0002	0.0470	-0.0008	0.0002	0.0000	-0.0007	0.0008	0.3390
ln_yt	0.0012	0.0003	0.0000	0.0006	0.0003	0.0460	0.0013	0.0012	0.2910
ln_xLt	-0.0007	0.0007	0.3230	-0.0005	0.0007	0.4840	-0.0033	0.0047	0.4800
ln_xMt	-0.0013	0.0008	0.0950	-0.0007	0.0006	0.2510	-0.0037	0.0028	0.1900
ln_yxL	-0.0024	0.0040	0.5540	0.0007	0.0038	0.8440	-0.0094	0.0129	0.4640
ln_yxM	-0.0058	0.0041	0.1580	-0.0126	0.0039	0.0010	0.0182	0.0114	0.1120
_cons	-0.0521	0.0109	0.0000	-0.0770	0.0078	0.0000	-0.0796	0.0160	0.0000
ln_y_gmean				-0.1033	0.0128	0.0000			
ln_xL_gmean				-0.0216	0.0112	0.0540			
ln_xM_gmean				0.0150	0.0107	0.1630			
t_gmean				0.0101	0.0040	0.0110			
			p-val			p-val			p-val
Sig. of TC	439.85		0.0000	511.30		0.0000	4.70		0.0003
LL test for	0.0000			-0.0001			-0.0015		
R2	0.9891			0.9912					
Wald/F-test	158329.6		0.0000	327279.4		0.0000	8029.14		0.0000
AR(3)							-0.31		0.757
Hansen test							236.20		0.113
N.							226		
N. groups							616		
	Mean	Std.D.		Mean	Std.D.		Mean	Std.D.	
Overall TE	0.9585	0.0122		0.9711	0.0060		0.9421	0.0209	
Transient TE	0.9587	0.0122		0.9715	0.0060		0.9429	0.0209	
PersistentTE	0.9998	0.0000		0.9996	0.0000		0.9992	0.0000	

Note: Sig. of TC means the significance of technical change ($\chi^2[5]$, $\chi^2[6]$, $F[5,615]$).

The share of material in the total input is about 60%, the share of labour is about 30%, and the absolute value of output elasticity is only slightly lower than 1, representing that the economies of scale is not exhibited. The low negative estimates of the parameters δ_t represent the slight decrease in production costs which is accelerating over time ($\delta_{it} < 0$). The parameters of biased technical change are not statistically significant at the 1% significance level.

However, similarly to country-specific IDF estimates, it is obvious that the values of the estimated parameters slightly differ in the analyzed three model specifications. The comparison of GTRE and GMM reveals that the output elasticity and the cost-share of material are underestimated and the cost-share of labour is overestimated. This suggests that the endogeneity might be an issue and we will use in the analysis only GMM estimates which provide unbiased and consistent parameter estimate.

Similarly to the majority of country-specific IDF estimates, the zero hypothesis of the log-likelihood test: $\sigma_{\eta} = 0$, is not rejected. That is, the existence of persistent technical inefficiency is not statistically significant and the inefficiency, in overall view, is especially due to the non-systematic short-term managerial failures and shocks. Moreover, the overall technical efficiency estimates indicate high technical efficiency. The overall technical efficiency is about 94 %, as evaluated at the sample averages. That is, the sample meat processors can reduce their costs by 6%, to produce the same volumes of outputs. Furthermore, the meat processors operate very close to the estimated mean value (see the low values of standard deviation in Table 15). Due to the insignificance of the persistent part of technical efficiency, the comparative analysis of technical efficiency is based only on the overall technical efficiency estimates.

4.1.2.1.2 Technical efficiency and productivity comparison

Table 16 provides the country-level overall technical efficiency estimates for the sector 10.1 for GMM model specification. Annex I, Table E1 provides the complete estimates of the transient technical efficiency. The results show that we cannot observe any considerable differences between the analyzed countries. The mean values are very closed and the standard deviations are not higher than 0.04.

Table 16 - Meta-frontier overall technical efficiency (10.1). (Source: Own calculation)

Country	GMM	
	Mean	Std.Dev.
Austria	0.9435	0.0087
Belgium	0.9416	0.0300
Czechia	0.9399	0.0365
Finland	0.9399	0.0348
France	0.9430	0.0146
Germany	0.9436	0.0149
Ireland	LNO	LNO
Italy	0.9423	0.0192
Romania	EE	EE
Spain	0.9419	0.0201
Sweden	0.9421	0.0194
United Kingdom	0.9412	0.0140

Note: LNO means the low number of observations, EE is excluded from the estimation

Table 17 presents TFP estimates using the Törnqvist-Theil index calculated from meta-frontier IDFs for the meat processing sector. The results allow direct comparison of TFP levels among countries. That is, the results suggest that Czech, French, Italian, Spanish and Swedish processors indicate average sample TFP. Austrian, Belgian, German and British processor have slightly lower productivity, around 97 % with respect to the sample mean. On the other hand, Finish processors experienced above-average TFP, approximately 101 %. However, the differences among the countries are considerably low. If we take into consideration only technical efficiency and technical change component of TFP, we can observe similar values of indices. That is, the differences in TFP, although small, are due to the scale component.

Table 17 - Meta-frontier total factor productivity (TFP, 10.1). (Source: Own calculation)

Country	GMM			
	TFP		TE&TC	
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.
Austria	0.9676	0.0131	1.0163	0.0111
Belgium	0.9801	0.0253	1.0050	0.0389
Czechia	1.0007	0.0355	0.9936	0.0550
Finland	1.0126	0.0330	0.9913	0.0482
France	1.0060	0.0303	0.9992	0.0186
Germany	0.9790	0.0258	1.0093	0.0197
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	1.0000	0.0307	0.9998	0.0238
Romania	EE	EE	EE	EE
Spain	1.0008	0.0319	0.9992	0.0248
Sweden	1.0044	0.0326	0.9992	0.0239
United Kingdom	0.9654	0.0162	1.0144	0.0164

Note: LNO means the low number of observations, EE is excluded from the estimation

4.1.2.2 MANUFACTURE OF DAIRY PRODUCTS

4.1.2.2.1 Model estimate

Table 18 summarises parameter estimates of the stochastic meta-frontier input distance function models in the three alternative specifications for the sector 10.5 in 10 European countries. It holds for all model specifications that the monotonicity requirements and the requirements of the concavity in inputs are met by the estimate, evaluated on the sample mean. The first-order parameters of IDF are highly significant even at the 1% significance level and have a similar pattern indicating the high material intensity of the dairy industry.

The share of material in the total input is again about 60%, the share of labour is about 30%, and the output elasticity varies between (-0.98) and (-0.96). The time parameter (δ_t) has a low negative value representing the cost decrease with the decelerating rate ($\delta_{tt} > 0$) over the analyzed period. However, the second-order time parameter (δ_{tt}) is statistically significant only with the 10% significance level in the GMM model. The parameters of biased technical change are not statistically significant even at the 10% significance level. The rest of second-order parameters have a similar pattern as well. The Hansen statistic rejects the zero hypothesis, that is, we can conclude that the estimated parameters are quite robust to these specifications.

The results reveal high overall technical efficiency. Evaluated at the sample averages, the overall technical efficiency is between 92% and 96%, that is, dairy processors can reduce their costs from 4% up to 6% subject to the model specification, to produce the same volumes of outputs. As far as the standard deviations is concerned, we may observe that the dairy producers operate very close to the estimated mean value of technical efficiency.

Table 18 - Meta-frontier model estimates (10.5). (Source: Own calculation)

10.5 Variable	GTRE			GTRE with Mundlak			GMM		
	Coef.	St.Er.	P> z	Coef.	St.Er.	P> z	Coef.	St.Er.	P> t
ln_y	-0.9601	0.0064	0.0000	-0.8886	0.0207	0.0000	-0.9801	0.0039	0.0000
ln_xL	0.2976	0.0161	0.0000	0.3039	0.0230	0.0000	0.2620	0.0088	0.0000
ln_xM	0.6483	0.0146	0.0000	0.6375	0.0222	0.0000	0.6864	0.0084	0.0000
t	-0.0074	0.0008	0.0000	-0.0090	0.0009	0.0000	-0.0069	0.0010	0.0000
ln_y_2	-0.0032	0.0057	0.5740	-0.0007	0.0053	0.8890	0.0045	0.0052	0.3920
ln_xL_2	0.0538	0.0072	0.0000	0.0582	0.0077	0.0000	0.0656	0.0127	0.0000
ln_xM_2	0.1322	0.0098	0.0000	0.1326	0.0090	0.0000	0.1472	0.0080	0.0000
ln_xLxM	-0.0847	0.0079	0.0000	-0.0863	0.0077	0.0000	-0.0949	0.0103	0.0000
t_2	0.0005	0.0004	0.1400	0.0000	0.0003	0.9240	0.0009	0.0005	0.0780
ln_yt	0.0005	0.0005	0.2800	0.0008	0.0005	0.0950	0.0004	0.0010	0.6780
ln_xLt	-0.0001	0.0011	0.9380	0.0003	0.0011	0.7700	-0.0014	0.0030	0.6390
ln_xMt	-0.0001	0.0012	0.9650	-0.0004	0.0012	0.7760	0.0033	0.0026	0.1920
ln_yxL	-0.0055	0.0073	0.4570	-0.0016	0.0069	0.8200	0.0008	0.0079	0.9180
ln_yxM	-0.0080	0.0059	0.1760	-0.0101	0.0057	0.0750	-0.0246	0.0069	0.0000
_cons	-0.0714	0.0136	0.0000	-0.0772	0.0135	0.0000	-0.0915	0.0095	0.0000
ln_y_gmean				-0.0867	0.0200	0.0000			
ln_xL_gmean				-0.0049	0.0201	0.8080			
ln_xM_gmean				-0.0013	0.0232	0.9550			
t_gmean				0.0007	0.0066	0.9110			
			p-val			p-val			p-val
Sig. of TC	159.07		0.0000	154.98		0.0000	11.16		0.0000
LL test for PTE	-0.0003			0.0000			0.3361		
R2	0.9933			0.9934					
Wald/F-test	88916.9		0.0000	139404.9		0.0000	7444.6		0.0000
AR(2)							-0.06		0.953
Hansen test							347.25		0.0000
N. instruments							226		
N. groups							625		
	Mean	Std.D.		Mean	Std.D.		Mean	Std.D.	
Overall TE	0.9553	0.0139		0.9624	0.0099		0.9200	0.0179	
Transient TE	0.9561	0.0139		0.9629	0.0099		0.9500	0.0177	
PersistentTE	0.9992	0.0000		0.9994	0.0000		0.9684	0.0044	

Note: Sig. of TC represents the significance of technical change ($\chi^2[5]$, $\chi^2[6]$, $F[14,624]$).

4.1.2.2.2 Technical efficiency and productivity comparison

Table 19 indicates that the overall technical efficiency is high in all countries and no significant differences among countries are pronounced. The lowest value of overall technical efficiency can be observed in Sweden, according to all model specifications and evaluated on mean values. Moreover, Swedish dairy industry can be characterized with the highest variability measured by standard deviation. On the contrary, the highest average value of overall technical efficiency is found in France and Austria. Moreover, the Austrian food producers in the dairy industry operate very close to the estimated mean value.

Table 19 - Meta-frontier overall technical efficiency (10.5). (Source: Own calculation)

Country	GTRE		GTRE with Mundlak		GMM	
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.
Austria	0.9558	0.0077	0.9629	0.0051	0.9202	0.0092
Belgium	0.9551	0.0115	0.9623	0.0086	0.9181	0.0200
Czechia	0.9547	0.0183	0.9620	0.0123	0.9191	0.0217
Finland	0.9551	0.0156	0.9621	0.0113	0.9212	0.0183
France	0.9558	0.0122	0.9627	0.0088	0.9212	0.0152
Germany	0.9554	0.0163	0.9626	0.0117	0.9185	0.0254
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	0.9557	0.0115	0.9625	0.0083	0.9206	0.0139
Romania	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE
Spain	0.9554	0.0120	0.9624	0.0085	0.9197	0.0145
Sweden	0.9513	0.0261	0.9591	0.0210	0.9171	0.0314
United Kingdom	0.9547	0.0155	0.9622	0.0102	0.9190	0.0195

Note: LNO means the low number of observations, EE is excluded from the estimation.

Table 20 shows that the differences among the countries are not large also in the case of TFP. In particular, the majority of countries is characterized by similar level of TFP in dairy industry. The above-average productivity can be observed only in Sweden. On the other hand, Austrian, Belgian, German and British total factor productivity is slightly below the sample average.

Table 20 - Meta-frontier total factor productivity (TTI, 10.5). (Source: Own calculation)

Country	GTRE		GTRE with Mundlak		GMM			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.	TFP		TE&TC	
					Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.
Austria	0.9258	0.0125	0.9535	0.0103	0.9673	0.0279	0.9939	0.0102
Belgium	0.9433	0.0425	0.9633	0.0277	0.9663	0.0273	0.9953	0.0185
Czechia	0.9938	0.1117	0.9948	0.0759	0.9692	0.0402	0.9984	0.0248
Finland	1.0530	0.1525	1.0373	0.1069	0.9943	0.0610	1.0019	0.0209
France	1.0148	0.0759	1.0075	0.0505	0.9992	0.0468	1.0027	0.0187
Germany	0.9265	0.0330	0.9572	0.0218	0.9727	0.0291	0.9920	0.0308
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	1.0297	0.0879	1.0180	0.0588	1.0069	0.0547	1.0028	0.0165
Romania	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE
Spain	1.0263	0.0916	1.0161	0.0606	1.0091	0.0578	1.0022	0.0170
Sweden	1.1127	0.1312	1.0758	0.0943	1.0238	0.0549	1.0017	0.0363
United Kingdom	0.9372	0.0246	0.9601	0.0177	0.9698	0.0386	0.9944	0.0214

Note: LNO means the low number of observations, EE is excluded from the estimation.

If we take again into consideration only the technical efficiency and technical change component, we cannot observe any differences. That is, the identified differences in TFP are due to the scale effect. The variability in TFP change is considerable large. This especially holds for Finland and Sweden, where the standard deviations are the

highest (considering all model specifications). On the other hand, the lowest spread is, similarly to the sector 10.1, found in Austria.

4.1.2.3 MANUFACTURE OF GRAIN MILL PRODUCTS

4.1.2.3.1 Model estimate

The parameter estimates of the stochastic meta-frontier input distance function models for the sector 10.6 indicate that also in the case of milling industry, the meta-frontier IDF satisfies the properties of monotonicity and concavity in inputs. Moreover, most of the estimated parameters are highly statistically significant, even at the 1% significance level in all model specifications. The results of the Hansen test and the Arellano-Bond autocorrelation test indicate the GMM model validity (see Table 21).

Table 21 - Meta-frontier model estimates (10.6). (Source: Own calculation)

10.6 Variable	GTRE			GTRE with Mundlak			GMM		
	Coef.	St.Er.	P> z	Coef.	St.Er.	P> z	Coef.	St.Er.	P> t
ln_y	-0.9550	0.0090	0.0000	-0.7214	0.0499	0.0000	-0.9607	0.0064	0.0000
ln_xL	0.2454	0.0162	0.0000	0.3042	0.0222	0.0000	0.2691	0.0131	0.0000
ln_xM	0.6692	0.0151	0.0000	0.6039	0.0280	0.0000	0.6926	0.0122	0.0000
t	-0.0078	0.0010	0.0000	-0.0088	0.0011	0.0000	-0.0065	0.0014	0.0000
ln_y_2	-0.0029	0.0162	0.8600	0.0047	0.0125	0.7090	-0.0187	0.0076	0.0140
ln_xL_2	0.1113	0.0260	0.0000	0.1211	0.0219	0.0000	0.1056	0.0256	0.0000
ln_xM_2	0.1918	0.0139	0.0000	0.1858	0.0122	0.0000	0.1533	0.0215	0.0000
ln_xLxM	-0.1383	0.0140	0.0000	-0.1344	0.0139	0.0000	-0.1159	0.0213	0.0000
t_2	0.0007	0.0005	0.2050	-0.0001	0.0005	0.7940	0.0011	0.0006	0.1000
ln_yt	0.0010	0.0008	0.2360	-0.0003	0.0009	0.7320	0.0022	0.0014	0.1200
ln_xLt	0.0017	0.0023	0.4620	0.0009	0.0021	0.6540	0.0021	0.0035	0.5400
ln_xMt	-0.0010	0.0018	0.5790	-0.0004	0.0017	0.8300	-0.0051	0.0028	0.0640
ln_yxL	-0.0180	0.0103	0.0790	-0.0001	0.0096	0.9890	-0.0167	0.0108	0.1240
ln_yxM	-0.0189	0.0116	0.1030	-0.0273	0.0100	0.0060	0.0183	0.0104	0.0800
_cons	-0.0792	0.0244	0.0010	-0.0894	0.0180	0.0000	-0.0852	0.0130	0.0000
ln_y_gmean				-0.2760	0.0517	0.0000			
ln_xL_gmean				-0.0787	0.0238	0.0010			
ln_xM_gmean				0.0763	0.0305	0.0120			
t_gmean				0.0210	0.0063	0.0010			
			p-val			p-val			p-val
Sig. of TC	96.32		0.0000	104.41		0.0000	15.01		0.0000
LL test for PTE	-0.0001			-0.0003			0.0000		
R2	0.9908			0.9926					
Wald/F-test	27371.2		0.0000	86664.7		0.0000	9017.1		0.0000
AR(2)							-0.47		0.6370
Hansen test							320.43		0.0210
N. instruments							286		
N. groups							377		
	Mean	Std.D.		Mean	Std.D.		Mean	Std.D.	
Overall TE	0.9325	0.0234		0.9406	0.0201		0.9267	0.0258	
Transient TE	0.9331	0.0235		0.9413	0.0201		0.9270	0.0258	
PersistentTE	0.9994	0.0000		0.9992	0.0000		0.9996	0.0000	

Note: Sig. of TC means the significance of technical change ($\chi^2[5]$, $\chi^2[6]$, $F[5,376]$).

The elasticities of the meta-frontier correspond with country IDF estimates and the information we have in the data. That is, the cost share of material is about 60% and the share of labour is about 30%. Moreover, the elasticity of output, which corresponds to the negative of the cost elasticity, is again close to 1. In line with our previous results,

the sector 10.6 (Manufacture of grain mill products) can be characterized with a slight cost decrease in the analyzed time. In other words, we can observe positive technological change which is Hicks-neutral.

The log-likelihood test rejects the existence of persistent technical inefficiency. The average sample score of overall technical efficiency ranges from 92.67% (in GMM) to 94.06% (in GTRE with Mundlak adjustment) with low standard deviations.

4.1.2.3.2 Technical efficiency and productivity comparison

Table 22 reveals that sample mills can reduce their costs from 5.81% up to 7.7% on average, subject to the study country and model specification, to produce the same volumes of outputs. If we use GMM results, we can conclude that, again, the average overall technical efficiency is similar in all countries. The highest cost reduction can be done in the Czech Republic (7.7%). On the other hand, the most efficient mill production is revealed in France. The variability of overall technical efficiency estimates is the highest in Germany and the lowest in Austria.

Table 22 - Meta-frontier overall technical efficiency (10.6). (Source: Own calculation)

Country	GTRE		GTRE with Mundlak		GMM	
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.
Austria	0.9336	0.0070	0.9419	0.0074	0.9260	0.0092
Belgium	0.9328	0.0172	0.9413	0.0128	0.9275	0.0144
Czechia	0.9305	0.0323	0.9381	0.0281	0.9235	0.0371
Finland	0.9301	0.0393	0.9368	0.0353	0.9239	0.0441
France	0.9338	0.0149	0.9416	0.0140	0.9282	0.0156
Germany	0.9319	0.0481	0.9418	0.0385	0.9260	0.0526
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	0.9329	0.0174	0.9411	0.0146	0.9270	0.0186
Romania	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE
Spain	0.9325	0.0184	0.9408	0.0149	0.9266	0.0199
Sweden	0.9316	0.0221	0.9387	0.0203	0.9264	0.0238
United Kingdom	0.9324	0.0196	0.9409	0.0153	0.9263	0.0232

Note: LNO means the low number of observations, EE is excluded from the estimation.

Table 23 reveal TFP differences among countries. The below-average productivity can be observed in Austria, Belgium, Germany and the United Kingdom. The productivity level in these countries is approximately 5 % below the sample mean. On the other hand, the above average productivity can be found in Finland. Czech, French, Italian, Spanish and Swedish processors operate with similar TFP, that is the sample average TFP. The sum of technical efficiency and technical change component suggests again that the differences in TFP are due to the scale component.

Table 23 - Meta-frontier total factor productivity (TFP, 10.6). (Source: Own calculation)

Country	GTRE		GTRE with Mundlak		GMM			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.	TFP		TE&TC	
					Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.
Austria	0.9903	0.0948	1.0713	0.0958	0.9374	0.0160	0.9992	0.0113
Belgium	0.9300	0.0468	0.9964	0.0542	0.9497	0.0243	1.0030	0.0158
Czechia	1.0292	0.2083	1.0003	0.0986	0.9912	0.0534	0.9960	0.0485
Finland	1.2668	0.2739	1.1090	0.1417	1.0397	0.0790	0.9910	0.0554
France	0.9938	0.0919	0.9853	0.0427	1.0053	0.0498	1.0009	0.0179
Germany	0.9528	0.1098	1.0255	0.0906	0.9548	0.0263	0.9993	0.1024
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	0.9787	0.0882	0.9841	0.0442	1.0018	0.0563	1.0019	0.0208
Romania	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE
Spain	0.9718	0.0911	0.9854	0.0448	0.9932	0.0562	1.0016	0.0225
Sweden	1.0354	0.1383	1.0010	0.0487	1.0092	0.0751	0.9999	0.0273
United Kingdom	0.9471	0.0520	1.0158	0.0554	0.9480	0.0265	1.0006	0.0281

Note: LNO means the low number of observations, EE is excluded from the estimation.

4.1.2.4 MANUFACTURE OF BAKERY AND FARINACEOUS PRODUCTS

4.1.2.4.1 Model estimate

The theoretical assumptions about the input distance function are satisfied also in meta-frontier estimations for the sector 10.7 (Manufacture of bakery and farinaceous products). The majority of the estimated parameters are again highly statistically significant, even at the 1% significance level in all model specifications. This holds for technical change, as well, see Table 24.

In line with the country-specific IDF and previous results about inter-sectoral heterogeneity, the cost-share of labour is similarly to the cost-share of material around 45%. Moreover, the output elasticity is close to one, indicating no economies of scale. The estimates of the parameters δ_t are statistically significant at the 1% level in all specifications and have a similar (low negative) pattern, that is, it shows the slight decrease in production costs. In other words, the estimates suggest positive Hicks-neutral technological change which accelerates over time.

The overall technical efficiency is again high, around 95 %. Since the persistent technical inefficiency was not estimated, we can conclude that the deviation from the frontier is due to the transient inefficiency.

Table 24 - Meta-frontier model estimates (10.7). (Source: Own calculation)

10.7 Variable	GTRE			GTRE with Mundlak			GMM		
	Coef.	St.Er.	P> z	Coef.	St.Er.	P> z	Coef.	St.Er.	P> t
ln_y	-0.9297	0.0076	0.0000	-0.8651	0.0184	0.0000	-0.9630	0.0044	0.0000
ln_xL	0.4638	0.0090	0.0000	0.4534	0.0125	0.0000	0.5005	0.0069	0.0000
ln_xM	0.4596	0.0090	0.0000	0.4606	0.0133	0.0000	0.4490	0.0068	0.0000
t	-0.0084	0.0004	0.0000	-0.0084	0.0004	0.0000	-0.0089	0.0006	0.0000
ln_y_2	-0.0217	0.0065	0.0010	-0.0143	0.0053	0.0070	0.0038	0.0045	0.4070
ln_xL_2	0.1227	0.0118	0.0000	0.1241	0.0119	0.0000	0.1967	0.0223	0.0000
ln_xM_2	0.1438	0.0107	0.0000	0.1447	0.0100	0.0000	0.1440	0.0134	0.0000
ln_xLxM	-0.1115	0.0108	0.0000	-0.1100	0.0108	0.0000	-0.1583	0.0140	0.0000
t_2	-0.0027	0.0003	0.0000	-0.0027	0.0003	0.0000	-0.0021	0.0004	0.0000
ln_yt	0.0014	0.0004	0.0000	0.0009	0.0004	0.0250	0.0013	0.0007	0.0680
ln_xLt	-0.0010	0.0008	0.1860	-0.0007	0.0008	0.3670	-0.0009	0.0018	0.6200
ln_xMt	0.0012	0.0006	0.0520	0.0012	0.0006	0.0750	0.0020	0.0020	0.2970
ln_yxL	-0.0106	0.0058	0.0690	-0.0091	0.0053	0.0880	-0.0072	0.0060	0.2250
ln_yxM	0.0043	0.0057	0.4560	0.0024	0.0051	0.6350	0.0035	0.0062	0.5700
_cons	-0.0177	0.0095	0.0630	-0.0323	0.0075	0.0000	-0.0719	0.0070	0.0000
ln_y_gmean				-0.0897	0.0166	0.0000			
ln_xL_gmean				0.0174	0.0131	0.1830			
ln_xM_gmean				-0.0113	0.0140	0.4200			
t_gmean				0.0085	0.0040	0.0310			
			p-val			p-val			p-val
Sig. of TC	533.37		0.0000	519.37		0.0000	41.88		0.0000
LL test for PTE	-0.0007			0.0000			-0.0004		
R2	0.9914			0.9918					
Wald/F-test	209357.8		0.0000	370972.3		0.0000	14518.1		0.0000
AR(2)							-0.72		0.4690
Hansen test							491.42		0.0000
N. instruments							227		
N. groups							2020		
	Mean	Std.D.		Mean	Std.D.		Mean	Std.D.	
Overall TE	0.9503	0.0169		0.9529	0.0156		0.9414	0.0224	
Transient TE	0.9510	0.0169		0.9531	0.0156		0.9419	0.0224	
PersistentTE	0.9993	0.0000		0.9998	0.0000		0.9995	0.0000	

Note: Sig. of TC means the significance of technical change ($\chi^2[5]$, $\chi^2[6]$, $F[5,2019]$).

4.1.2.4.2 Technical efficiency and productivity comparison

Table 25 provides the country-level overall technical efficiency estimates for the sector 10.7. The results show that we cannot observe significant difference in overall technical efficiency among the countries in milling industry. Moreover, the overall technical efficiency is high.

Table 25 - Meta-frontier overall technical efficiency (10.7). (Source: Own calculation)

Country	GTRE		GTRE with Mundlak		GMM	
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.
Austria	0.9507	0.0063	0.9538	0.0054	0.9418	0.0081
Belgium	0.9506	0.0149	0.9537	0.0135	0.9419	0.0221
Czechia	0.9479	0.0239	0.9505	0.0220	0.9379	0.0328
Finland	0.9505	0.0200	0.9530	0.0186	0.9412	0.0263
France	0.9511	0.0112	0.9535	0.0104	0.9424	0.0155
Germany	0.9516	0.0150	0.9546	0.0139	0.9429	0.0230
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	0.9504	0.0183	0.9531	0.0169	0.9418	0.0233
Romania	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE
Spain	0.9498	0.0223	0.9525	0.0204	0.9410	0.0280
Sweden	0.9506	0.0148	0.9530	0.0139	0.9413	0.0192
United Kingdom	0.9503	0.0118	0.9532	0.0113	0.9417	0.0151

Note: LNO means the low number of observations, EE is excluded from the estimation.

Törnqvist-Theil productivity indices in Table 26 indicate considerable differences in productivity levels also in the case of bakery industry. In particular, the below-average productivity level can be observed in Austria, Belgium, Germany and the United Kingdom. The productivity level in these countries is from 91 % to 94 % of the average. The other countries are characterized by similar productivity level. Taking into consideration the sum of technical efficiency and technical change component, the differences are again due to the scale component.

Table 26 - Meta-frontier total factor productivity (TFP, 10.7). (Source: Own calculation)

Country	GTRE		GTRE with Mundlak		GMM			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.	TFP		TE&TC	
					Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.
Austria	0.8920	0.0185	0.9406	0.0181	0.9112	0.0311	0.9938	0.0099
Belgium	0.8839	0.0357	0.9308	0.0282	0.9171	0.0368	0.9968	0.0265
Czechia	1.0306	0.1480	1.0189	0.1001	1.0039	0.0512	0.9960	0.0408
Finland	1.0426	0.1245	1.0274	0.0844	1.0156	0.0496	1.0017	0.0325
France	1.0111	0.0761	1.0054	0.0506	1.0184	0.0397	1.0021	0.0191
Germany	0.9172	0.0635	0.9546	0.0454	0.9416	0.0589	0.9964	0.0304
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	0.9827	0.0944	0.9886	0.0620	0.9975	0.0526	0.9991	0.0343
Romania	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE
Spain	0.9888	0.0995	0.9921	0.0659	0.9992	0.0532	0.9983	0.0422
Sweden	1.0160	0.0897	1.0096	0.0598	1.0168	0.0433	1.0012	0.0223
United Kingdom	0.8974	0.0484	0.9444	0.0437	0.9116	0.0303	0.9966	0.0182

Note: LNO means the low number of observations, EE is excluded from the estimation.

4.2 AGRICULTURE

4.2.1 COUNTRY INPUT DISTANCE FUNCTION ESTIMATES

This chapter presents a comparison of technology, efficiency and productivity assessments based on the estimates of country-specific input distance functions on agricultural level using GMM estimator. Similarly to the food processing level, we evaluate the results for all the analyzed countries together. Our analysis starts with the discussion of the first-order parameters and economies of scale (Chapter 4.2.1.1), proceeds by technical change (Chapter 4.2.1.2) and technical efficiency evaluation (Chapter 4.2.1.3) and concludes with the consideration on productivity developments (Chapter 4.2.1.4).

4.2.1.1 TECHNOLOGY AND ECONOMY OF SCALE

Table 27 provides the estimates of the first order parameters for cereal production. Annex II (Tables F1-F13) contains the whole set of estimated parameters of all the country input distance functions for cereal production.

The results show that the majority of the first-order parameters are statistically significant even at the 1% significance level in all the analyzed countries. Moreover, the estimates meet the theoretical assumptions. Specifically, the results of fitted distance functions evaluated at the sample means are non-increasing in outputs and non-decreasing in inputs. Moreover, quasi-concavity assumption of the input distance functions with respect to inputs is met by all the estimates as well. Finally, AR(2) test and Hansen's J-test statistics indicate the validity of model estimates.

Table 27 - First-order parameters (cereals). (Source: Own calculation)

Coeff.	Austria	Belgium	Czechia	Finland	France	West Germany	East Germany	Ireland	Italy	Romania	Spain	Sweden	United Kingdom
α_{yC}	-0.1124	-0.1121	-0.3321	-0.2247	-0.3162	-0.2435	-0.3405	-0.1388	-0.2247	-0.2627	-0.2524	-0.1910	-0.1954
	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***
α_{yAOC}	-0.1149	-0.0619	-0.3040	-0.1337	-0.1175	-0.0957	-0.1771	-0.1053	-0.2504	-0.2378	-0.0894	-0.2461	-0.1546
	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***
α_{yAOO}	-0.4294	-0.4103	-0.3083	-0.2766	-0.2996	-0.4084	-0.3524	-0.3400	-0.3547	-0.2045	-0.3231	-0.3333	-0.3798
	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***
β_L	0.1331	0.1508	0.1268	0.1763	0.1574	0.1108	0.1085	0.2591	0.2087	0.2474	0.1507	0.1496	0.1122
	***	**	***	***	***	***	*	***	***	***	***	***	***
β_W	0.2474	0.3639	0.1500	0.2824	0.2132	0.2697	0.1231	0.2926	0.2452	0.2912	0.2703	0.2867	0.2821
	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***
β_K	0.1893	0.1243	0.0875	0.0694	0.1415	0.0719	0.1670	0.0517	0.0748	0.0887	0.0757	0.0895	0.0920
	***	*	***	***	**	**	***	***	***	***	***	***	*

Note: ***, **, * denotes significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively.

The first order parameters on inputs reveal common and expected patterns in the cost structure of cereal production among analyzed countries. That is, cereal production in the selected for the analysis 12 European countries is characterized by the highest share of material inputs in the cost structure (from 36% to 64%). Considering the average agricultural area operated by farms in single country samples (Table 4), these results indicate that large-scale farms tend to have higher material cost-shares compared to small-scale ones. Then, the cost-share of labour is the second highest

one for all the analyzed countries (15% - 36%). The lowest value is found in East Germany and the Czech Republic where, however, the numbers of working units employed by farms on average (Table 4) are among the highest. These findings indicate the low marginal productivity of labour input in the Czech Republic and East Germany agriculture compared to the rest of the analyzed countries. Finally, in the majority of countries, the share of capital in the total input is the lowest (Austria and East Germany are exceptions).

The elasticities of outputs are also highly statistically significant even at the 1% significance level in all the analyzed countries. The results reveal considerable differences in the output elasticities. Based on the elasticities of outputs, the analyzed countries can be distinguished into two categories: countries with the highest elasticity of other productions (y_{AOO}): Austria, Belgium, Finland, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Spain, Sweden, and the United Kingdom; and countries with the highest elasticity of cereals production (y_C): Czechia, France, and Romania.

As far as the economies of scale are concerned, we can conclude that the absolute value of the sum of output elasticities is lower than 1 in all the analyzed countries. That is, the economies of scale can be exploited. In other words, the costs increase at a higher rate than the output in all the analyzed countries. In the Czech Republic and East Germany, the sums of the IDF elasticities with respect to output are the highest among the countries under investigation, whereas the lowest value belongs to Ireland.

The majority of the first-order parameters of IDFs in milk production are also statistically significant even at the 1% significance level for all the analyzed countries, see Table 28. Equally important, the theoretical assumptions are met by the estimates for all countries and AR(2) and Hansen's J-test confirmed the validity of all IDF estimates. Tables I1-I13 in Annex II present the whole set of estimated parameters of country-specific input distance functions of milk production. These results show that the second order parameters in most of the cases are also highly statistically significant at 1 % significance level.

Table 28 - First-order parameters (milk). (Source: Own calculation)

Coeff.	Austria	Belgium	Czechia	Finland	France	West Germany	East Germany	Ireland	Italy	Romania	Spain	Sweden	United Kingdom
α_{yC}	-0.3037 ***	-0.3194 ***	-0.3328 ***	-0.5298 ***	-0.4922 ***	-0.3985 ***	-0.4385 ***	-0.4135 ***	-0.3715 ***	-0.1349 ***	-0.6928 ***	-0.4092 ***	-0.5249 ***
α_{yAOC}	-0.1564 ***	-0.2057 ***	-0.1632 ***	-0.0873 ***	-0.1710 ***	-0.1603 ***	-0.1333 ***	-0.2236 ***	-0.0871 ***	-0.1002 ***	-0.0564 ***	-0.0926 ***	-0.1640 ***
α_{yAOO}	-0.1645 ***	-0.1585 ***	-0.4583 ***	-0.1447 ***	-0.1760 ***	-0.1800 ***	-0.3804 ***	-0.1309 ***	-0.2763 ***	-0.4258 ***	-0.0880 ***	-0.3078 ***	-0.1690 ***
β_L	0.1435 ***	0.0704 **	0.1184 **	0.0994 ***	0.0531 ***	0.0827 ***	0.0536 ***	0.2208 ***	0.1536 ***	0.2160 ***	0.1155 ***	0.0605 **	0.1122 ***
β_W	0.3351 ***	0.3691 ***	0.3195 ***	0.2554 ***	0.2168 ***	0.2991 ***	0.1827 ***	0.1785 ***	0.3197 ***	0.3259 ***	0.2531 ***	0.2651 ***	0.2801 ***
β_K	0.1995 ***	0.1707 ***	0.0759 ***	0.0741 ***	0.2477 ***	0.0994 ***	0.1808 ***	0.0746 ***	0.1112 ***	0.1031 ***	0.0698 ***	0.0809 ***	0.1234 ***

Note: ***, **, * denotes significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels, respectively.

Similarly to the cereals production, material inputs in milk production play a dominant role in the cost structure. The share of material evaluated on sample means is between 32% in Austria and 59% in Sweden. The cost-share of labour ranges from 18% in

Ireland to 37% in Belgium. Considering the number of working units employed by farms in single country samples (Table 5), these results indicate low marginal productivity of labour input in Ireland compared to the rest of the analyzed countries. In contrast to the cereals production, the cost-share of capital turned out to be the lowest only for six of the analyzed countries, namely the Czech Republic, Finland, Ireland, Italy, Romania, and Spain. This reveals higher capital intensity in the milk production in comparison to the production of cereals.

The elasticities of outputs are statistically significant even at the 1% level in all the analyzed countries. Similarly to the cereals production, country-specific IDF estimates indicate considerable differences in these elasticities, which highlights differences in the importance of output m in terms of cost. Table 28 shows that the milk production (y_C) in the analyzed sample is the most important output in the majority of the analyzed countries. There are two exceptions: the Czech Republic and Romania where the highest elasticity of other output is revealed. This reflects the fact that dairy production in these countries is mainly carried out on less specialized farms.

The absolute value of the sum of output elasticities is lower than 1 in all the analyzed countries. In other words, the diseconomies of scale become apparent in the milk production. Among all the countries under consideration the sum of the IDF elasticities with respect to output is the highest for the Czech Republic and East Germany, whereas the lowest value belongs to Austria, evaluated on country samples means.

Table 29 - Returns to scale (cereals and milk). (Source: Own calculation)

Country	Cereals				Milk			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Austria	1.5388	0.1546	1.0044	2.3375	1.6138	0.1488	1.1702	3.1267
Belgium	1.7529	0.2984	1.2166	4.0316	1.4729	0.1245	1.1951	2.1358
Czechia	1.0609	0.0389	0.9561	1.1785	1.0502	0.0527	0.9411	1.7810
Finland	1.6008	0.2094	1.2004	2.5623	1.3349	0.1821	0.9453	3.0081
France	1.3789	0.1529	0.9959	2.7255	1.2120	0.2158	0.8849	18.2378
West Germany	1.3376	0.1700	0.9242	2.9243	1.4414	0.4841	0.7581	16.0861
East Germany	1.1494	0.3114	0.6746	3.1761	1.0532	0.0650	0.8939	1.3096
Ireland	1.8592	0.8281	0.7683	23.6279	1.3364	0.2373	0.8930	3.3368
Italy	1.2221	0.1476	0.8599	2.1405	1.3785	0.1623	0.9980	2.4035
Romania	1.4500	0.2172	0.9019	3.1914	1.5858	0.3340	0.8284	2.8902
Spain	1.5581	0.3037	0.9036	3.1360	1.2193	0.1819	0.7912	2.3882
Sweden	1.3191	0.1750	0.8872	2.4795	1.2521	0.1553	0.8629	3.0003
United Kingdom	1.3851	0.1406	0.8523	1.9927	1.1730	0.0964	0.9370	1.7291

Table 29 presents the country-specific returns to scale for cereals and milk production. Evaluated on country samples means a value larger than 1, indicating that agricultural producers exhibit increasing returns to scale (RTS), is the common pattern of both, milk and cereals, productions in the analyzed countries. The lowest value was observed for the Czech Republic and East Germany, i.e. countries where large-scale farms dominate in agricultural production. The closeness of the average value of RTS to 1 in the Czech Republic and in East Germany indicate that the Czech sample farms and especially East German milk producers tend to be close to the optimal scale of

production. The magnitude of RTS (evaluated on country samples means) of the rest analyzed countries reveals that the cereals producers in these countries have a substantial potential to improve their productivity by increasing scales of operations. This also holds for milk production, although the magnitude of RTS in milk production (evaluated on country samples means) is lower for the majority of countries than in the case of cereals production.

4.2.1.2 TECHNICAL CHANGE

The comparative analysis of the countries' differences in technical change and biased technical change is represented by Tables 30, 31 and 32 given below. Table 30 provides the estimate of technical change parameters in cereal production. The estimates show that the parameters on technological change (δ_t) are statistically significant at the 5% level in Belgium, France, West Germany, Romania, Finland, West and East Germany and Sweden. Whereas Belgium, France, West Germany and Romania experienced a positive technical change connected with the slight decrease in production costs, at the same time cereals production in Finland, East Germany, and Sweden is characterized by a negative technical change, where an increase in production costs was revealed.

Table 30 - Technical change parameters (cereals). (Source: Own calculation)

Coeff.	Austria	Belgium	Czechia	Finland	France	West Germany	East Germany	Ireland	Italy	Romania	Spain	Sweden	United Kingdom
δ_t	-0.0003	-0.0170	-0.0006	0.0136	-0.0043	-0.0319	0.0060	-0.0087	0.0012	-0.0092	-0.0046	0.0111	-0.0014
		***		***	***	***	**	*		**		***	
δ_{tt}	0.0041	0.0046	0.0096	0.0040	0.0020	0.0164	0.0101	0.0052	0.0008	0.0126	0.0050	0.0029	0.0042
	***	***	***	***	***	***	***			***	***	***	***
δ_{yCt}	-0.0086	-0.0037	0.0075	-0.0079	0.0009	-0.0033	-0.0086	0.0018	0.0042	-0.0063	0.0087	0.0002	0.0087
	***						**				*		**
δ_{yAOct}	0.0075	0.0041	-0.0047	-0.0021	-0.0019	-0.0001	-0.0014	0.0108	0.0014	0.0014	-0.0017	-0.0073	-0.0026
	***		***									***	
δ_{yAOOt}	0.0007	0.0056	0.0051	0.0026	-0.0020	0.0038	0.0072	0.0111	0.0097	0.0080	0.0010	0.0065	0.0038
			**		**	**	***		***	**		***	
δ_{Lt}	0.0072	-0.0024	0.0174	-0.0123	-0.0037	0.0014	0.0250	0.0133	-0.0032	0.0077	-0.0032	0.0069	0.0097

δ_{Wt}	-0.0073	0.0109	0.0137	0.0099	0.0055	-0.0011	-0.0131	0.0251	0.0300	0.0219	-0.0013	-0.0047	-0.0031
			*				*		***	***			
δ_{Kt}	-0.0034	0.0067	-0.0058	0.1210	0.0029	-0.0003	-0.0102	0.0039	-0.0046	0.0009	0.0101	-0.0090	0.0017
				*			*					**	

Moreover, Finnish, East German and Swedish cost growth was accelerating over the analyzed period at the 1% significance level. The parameters δ_{mt} , that measure the annual rate of change in the sample average farm's estimated output elasticities, are statistically significant at least at the 10% level in the majority of countries. Although the effect of time differs, we can conclude that the elasticity of crop production (other than cereals, yAOO) changed predominantly. The biased technical change resulting from relative resource scarcity is not statistically significant (at 10% level) in the majority of analyzed countries (Table 30). That is, these countries are characterized by Hick's neutral technical change. The biased technical change was estimated for cereal production in the Czech Republic, Finland, East Germany, Italy, Romania, and Sweden. This biased technical change is predominantly labour-saving. This is the

case of Italian, Romanian and the Czech Republic's cereals production. The Finland cereals production can be characterized by capital-saving biased technical change, whereas the capital using biased technical change was revealed in East Germany and Sweden.

As far as milk production is concerned (Table 31), the estimates of the parameters δ_t are statistically significant at the 5% level in Belgium, the Czech Republic, Finland, West and East Germany, Ireland, Italy, Spain, and the United Kingdom. In the majority of these countries, the parameters δ_t have a positive pattern representing an increase in production costs, that is, technological regress, evaluated on country samples means. Moreover, the cost growth is accelerating over the analyzed period at the 5% level of significance in the Czech Republic, Finland, and Ireland. The biased technical change is statistically significant (at 10% level) in the majority of the analyzed countries, however, there is no common pattern. The models reveal statistically significant land-using biased technical change in Austria, the Czech Republic, Italy, Spain, and the United Kingdom. This indicates that farmers in these five countries underwent structural changes leading to a higher specialization in livestock (milk) production as well as higher dependence on external suppliers due to a decrease in home feed production in the analyzed period. The East German, Irish and Italian milk production can be characterized by labour-saving technical change, whereas the Spanish milk production underwent labour using biased technical change in the analyzed period. Finally, in the majority of countries milk production can be characterized by the capital using biased technical change. Austria and France are the exceptions that are characterised by capital saving technical change. This suggests that milk producers in the majority of the analyzed countries invested in fixed assets at the beginning of the period under investigation.

Table 31 - Technical change parameters (milk). (Source: Own calculation)

Coeff.	Austria	Belgium	Czechia	Finland	France	West Germany	East Germany	Ireland	Italy	Romania	Spain	Sweden	United Kingdom
δ_t	-0.0009	-0.0076	0.0125	0.0132	-0.0009	0.0288	-0.0487	0.0095	0.0044	-0.0015	-0.0139	0.0017	-0.0141
		***	***	***		***	***	***	**		***		***
δ_{tt}	0.0018	0.0038	0.0053	0.0030	0.0020	0.0022	0.0200	0.0045	0.0005	0.0085	0.0048	0.0021	0.0076
	***	***	***	***	***		***	***		**	***	**	***
δ_{yCt}	-0.0021	0.0022	-0.0032	0.0132	0.0023	-0.0054	0.0024	0.0036	0.0013	0.0036	-0.0080	0.0097	-0.0082
				***	**	**					**	***	**
δ_{yAOct}	0.0017	-0.0015	-0.0019	-0.0022	0.0030	-0.0019	-0.0013	0.0066	-0.0053	0.0072	-0.0004	0.0033	-0.0032
					***			**	**				
δ_{yAOot}	0.0009	0.0018	0.0062	-0.0032	-0.0008	-0.0009	0.0014	-0.0052	0.0091	-0.0149	-0.0020	-0.0098	0.0098
			**		*			**	***	*		**	***
δ_{Lt}	-0.0129	0.0018	-0.0187	0.0093	-0.0026	0.0015	-0.0076	-0.0049	-0.0130	0.0083	-0.0076	0.0081	-0.0157
	***		**	*					***		**		**
δ_{Wt}	0.0009	-0.0043	0.0015	-0.0060	0.0017	-0.0053	0.0186	0.0106	0.0189	0.0024	-0.0243	-0.0024	-0.0008
							**	**	***		***		
δ_{Kt}	0.0110	-0.0093	-0.0008	-0.0082	0.0038	0.0052	-0.0041	0.0050	-0.0066	0.0014	-0.0091	-0.0099	0.0046
	***	*		*	**				***		***	**	

Since the period under investigation begins in 2004, it could be expected that at this stage of the European agricultural development labour may become scarcer while capital may become more abundant. In other words, labour-saving and capital-using

technical changes could be expected. The fact that we revealed some exceptions from these patterns indicates that serious adjustment problems in these countries may exist, including problems in the capital market.

Table 32 summarizes statistical characteristics of the derivatives of the input distance function with respect to time that provides a dual measure of the rate of technical change. A negative value of this derivative indicates a technical progress connected with cost diminishing, this is the case for Austrian, Belgian, Czech, French, West German, Irish, Romanian, Spanish, and British cereals production. On the other hand, the Finnish, East German, Italian, and Swedish cereals production can be characterized by slight technological regress, evaluated on country samples means. These results foreshadow a potential loss of profitability and competitiveness of cereals production, especially in East Germany, Finland and Sweden, where the magnitude of the rate of technical regress is more pronounced.

Table 32 - Elasticities of IDF with respect to time (cereals and milk). (Source: Own calculation)

Country	Cereals				Milk			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Austria	-0.0003	0.0202	-0.0673	0.0642	-0.0009	0.0100	-0.0409	0.0321
Belgium	-0.0170	0.0188	-0.0608	0.0370	0.0125	0.0238	-0.0529	0.0729
Czechia	0.0004	0.0338	-0.0971	0.0797	-0.0076	0.0154	-0.0505	0.0318
Finland	0.0136	0.0222	-0.0462	0.0782	0.0132	0.0144	-0.0286	0.0556
France	-0.0043	0.0089	-0.0261	0.0284	-0.0009	0.0085	-0.0294	0.0249
West Germany	-0.0319	0.0613	-0.1562	0.0940	0.0288	0.0096	0.0031	0.0834
East Germany	0.0288	0.0365	-0.1003	0.0983	-0.0487	0.0707	-0.1825	0.1159
Ireland	-0.0087	0.0232	-0.1129	0.0580	0.0095	0.0151	-0.0366	0.0543
Italy	0.0012	0.0154	-0.0559	0.0623	0.0044	0.0139	-0.0601	0.0816
Romania	-0.0092	0.0341	-0.1222	0.0909	-0.0015	0.0255	-0.0988	0.0776
Spain	-0.0046	0.0235	-0.0848	0.0531	-0.0139	0.0264	-0.1023	0.0626
Sweden	0.0111	0.0146	-0.0500	0.0556	0.0017	0.0130	-0.0692	0.0417
United Kingdom	-0.0014	0.0183	-0.0678	0.0448	-0.0141	0.0329	-0.1164	0.0619

As far as the milk production is concerned, the technological progress is revealed in Austria, Belgium, France, East Germany, Romania, Spain, and the United Kingdom. However, the magnitude of the rate of technical progress is considerable only in the United Kingdom and Spain. On the other hand, the considerable technical regress connected with the loss of competitiveness was detected in estimates for West Germany, Finland, and Belgium.

4.2.1.3 TECHNICAL EFFICIENCY

This chapter provides a discussion on the components of the country-specific overall technical efficiency and a comparison of trends in transient technical efficiency development in cereals and milk production in the selected European countries. The overall comparison of technical efficiency levels among selected for the analysis countries will be carried out using meta-frontier analysis and presented in chapter 4.2.2.

Table 33 provides overall technical efficiency scores together with both components: transient technical efficiency and persistent technical efficiency. The overall technical efficiency estimates indicate that farmers have the average overall technical efficiency

in the interval between 0.82 and 0.91, meaning that, they can reduce their costs by 9% up to 18% to produce the same volumes of outputs.

Table 33 - Overall technical efficiency and its decomposition (cereals). (Source: Own calculation)

Country	Overall TE				Transient TE				Persistent TE			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Austria	0.8642	0.0282	0.6869	0.9337	0.9399	0.0163	0.7803	0.9848	0.9194	0.0241	0.8069	0.9672
Belgium	0.8194	0.0625	0.4779	0.9373	0.9263	0.0343	0.6686	0.9837	0.8842	0.0544	0.6125	0.9704
Czechia	0.8690	0.0279	0.6607	0.9479	0.9396	0.0154	0.8183	0.9857	0.9248	0.0240	0.7602	0.9783
Finland	0.8282	0.0473	0.5730	0.9319	0.9236	0.0232	0.6824	0.9838	0.8966	0.0433	0.6716	0.9639
France	0.8677	0.0333	0.6672	0.9528	0.9472	0.0146	0.7949	0.9909	0.9161	0.0306	0.7673	0.9763
West Germany	0.8611	0.0439	0.4899	0.9618	0.8917	0.0445	0.5048	0.9840	0.9656	0.0049	0.9400	0.9785
East Germany	0.8600	0.0327	0.6539	0.9439	0.9203	0.0302	0.7128	0.9831	0.9344	0.0154	0.8424	0.9753
Ireland	0.8298	0.0489	0.4879	0.9323	0.8995	0.0472	0.5320	0.9836	0.9224	0.0209	0.8486	0.9565
Italy	0.8266	0.0393	0.5453	0.9220	0.9076	0.0268	0.6580	0.9710	0.9105	0.0301	0.7302	0.9652
Romania	0.8467	0.0348	0.6222	0.9299	0.9451	0.0102	0.8776	0.9763	0.8959	0.0341	0.7087	0.9633
Spain	0.8241	0.0638	0.4921	0.9398	0.9540	0.0076	0.9146	0.9769	0.8638	0.0657	0.5378	0.9665
Sweden	0.8774	0.0330	0.5692	0.9423	0.9209	0.0321	0.6060	0.9819	0.9528	0.0103	0.9053	0.9751
United Kingdom	0.8600	0.0389	0.6673	0.9543	0.9396	0.0188	0.7926	0.9868	0.9152	0.0349	0.7554	0.9744

The overall technical efficiency is relatively dense around the mean and skewed to higher values in the majority of analyzed countries. Slightly higher values of the standard deviation indicating intra-sector variability are revealed in Belgium and Spain. The highest polarization, that is the highest difference between the most technically efficient cereals producer and the least technically efficient one, can be found in West Germany. On the other hand, the lowest polarization is uncovered in Austrian cereals production. This may signalize about the fact that Austrian cereals producers are exposed to high competitive pressure which, however, contributes to the resource efficiency and sustainability of Austrian agriculture.

In addition, table 33 presents two components of the overall technical efficiency - transient and persistent technical efficiency. The results indicate that estimates of the persistent part, associated with systematic failures in the production, exhibit lower mean scores and higher variation in almost all the analyzed countries as compared to the time-varying part of technical efficiency (Germany, Ireland, Italy, and Sweden are the exceptions). Moreover, the results show that many farms are protractedly falling behind the most efficient producers in the majority of the analyzed countries. For Ireland and Sweden, transient technical efficiency also shows a higher variability compare to the persistent one. Moreover, in Ireland and Sweden, the transient technical efficiency experienced a substantial variation over the analyzed period (see Figure C1 in Annex II). The transient efficiency development has no common pattern in all the analyzed countries. We can conclude that the development of technical efficiency is predominantly stochastic in the European countries. The technical efficiency fluctuations may also arise, apart from previously described causations, due to shocks connected with weather conditions and climatic changes. To minimize negative shocks as well as to improve long term efficiency of input usage as essential components of sustainable agriculture, an agri-policy intervention is required to build

an agribusiness environment supporting investments to R&D, new technologies, education and knowledge transfer.

Table 34 - Overall technical efficiency and its decomposition (milk). (Source: Own calculation)

Country	Overall TE				Transient TE				Persistent TE			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Austria	0.9187	0.0122	0.8224	0.9579	0.9601	0.0093	0.8514	0.9901	0.9568	0.0080	0.9178	0.9769
Belgium	0.8534	0.0494	0.5458	0.9533	0.9454	0.0181	0.8180	0.9870	0.9026	0.0479	0.6378	0.9758
Czechia	0.8344	0.0542	0.5618	0.9398	0.9420	0.0167	0.8136	0.9868	0.8857	0.0540	0.6096	0.9781
Finland	0.8954	0.0307	0.7539	0.9505	0.9679	0.0061	0.9144	0.9882	0.9251	0.0306	0.7889	0.9733
France	0.8681	0.0423	0.6071	0.9586	0.9506	0.0155	0.7819	0.9917	0.9131	0.0404	0.6581	0.9778
West Germany	0.9524	0.0101	0.8966	0.9740	0.9980	0.0000	0.9979	0.9981	0.9543	0.0102	0.8984	0.9759
East Germany	0.8083	0.0987	0.3762	0.9804	0.8092	0.0988	0.3767	0.9816	0.9988	0.0000	0.9988	0.9988
Ireland	0.9121	0.0422	0.7517	0.9748	0.9965	0.0001	0.9962	0.9969	0.9153	0.0423	0.7544	0.9780
Italy	0.9168	0.0221	0.7919	0.9637	0.9965	0.0000	0.9963	0.9967	0.9200	0.0221	0.7947	0.9670
Romania	0.8290	0.0372	0.5884	0.9165	0.9008	0.0346	0.6750	0.9743	0.9201	0.0174	0.7929	0.9616
Spain	0.9283	0.0216	0.8148	0.9728	0.9977	0.0000	0.9976	0.9978	0.9305	0.0216	0.8168	0.9750
Sweden	0.9143	0.0181	0.7889	0.9642	0.9491	0.0161	0.8306	0.9870	0.9632	0.0079	0.9342	0.9793
United Kingdom	0.7288	0.0764	0.3702	0.9905	0.9224	0.0330	0.6852	0.9905	0.7897	0.0745	0.4947	1.0000

Table 34 presents the country-specific overall technical efficiency, transient technical efficiency and persistent technical efficiency scores for milk production. The average overall technical efficiency is between 73 % and 95%. That is, on average, farms producing milk can reduce their costs by 5% up to 27% to produce the same volumes of outputs in analyzed countries. Similarly to the cereals production, the overall technical efficiency of farms producing milk is relatively dense around the mean and skewed to higher values in the majority of the analyzed countries. Slightly higher intra-sector variability is detected for the Czech Republic and the United Kingdom. Moreover, British milk production is characterized by the highest difference between the most technically efficient milk producer and the least technically efficient one. On the other hand, the lowest polarization is uncovered for West and East Germany, followed by Austria.

The decomposition of overall technical efficiency indicates that the transient part exhibit higher mean scores and lower variability in almost all the analyzed countries as compared to the persistent technical efficiency. This suggests that many farmers are, from a long-run perspective, falling behind the most efficient farms in the production of milk in the majority of the analyzed countries. The mean scores of time-varying technical efficiencies are found to be lower than the persistent one only for East Germany, Romania, and Sweden. As far as the variability of these components are concerned, the standard deviation of the transient technical efficiency is higher than the standard deviation of the persistent one in Austria, East Germany, Romania, Sweden, and the United Kingdom.

In line with the results of cereals production, the development of the transient technical efficiency of farms producing milk is predominantly stochastic in the analyzed European countries (see Figure D1 in Annex II) and has no common pattern. However, the drop can be found in the years 2008 and 2013 in the majority of the analyzed

countries. These results point out the importance of recognizing regional specificities in agricultural policy settings.

4.2.1.4 TOTAL FACTOR PRODUCTIVITY

Figure 6 provides the TFP growth estimates using the Törnqvist-Theil index and its decomposition for cereals production. Although the TFP estimates reveal significant differences in the TFP development patterns among analyzed countries, we can conclude that the cereals production in the majority of the analyzed countries can be characterized by negative TFP growth in 2004-2017, evaluated on country samples means. Predominantly positive TFP change is revealed only in the Czech Republic and the United Kingdom.

Figure 6a - Cereals: Development and decomposition of TFP (part 1). (Source: Own calculation)

Figure 6b - Cereals: Development and decomposition of TFP (part 2). (Source: Own calculation)

The scale effect is the main source of the negative development. On the other hand, the effect of technical change contributes positively to the TFP growth, especially in the beginning of analyzed period suggesting huge investments into modernization and technological innovations implemented in the first half of the analyzed period.

Figure 7 presents the TFP estimates for milk production. Similarly to the cereals production, the TFP development paths are predominantly negative in the analyzed countries within the period 2004-2017, evaluated on country samples means.

Figure 7a - Milk: Development and decomposition of TFP (part 1). (Source: Own calculation)

Figure 7b -Milk: Development and decomposition of TFP (part 2). (Source: Own calculation)

Moreover, a growing tendency to a negative TFP development path can be observed. The Czech Republic might be an example of this development, where the positive values of TFP index changed to negative ones in the middle of the analyzed period. However, the negative values of TFP index in the last five years (2013-2017) predominated in all the analyzed countries.

The scale effect and the effect of technical change are the main sources of the TFP development. The negative contribution of the technical change is revealed especially in the Czech Republic, Finland, Spain, and the United Kingdom in the second half of the analyzed period. On the other hand, in the beginning of the analyzed period the effect of technical change in the majority of the analyzed countries contributed to the TFP growth positively. This suggests that considerable investments in modernization and technological innovations were implemented in the first half of the analyzed period also in the production of milk.

4.2.2 META-FRONTIER ANALYSIS

This chapter provides the results of a comparative analysis of technical efficiency and productivity based on the meta-frontier estimates on agriculture level, more precisely in cereals and milk production. The structure of this chapter is as follows. First, we present the results of the meta-frontier input distance function estimates for cereal and milk production, then we present and compare the basic statistical characteristics of technical efficiency and productivity among the analyzed countries.

4.2.2.1 CEREALS PRODUCTION

4.2.2.1.1 Technology and technical change

Annex II – Table G1 presents the parameters estimates of the stochastic meta-frontier input distance function models for the cereals production. The meta-frontier model satisfies the theoretical assumptions of input-distance function, namely the properties of monotonicity and concavity in inputs, evaluated on the sample mean. Moreover, most of the estimated parameters are highly statistically significant, even at the 1% significance level. Table 35 provides only the first-order parameters and technical change parameters estimates of this meta-frontier IDF for cereal production. The elasticities of the IDF with respect to inputs are in line with country IDF estimates. That is, material inputs dominate the cost structure of the cereals production, followed by labour, and the cost-share of capital is the lowest. The elasticities of the IDF with respect to outputs point out to the importance of both cereals and other production. Moreover, the sum of elasticities of output (evaluated on the sample mean) confirms that the potential of economies of scale can still be exploited, meaning that costs can be reduced if farmers increase the volume of production.

The majority of technical change parameters are statistically significant at the level of 10% and reveal the slight technical regress that was accelerating in the analyzed period. The biased technical change is land using and labour and capital saving. On the other hand, is capital Moreover, the time effect on elasticity of IDF with respect to animal production (yA00) is revealed. This may imply particular changes in production structure.

Table 35 - First-order parameters and technical change parameters estimate (cereals). (Source: Own calculation)

First-order parameters			
Variable	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
In_yC	-0.2605	0.0111	0.0000
In_yAOC	-0.1359	0.0077	0.0000
In_yAOC	-0.3117	0.0092	0.0000
In_xL	0.1169	0.0239	0.0000
In_xW	0.2900	0.0182	0.0000
In_xK	0.1118	0.0157	0.0000
Technical change parameters			
Variable	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
t	-0.0241	0.0022	0.0000
t ²	0.0127	0.0008	0.0000
In_yCt	0.0028	0.0015	0.0620
In_yAOCt	0.0004	0.0010	0.6530
In_yAOCt	-0.0030	0.0009	0.0010
In_xLt	-0.0084	0.0032	0.0090
In_xWt	0.0080	0.0022	0.0000
In_xKt	0.0084	0.0025	0.0010

4.2.2.1.2 Technical efficiency and productivity comparison

Table 36 provides the country-level overall technical efficiency estimates for the cereals production. The estimates of the transient technical efficiency are presented in Annex II, Table H1. The mean values of overall technical efficiency are very close. Since we did not estimate the persistent technical inefficiency, this holds for transient technical efficiency as well. Given this, we can state that there are no considerable differences in technical efficiency among the analyzed countries in the case of cereals production, evaluated on the sample mean. In other words, the frontier technologies in cereals production in the analyzed countries are similar and farmers are highly efficient.

Table 36 - Meta-frontier overall technical efficiency (cereals). (Source: Own calculation)

Country	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max
Austria	0.9083	0.0293	0.6941	0.9842
Belgium	0.9102	0.0213	0.7632	0.9603
Czechia	0.9068	0.0305	0.6762	0.9814
Finland	0.9041	0.0396	0.6214	0.9832
France	0.9069	0.0291	0.7322	0.9872
West Germany	0.9086	0.0260	0.7209	0.9799
East Germany	0.9078	0.0271	0.6899	0.9715
Ireland	0.9079	0.0286	0.7489	0.9629
Italy	0.9066	0.0367	0.7008	0.9740
Romania	0.9082	0.0350	0.6426	0.9755
Spain	0.9065	0.0387	0.6605	0.9670
Sweden	0.9080	0.0274	0.6931	0.9724
United Kingdom	0.9080	0.0261	0.7186	0.9712

Table 37 provides the meta-frontier TFP estimates employing the Törnqvist-Theil index. Since we did not get consistent results for TFP index including all components we present the version which does not include the scale component, that is, TFP

includes only technical efficiency and technical change component (i.e. TFP in the situation of constant returns to scale). The results suggest that the levels of indices do not differ significantly. In other words, if we assume constant returns to scale, the productivity levels are comparable among the countries.

Table 37 - Meta-frontier total factor productivity (cereals). (Source: Own calculation)

GMM	Cereals	
	TE&TC	
Country	Mean	Std.Dev.
Austria	1.0009	0.0462
Belgium	1.0063	0.0569
Czechia	0.9879	0.0457
Finland	0.9950	0.0471
France	0.9974	0.0489
West Germany	1.0011	0.0464
East Germany	0.9965	0.0411
Ireland	1.0054	0.0424
Italy	1.0018	0.0532
Romania	1.0090	0.0476
Spain	1.0151	0.0521
Sweden	1.0051	0.0423
United Kingdom	1.0042	0.0380

4.2.2.2 MILK PRODUCTION

4.2.2.2.1 Technology and technical change

Table 38 provides first-order parameters and technical change parameters estimates of the stochastic meta-frontier input distance functions for milk production. The whole set of estimated parameters of the meta-frontier model describing milk production is presented in Annex II – Table J1. As far as the theoretical consistency of IDF is concerned, we can again conclude that the monotonicity requirements, as well as the requirements of the concavity in inputs, are met by the estimate, evaluated on the sample mean.

The first-order parameters of IDF, that are highly significant even at the 1 % significance level, and in line with the results of country-specific IDFs, reveal the high material cost share in the milk production. The share of material in the total input is 59%. The rest of costs represent labour with 24% share, capital with 12% share and land with 5% share, evaluated on the sample mean. Milk represents an output with the highest score of the absolute value of output elasticity. The absolute value of the sum of the output elasticities is lower than 1, suggesting that the economies of scale can be exploited.

The parameter on technical change (δ_t) is not statistically significant at the 5 % significance level. The parameters δ_{mt} , that measure the annual rate of change in the sample average farm's estimated output elasticities, are statistically significant at the 10 % level in the case of milk (yC) and other output (yA00). The biased technical change resulted from relative resource scarcity is statistically significant at the 10%

level only in the case of capital and, in the line with country IDF estimates, is capital using.

Table 38 - First-order parameters and technical change parameters estimate (milk). (Source: Own calculation)

First-order parameters			
Variable	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_yC	-0.4009	0.0071	0.0000
ln_yAOC	-0.1688	0.0057	0.0000
ln_yAOO	-0.1833	0.0039	0.0000
ln_xL	0.0485	0.0089	0.0000
ln_xW	0.2399	0.0116	0.0000
ln_xK	0.1189	0.0092	0.0000
Technical change parameters			
Variable	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
t	-0.0040	0.0029	0.1620
t ²	0.0052	0.0007	0.0000
ln_yCt	0.0022	0.0012	0.0680
ln_yAOCt	-0.0003	0.0010	0.7800
ln_yAOOt	0.0012	0.0007	0.0910
ln_xLt	0.0024	0.0018	0.1860
ln_xWt	0.0029	0.0023	0.1990
ln_xKt	-0.0049	0.0019	0.0080

4.2.2.2.2 Technical efficiency and productivity comparison

Table 39 provides the country-level overall technical efficiency estimates for milk production. The estimates of the transient technical efficiency are presented in Annex II, Table K1. The mean values of overall technical efficiency suggest that milk production in the analyzed countries is highly efficient and sustainable.

Table 39 - Meta-frontier overall technical efficiency (milk). (Source: Own calculation)

Country	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max
Austria	0.9471	0.0112	0.8601	0.9830
Belgium	0.9474	0.0108	0.8536	0.9772
Czechia	0.9477	0.0115	0.8409	0.9876
Finland	0.9461	0.0152	0.8466	0.9863
France	0.9476	0.0099	0.8494	0.9850
West Germany	0.9480	0.0097	0.8632	0.9858
East Germany	0.9470	0.0099	0.8830	0.9811
Ireland	0.9466	0.0137	0.8379	0.9724
Italy	0.9450	0.0193	0.7866	0.9878
Romania	0.9442	0.0232	0.7694	0.9891
Spain	0.9456	0.0170	0.7862	0.9849
Sweden	0.9470	0.0119	0.8187	0.9875
United Kingdom	0.9472	0.0116	0.8436	0.9763

Table 40 provides the meta-frontier TFP estimates employing the Törnqvist-Theil index. We obtained the results that are similar to the results relevant to cereal production. TFP index with all components does not provide consistent results, meaning that we present the version which includes technical efficiency and technical change component only (i.e. TFP in the situation of constant returns to scale). These

results show that the levels of indices do not differ significantly. In other words, if we assume constant returns to scale, the productivity level is comparable among the countries.

Table 40 - Meta-frontier total factor productivity (milk). (Source: Own calculation)

GMM	Milk	
	TE&TC	
Country	Mean	Std.Dev.
Austria	1.0002	0.0232
Belgium	1.0005	0.0219
Czechia	1.0005	0.0213
Finland	0.9991	0.0188
France	1.0007	0.0212
West Germany	1.0025	0.0205
East Germany	0.9951	0.0206
Ireland	0.9996	0.0180
Italy	0.9978	0.0266
Romania	0.9968	0.0267
Spain	0.9985	0.0271
Sweden	1.0001	0.0233
United Kingdom	1.0003	0.0198

4.3 SALMON PRODUCTION

4.3.1 IDF ESTIMATE, TECHNOLOGY AND ECONOMY OF SCALE

Table 41 provides the parameters estimates of the stochastic frontier input distance function model for the salmon production.

Table 41 - IDF parameters estimates (salmon). (Source: Own calculation)

Variable	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_y	-0.9451	0.0323	0.0000
ln_xL	0.1486	0.0549	0.0080
ln_xM	0.6936	0.0524	0.0000
T	0.0114	0.0056	0.0460
ln_y 2	-0.0604	0.0305	0.0510
ln_xL 2	0.0591	0.0325	0.0730
ln_xM 2	0.2014	0.0547	0.0000
ln_xLxM	-0.1011	0.0374	0.0080
t 2	-0.0069	0.0026	0.0100
ln_yt	0.0120	0.0049	0.0160
ln_xLt	-0.0012	0.0119	0.9160
ln_xMt	-0.0030	0.0110	0.7840
ln_yxL	-0.0100	0.0276	0.7190
ln_yxM	0.0243	0.0312	0.4400
Dsmall&middle	0.1729	0.0608	0.0060
_cons	-0.0606	0.0397	0.1310
			p-value
AR(2)	0.400		0.690
Hansen test	76.65	$\chi^2[275]$	1.000

The estimates are consistent with theoretical assumptions, that is, the estimation inherits the properties of IDF - the assumptions of monotonicity and quasi-concavity in inputs - evaluated on the sample mean. The first-order parameters of IDF are highly significant, even at the 1% significance level. The majority of second-order parameters are statistically significant as well, at least at the 10% significance level. Moreover, the validity of the instruments employed in GMM is proved by the Hansen J test and by the Arellano-Bond autocorrelation test.

The first-order parameters suggest that the salmon production is characterized by high share of material in the total input (69%) and the low share of labour (15%). The cost-share of capital is about 16%, evaluated on the sample mean. The absolute value of output elasticity is slightly lower than 1, meaning that no considerable effect of economies of scale can be expected. The estimate of the parameter δ_t is statistically significant at the 5% level and reveals the slight increase in production costs, which is decelerating over the analyzed period ($\delta_{tt} < 0$). The parameters of biased technical change resulted from relative resource scarcity are not statistically significant even at the 10% significance level.

Table 42 and Figure 8 present the basic statistical characteristics of the salmon producers' returns to scale. The sample mean is only slightly larger than 1, indicating that salmon producers operate on almost constant returns to scale, in other words, in optimal size, evaluated on the sample mean. Figure 8 reveals that returns to scale slightly increased over the analyzed period 2008 - 2018.

Table 42 - Returns to scale (salmon). (Source: Own calculation)

	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.		
Total sample	1.0653	0.0875	0.8287	1.3991		
	Min.	1 st Q	Median	Mean	3th Q	Max.
Total sample	0.8287	1.0059	1.0761	1.0653	1.1250	1.3991
Large producers	0.8287	0.9545	1.0086	1.0018	1.0441	1.1835
Small & Middle producers	1.0370	1.0970	1.1230	1.1320	1.1530	1.3990

Histogram of data\$RTS_GMM

Figure 8 - Distribution of returns to scale (total sample - salmon). (Source: Own calculation)

However, the scale efficiency is more pronounced in the case of large producers. Table 42 shows that large producers operate with constant return to scale, that is, their firm sizes are optimal, evaluated on the sample mean. Figure 9 adds the distribution of the returns to scale in the sample of large salmon producers and the development of RTS in the analyzed period.

Figure 9 - Distribution of returns to scale (large producers - salmon). (Source: Own calculation)

The increasing returns to scale are revealed in the sample of small and middle enterprises, see Table 42 and Figure 10. We can conclude that small and middle salmon producers have a substantial potential to improve their productivity, as well as profitability by increasing scales of operations.

Figure 10 - Distribution of returns to scale (small & middle producers - salmon). (Source: Own calculation)

4.3.2 TECHNICAL CHANGE

Table 43 presents the results of technical change estimation in the salmon production. Although, a positive mean value reveals that the technical regress is the predominant feature of Norwegian salmon production, according to Figure 11 this technical regress was decelerating over time and changed to be positive at the end of analyzed period. This may indicate that salmon producers invested in new technologies during the observed to decrease costs.

Table 43 - Technical change (salmon). (Source: Own calculation)

	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.		
Total sample	0.0115	0.0224	-0.0520	0.0825		
	Min.	1 st Q	Median	Mean	3th Q	Max.
Total sample	-0.0520	-0.0047	0.0098	0.0115	0.0262	0.0825
Large producers	-0.0355	0.0078	0.0231	0.0233	0.0373	0.0825
Small & Middle producers	-0.0520	-0.0126	-0.0010	-0.0010	0.0102	0.0380

Figure 11 - Distribution of technical change (total sample - salmon). (Source: Own calculation)

According to Table 43 and Figure 12, the mentioned technical regress is revealed especially in large companies. On the other hand, the technical change is predominantly positive in the sample of small and middle producers, see Figure 13. This suggests that small and middle producers had heavily invested to stay competitive on the market.

Figure 12 - Distribution of technical change (large producers - salmon). (Source: Own calculation)

Figure 13 - Distribution of technical change (small & middle producers - salmon). (Source: Own calculation)

4.3.3 TECHNICAL EFFICIENCY

The competitiveness is driven not only by technical progress but also by the input use efficiency. Table 44 shows that the overall technical efficiency is on average 83.5 %, that is, the salmon producers can reduce their costs by 16% to produce the same volume of output. However, the lowest technical efficiency score (60%) reveals that there may exist more considerable space for improvements for some producer.

Table 44 - Overall technical efficiency (salmon). (Source: Own calculation)

	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.		
Total sample	0.8347	0.0557	0.6037	0.9331		
	Min.	1 st Q	Median	Mean	3th Q	Max.
Total sample	0.6037	0.8094	0.8454	0.8347	0.8692	0.9331
Large producers	0.6037	0.8229	0.8490	0.8389	0.8694	0.9220
Small & Middle producers	0.6886	0.7954	0.8340	0.8305	0.8688	0.9331

Figure 14 - Distribution of overall technical efficiency (total sample - salmon). (Source: Own calculation)

No significant differences were revealed between the group of large and the group of small companies, if we compare the mean or median value. According to the Figure 15 and Figure 16, it is obvious, that the overall technical efficiency scores are more

concentrated around the mean value in the group of large companies than it is in the case of the group of small ones.

Figure 15 - Distribution of overall technical efficiency (large producers - salmon). (Source: Own calculation)

Figure 16 - Distribution of overall technical efficiency (small & middle producers - salmon). (Source: Own calculation)

Table 4.3.5 and Figure 17 presents the decomposition of the overall technical efficiency into transient and persistent parts. The persistent part of overall technical efficiency exhibits lower mean and median compared to the transient part. This indicates that salmon production is characterized more by systematic failures than short-term shocks.

Table 45 - Decomposition of overall technical efficiency (salmon). (Source: Own calculation)

Transient technical efficiency						
	Min.	1 st Q	Median	Mean	3th Q	Max.
Total sample	0.8201	0.9223	0.9322	0.9301	0.9421	0.9766
Large producers	0.8201	0.9240	0.9328	0.9307	0.9415	0.9669
Small & Middle producers	0.8314	0.9211	0.9317	0.9295	0.9427	0.9766
Persistent technical efficiency						
	Min.	1 st Q	Median	Mean	3th Q	Max.
Total sample	0.6413	0.8718	0.9076	0.8974	0.9346	0.9722
Large producers	0.6413	0.8852	0.9100	0.9012	0.9354	0.9667
Small & Middle producers	0.7653	0.8565	0.8973	0.8934	0.9324	0.9722

Figure 17 - Distribution of transient (TTE) and persistent (PTE) technical efficiency (total sample - salmon). (Source: Own calculation)

As far as size groups are concerned, we can conclude that there are no significant differences among the group of large and the group of small and middle producers. This holds for both parts of overall technical efficiency, as well as for the development of the transient technical efficiency (see Figure 18 and Figure 19).

Figure 18 - Distribution of transient technical efficiency (salmon). (Source: Own calculation)

Figure 19 - Distribution of persistent technical efficiency (salmon). (Source: Own calculation)

To summarize our findings, the Norwegian salmon production can be characterized by relatively high overall technical efficiency. However, regardless of the size of enterprise, producers and policy makers should especially focus on overcoming the long-term inefficiency connected with structural problems and non-competitive market conditions. The elimination of this persistent resource waste brings the increase of profitability, competitiveness, and sustainability.

4.4 ITALIAN TOMATO PROCESSING

4.4.1 IDF ESTIMATE, TECHNOLOGY AND ECONOMY OF SCALE

Table 46 provides the parameters estimates of the stochastic frontier input distance function model for tomato processing. The estimation inherits the properties of IDF - monotonicity and quasi-concavity in inputs - evaluated on the sample mean. The first-order parameters of IDF are highly significant, even at the 1% significance level. Majority of second-order parameters are statistically significant as well, at least at the 10% level. The Hansen J test and the Arellano-Bond autocorrelation test indicate the validity of the instruments employed in GMM.

Table 46 - IDF parameters estimates (tomato processing). (Source: Own calculation)

Variable	Parameter	Std.Err.	P-value
ln_y	-0.993	0.011	0.000
ln_xL	0.194	0.027	0.000
ln_xM	0.768	0.029	0.000
t	0.006	0.006	0.282
ln_y_2	-0.001	0.007	0.942
ln_xL_2	0.087	0.035	0.015
ln_xM_2	0.156	0.068	0.023
ln_xLxM	-0.123	0.045	0.008
t_2	-0.001	0.003	0.762
ln_yt	0.006	0.003	0.028
ln_xLt	0.003	0.006	0.669
ln_xMt	-0.001	0.008	0.867
ln_yxL	0.000	0.016	0.993
ln_yxM	-0.040	0.018	0.027
Constant	-0.031	0.025	0.225
	Test statistic		P-value
AR(2)	-1.200		0.228
Hansen test	79.58 (332)		1.000

The tomato processing is characterized by high share of material in the total input (77%). The labour cost share is about 15%. The capital cost-share is considerably low, but it corresponds with the information we have in the dataset. The absolute value of output elasticity is equal to 1. This suggests that tomato processors have optimal size of production. The estimate of the parameter δ_t (technical change) is not statistically significant at the 5% level. Moreover, the estimate reveals that not even other variables related to the technological change are statistically significant, except of the output. The F-test rejects statistically significant impact of technological change even at 10 % significance level.

Table 47 and Figure 20 present the basic statistical characteristics of the tomato processors' returns to scale. The sample mean is equal to 1. The same holds for the processors' size groups. That is, small, middle, large as well as very large processors produce with constant returns to scale. This suggest that the size of production is optimal, at least from the static point of view.

Table 47 - Returns to scale (tomato). (Source: Own calculation)

	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.		
Total sample	1.0087	0.0472	0.8243	1.1824		
	Min.	1 st Q	Median	Mean	3th Q	Max.
Total sample	0.8243	0.9762	1.0110	1.0087	1.0399	1.1824
Small producers	0.8659	0.9453	0.9793	0.9909	1.0170	1.1221
Middle producers	0.9105	0.9852	1.0178	1.0163	1.0448	1.1698
Large producers	0.8719	0.9787	1.0124	1.0087	1.0379	1.1548
Very large producers	0.9259	0.9638	0.9947	0.9948	1.0215	1.0626

Figure 20 - Distribution of returns to scale (tomato). (Source: Own calculation)

4.3.2 TECHNICAL CHANGE

The estimate did not reveal significant technological change. Table 48 and Figure 21 provide the distribution of technological change in the whole sample as well as according to the size groups. Despite the fact that the technological change is not pronounced in the whole sample, we can observe a tendency to a positive technological change in the last years. This may imply the increase in investment activities at the end of analyzed period.

Table 48 - Technical change (tomato). (Source: Own calculation)

	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.		
Total sample	1.0087	0.0472	0.8243	1.1824		
	Min.	1 st Q	Median	Mean	3th Q	Max.
Total sample	-0.0237	0.0005	0.0066	0.0064	0.0120	0.0414
Small producers	-0.0237	-0.0129	-0.0100	-0.0095	-0.0055	0.0066
Middle producers	-0.0159	-0.0020	0.0023	0.0018	0.0057	0.0145
Large producers	-0.0126	0.0079	0.0112	0.0112	0.0146	0.0246
Very large producers	0.0168	0.0223	0.0259	0.0278	0.0331	0.0414

Histogram of data\$TC_GMM

Figure 21 - Distribution of technical change (tomato). (Source: Own calculation)

4.3.3 TECHNICAL EFFICIENCY

Table 49 shows that the overall technical efficiency is on average 76.2 %. This indicates a considerable space for improvements. In other words, the tomato processors operating on the technological frontier have significantly lower costs, approximately by 24 %, as compared to the sample average. This represents a considerable competitive advantage for efficient processors.

Table 49 - Overall technical efficiency (tomato). (Source: Own calculation)

	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.		
Total sample	0.762	0.1269	0.0133	0.9622		
	Min.	1 st Q	Median	Mean	3th Q	Max.
Total sample	0.4069	0.7009	0.7757	0.762	0.8347	0.9622
Small producers	0.4575	0.7414	0.7909	0.789	0.8594	0.9455
Middle producers	0.4523	0.7016	0.7677	0.7611	0.8318	0.9542
Large producers	0.4332	0.6992	0.7686	0.7591	0.8325	0.9622
Very large producers	0.4069	0.6882	0.7759	0.7517	0.831	0.9024

Figure 22 - Distribution of overall technical efficiency (tomato). (Source: Own calculation)

Table 50 - Decomposition of overall technical efficiency (tomato). (Source: Own calculation)

Transient technical efficiency						
	Min.	1 st Q	Median	Mean	3th Q	Max.
Total sample	0.4126	0.7101	0.784	0.7709	0.8423	0.9751
Small producers	0.4607	0.7503	0.7966	0.7948	0.8633	0.9499
Middle producers	0.4592	0.7089	0.7775	0.7697	0.8377	0.9644
Large producers	0.4384	0.7094	0.7806	0.7691	0.842	0.9751
Very large producers	0.4126	0.6949	0.784	0.7598	0.8421	0.9121
Persistent technical efficiency						
	Min.	1 st Q	Median	Mean	3th Q	Max.
Total sample	0.9539	0.9860	0.9894	0.9883	0.9924	0.9969
Small producers	0.9841	0.9882	0.9930	0.9924	0.9959	0.9969
Middle producers	0.9615	0.9858	0.9894	0.9887	0.9920	0.9960
Large producers	0.9539	0.9850	0.9884	0.9871	0.9922	0.9960
Very large producers	0.9835	0.9868	0.9897	0.9893	0.9920	0.9921

The persistent technical inefficiency estimates indicate that tomato processors are characterized by considerably low level of systematic failures. On the other hand, the transient inefficiency is pronounced. Moreover, we can observe significant differences among middle, large and very large processors in overall technical efficiency. However, small processors seem to be more efficient. This suggests that small processors can cope better with non-systematic management problems and market shocks.

5. TECHNICAL CHANGE AND INNOVATIONS

This chapter presents the findings on the relations between the technical change and output, input quantities, and prices. Further, it discusses the impact of technological change on consumer and producer surplus as well as the total welfare effects and identifies role of innovations and main actors in the analyzed food value chains.

5.1 IMPACT OF TECHNICAL CHANGE ON QUANTITIES AND PRICES

The analysis of the impact of technical change on the output and input quantities and prices uses the technical change elasticities estimates that we obtained from IDF country estimates for food processing industries and agriculture. In particular, we investigate the relation between technical change and quantities of inputs and outputs by the use of panel regression models. The relation between technical change and prices is evaluated using the graphical analysis and aggregate price levels since our database does not contain information on individual prices.

Table 51 - Impact of technical change on output in food processing industry (sectors_dummy). (Source: Own calculation)

Food	Austria	Belgium	Czechia	Finland	France	Germany	Italy	Romania	Spain	Sweden	United Kingdom
TC	0.125	-8.129	-17.089	1.154	2.822	4.430	-115.716	0.501	-16.772	6.036	1.429
		*	***	**	***	***	***	***	***	***	
TC_101	-5.106	-22.435	-8.364	0.850	0.056	-5.686	-18.735	-0.482	6.845	2.586	2.606
	*	**	*			**	***	***	**	**	
TC_105	6.378	-26.742	51.474	-3.720	6.359	1.596	-55.008	0.678	-25.312	5.017	2.776
	***	**	***	*	***		***	***	*		
TC_106	18.262	-14.623	-163.606	-1.509	-1.008	-5.915	24.127	-0.148	7.720	-3.220	3.973
			***				***				
TC_107	4.420	40.995	-18.639	-3.799	-4.430	1.061	-15.588	0.183	-10.044	-5.811	0.841
		***	***	***	***		***		***	***	
_cons	10.890	10.079	7.488	6.903	7.885	10.235	9.218	5.236	8.346	7.304	10.554
	***	***	***	***	***	***		***	***	***	***

Tables 51 and 52 provide the estimate on the impact of technical change on food processing output using sectors (Table 51) and size (Table 52) dummy variables.⁶ Table 51 shows that the technological change has a significant impact on the food processing output in majority of countries. The overall positive impact was estimated in Finland, France, Germany, Romania and Sweden. However, the inter-sectoral differences are pronounced. This especially holds for slaughtering, dairy and bakery industry. That is, the technical change effect is country and sector specific. For example, the positive effect in Germany turns to be negative in slaughtering industry. We cannot observe any common patterns among the analyzed countries.

⁶ Annex III provides complete model estimates. This also holds for the model results presented in the rest of this chapter.

Table 52 shows the size effect in the analyzed relation. The size effect is significant in all analyzed countries. Moreover, the results suggest that the positive effect of technical change increases with the size of the food processing company.

Table 52 - Impact of technical change on output in food processing industry (size_dummy). (Source: Own calculation)

Food	Austria	Belgium	Czechia	Finland	France	Germany	Italy	Romania	Spain	Sweden	United Kingdom
TC_small		-5.488	-116.697	-10.988	-13.152	0.325	-53.494	1.933	-104.960	-13.185	2.657
		***	***	***	***		***	***	***	***	
TC	-119.100	-21.409	-31.766	4.002	3.237	-2.164	-129.087	-0.431	-45.081	8.506	-45.731
	***	***	***	***	***		***	***	***	***	***
TC_large	118.860	15.872	63.172	3.339	7.468	1.151	61.588	-0.977	89.957	0.316	48.165
	***	**	***	***	***		***	***	***		***
TC_v_large	123.198	46.861	130.526	0.574	20.054	13.167	-82.338	2.649	153.994	-1.653	54.380
	***	***	***		***	***	***	***	***		***
_cons	10.875	10.056	7.783	6.921	7.876	10.237	9.302	5.230	8.572	7.329	10.604
	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***

Table 53 - Impact of technical change on cereals output. (Source: Own calculation)

Cereals	Austria	Belgium	Czechia	Finland	France	West Germany	East Germany	Ireland	Italy	Romania	Spain	Sweden	United Kingdom
TC	-12.134	0.168	-2.699	11.621	-11.498	-0.710	-1.830	-3.425	-5.774	2.025	-10.951	-9.132	-6.510
	***		***	***	***	***	***	**	***	***	***	***	***
TC_ES	0.076	0.004	0.001	-0.039	0.030	-0.001	0.000	0.021	-0.001	0.008	0.003	-0.009	-0.002
	***			***	***		**			***		**	
_cons	8.699	9.313	11.368	9.630	10.466	9.745	11.621	9.457	8.639	7.715	9.828	9.410	10.023
	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***

Tables 53 and 54 provide the estimate on the impact of technical change on cereal and milk output, respectively. The estimates indicate a significant relationship in the majority of countries in both productions. However, the expected positive effect can be observed only in Belgian, Finish and Romanian cereal production and Austrian, Czech and West Germany milk production. Moreover, the size effect is pronounced in Finish, French and Romanian cereal production and in the majority of countries in milk production. But, we cannot observe the increasing positive association between technical change and agricultural output with increasing size of the farmer in most of cases.

Table 54 - Impact of technical change on milk output. (Source: Own calculation)

Milk	Austria	Belgium	Czechia	Finland	France	West Germany	East Germany	Ireland	Italy	Romania	Spain	Sweden	United Kingdom
TC	1.819	-5.158	1.701	0.942	-11.705	7.703	-0.288	0.882	-0.606	-2.386	-4.021	-2.184	0.538
	**	***	***		***	***	***			***	***	**	
TC_ES	-0.192	-0.006	-0.003	-0.065	-0.008	-0.050	0.000	-0.066	-0.049	0.026	-0.002	-0.019	-0.003
	***		***	***	***	***		***	***	***		***	**
_cons	10.263	11.350	12.219	11.375	11.511	11.279	12.959	11.256	10.733	8.201	11.547	11.564	12.078
	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***	***

Table 55 - Biased technical change. (Source: Own calculation)

Food processing industry													
Coeff.	Austria	Belgium	Czechia	Finland	France	Germany	Ireland	Italy	Romania	Spain	Sweden	United Kingdom	
δ_{yt}	-0.005	0.000	-0.001	0.004	0.001	-0.002	LNO	0.002	-0.005	0.001	0.004	0.004	
				*	*			***	***		***	***	
δ_{Wt}	0.010	-0.007	0.001	0.013	-0.003	0.005	LNO	0.004	-0.007	-0.001	0.002	0.005	
				*	**	**		**	*				
δ_{Mt}	0.006	0.003	0.001	-0.012	0.000	-0.001	LNO	-0.001	0.017	0.002	-0.001	-0.001	
				*					***				
Cereals production													
Coeff.	Austria	Belgium	Czechia	Finland	France	West Germany	East Germany	Ireland	Italy	Romania	Spain	Sweden	United Kingdom
δ_{yCt}	-0.004	0.008	-0.008	0.001	-0.003	-0.009	0.002	0.004	-0.006	0.009	0.000	0.009	-0.004
						**				*		**	
δ_{yAOct}	0.004	-0.005	-0.002	-0.002	0.000	-0.001	0.011	0.001	0.001	-0.002	-0.007	-0.003	0.004
		***									***		
δ_{yAOOt}	0.006	0.005	0.003	-0.002	0.004	0.007	0.011	0.010	0.008	0.001	0.007	0.004	0.006
		**		**	**	***		***	**		***		
δ_{Lt}	0.007	-0.002	0.017	-0.012	-0.004	-0.002	0.011	0.013	-0.003	0.008	-0.003	0.007	0.010
δ_{Wt}	-0.007	0.011	0.014	0.010	0.006	0.000	-0.005	0.025	0.030	0.022	-0.001	-0.005	-0.003
			*						***	***			
δ_{Kt}	-0.003	0.007	-0.006	0.121	0.003	0.004	-0.015	0.004	-0.005	0.001	0.010	-0.009	0.002
				*			***					**	
Milk production													
Coeff.	Austria	Belgium	Czechia	Finland	France	West Germany	East Germany	Ireland	Italy	Romania	Spain	Sweden	United Kingdom
δ_{yCt}	-0.002	0.002	-0.003	0.013	0.002	-0.005	0.002	0.004	0.001	0.004	-0.008	0.010	-0.008
				***	**	**					**	***	**
δ_{yAOct}	0.002	-0.002	-0.002	-0.002	0.003	-0.002	-0.001	0.007	-0.005	0.007	0.000	0.003	-0.003
					***			**	**				
δ_{yAOOt}	0.001	0.002	0.006	-0.003	-0.001	-0.001	0.001	-0.005	0.009	-0.015	-0.002	-0.010	0.010
			**		*			**	***	*		**	***
δ_{Lt}	-0.013	0.002	-0.019	0.009	-0.003	0.002	0.002	-0.005	-0.013	0.008	-0.008	0.008	-0.016
	***		**	*					***		**		**
δ_{Wt}	0.001	-0.004	0.002	-0.006	0.002	-0.005	0.004	0.011	0.019	0.002	-0.024	-0.002	-0.001
								**	***		***		
δ_{Kt}	0.011	-0.009	-0.001	-0.008	0.004	0.005	-0.009	0.005	-0.007	0.001	-0.009	-0.010	0.005
	***	*		*	**		*		***		***	**	

Table 55 provides summary of fitted parameters from country IDF models related to the biased technological change. That is, these parameters inform us directly on the effect of technological change on input quantities or input cost shares, respectively. As far as the food processing industry is concerned the labour saving technological change was estimated in France and Romania and labour using in Finland and Germany. Then, material saving technical change can be observed in Finland and

material using technical change experienced Romanian food processing industry. The other countries are rather characterized by Hicks-neutral technical change.

Analogically to food processing industry, the biased technical change is not highly pronounced in cereal and milk production as well. In particular, as far as cereal production is concerned, the Czech Republic, Italy and Romania indicate labour saving technical change, Finland capital saving and East Germany and Sweden capital using technical change. Milk production is characterized by land using technical change in Austria, the Czech Republic, Italy, Spain and the United Kingdom, land saving in Finland, labour saving in Ireland and Italy, labour using in Spain and, finally, material saving in Austria and France and material using technical change in Belgium, Finland, East Germany, Italy, Spain and Sweden.

The overall impact of technical change on material inputs demonstrates the Figures E1 – G1 in Annex III. The technical change dynamics show that the stable technical progress is the common pattern of food processing industry in the majority of analyzed countries except for Romania. That is, the technological change contributed to the decrease of input quantity for a given level of output. In other words, the given level of output is produced with lower inputs. The opposite can be observed in cereal (Figure F1) and milk (Figure G1) production.

Then, Figure F1, G1, and Figure H1 in Annex III provide information on output price developments on aggregate level. These dynamics do not provide any expected patterns about the relationship between technical change and output price. In particular, since the aggregate price index dynamics is determined by the set of factors, we cannot separate the impact of fitted technical change.

5.2 TECHNICAL CHANGE, CONSUMER AND PRODUCER SURPLUS AND WELFARE EFFECTS

Technical progress has numerous implications. Generally, it increases outputs (i.e. in agriculture, it increases the yield, or reduces yield losses), or reduces the cost of production. If we assume perfect competition, the technical change reduces the per-unit cost of production and hence shifts the supply function of the commodity down and to the right. This shift leads to an increase in the quantity exchanged (Q_0 to Q_1) and a fall in price from P_0 to P_1 (see Figure 23). As a result, consumers benefit from the price reduction. Additionally, producers may benefit from selling higher amounts of products.

Figure 23 - Effects of technological change on producer and consumer surplus. (Source: Alene et al., 2014).

Focus on Figure 23 in more details, the initial equilibrium is a point (P_0, Q_0) , where the demand for the commodity (D) is crossed by the initial supply curve (S_0). The technological change causes the shift of supply curve – from S_0 to S_1 and consequently, establishes the new equilibrium (P_1, Q_1) . The total benefit from this supply shift is equal to the area beneath the demand curve and between the two supply curves (area $abce$). This total benefit represents the sum of benefit to consumers (area P_0bcP_1) and the benefit to producers in the form of the changes in producer surplus (area P_1ce minus area P_0ba).

In our analysis we found the evidence on the positive technical progress in food processing industry and negative one in cereal and milk production. Thus, the effects may cancel as far as the total welfare effects are concerned. However, if we take the price development in the food chains into consideration, we shall distinguish between the stages of the food chain. The situation on the agricultural market might stay stable from a long-run perspective (i.e. if we do not consider short-run price fluctuation) as far as farm and processors rents are concerned. However, the technological progress with increasing prices on the processing stage, may suggest the increase in both processors rents as well as the rents of subsequent stage (supermarkets, consumer, etc.). Thus, the developments and estimated figures on technical change in the analyzed food chains suggest that the total welfare effects increased in analyzed period.

5.3 TECHNICAL CHANGE, INNOVATIONS AND MAIN ACTORS

The desk research was conducted to identify the main actors and main innovations, which drive development of different food sectors. In particular, we focused on the studies that dealt with the analysis of technical change and innovation in the food-value chain, then we identify the main actors based on the qualitative information and information we have in the dataset. The main innovations and actors in the food chain were identified and already presented in deliverable 5.1 (Barling and Gresham, 2019). Thus, we provide only the brief summary of key findings. Then, we complete the

information with the findings on the companies and farmers who drive the technical change in our analyzed samples.

Literature review

The productivity and profitability of actors in the agri-food chain is influenced by several factors, e.g. knowledge capital and knowledge transfer, price fluctuations, market risk, and natural conditions. Focus on agriculture, Fałkowski and Ciaian (2016), based on the recent literature, examined the producer organizations with a specific focus on the factors affecting farmers' market performance and welfare. As the key factors, human and social capital, networking, interpersonal relationships were considered. It was also concluded that the access to information and farming experience positively affect the emergence of producer organizations and that larger farms are more likely to join collective action. Bošková and Rättinger (2014) were focused on the effective knowledge transfer and innovation activities, that may push the producers in the vertical to improve their competitiveness while saving resources, in the Czech dairy agri-food supply chain. The research was conducted on the innovation activities and knowledge transfer in order to assess the potential for enhancing sustainable dairy production. The results show the increasing dynamics in the innovation process, while the innovation activity of farmers and processors was considered as disconnected and their collaboration with research institutions and other companies as rather low. Cooke (2001) focused on the role of local institutions in the creation of an innovative environment where the productivity drives from knowledge sharing.

Vigani et al. (2015) based on 700 wheat farmers in France and Hungary examined the main determinants of the wheat production. According to French farmers' opinion, the most important wheat yield determinants at national level are seasonal weather and soil quality; while Hungarians pointed climate change and seasonal weather. Both farmers perceive market risks as more detrimental than natural disasters. While crop insurance is the most adopted tool to deal with the natural risks in both countries, French farmers adopt diversification strategies more frequently than Hungarians to deal with market risks.

The weather conditions were considered as one of the main determinants of the grain prices by Kantike and Eglite (2013), who were focused on the most significant factors affecting the bread price fluctuation in Latvia. Among other factors, currency exchange rate fluctuations, speculations on markets of agricultural goods, and political decisions were mentioned. Then, the energy prices have been increasing which also affects the growth in the food prices, including bread. Finally, the manual work used in the process of bread production can be considered also as a significant driver of the level of bread price.

At the manufacture level, Lööf and Hashmati (2002) found out that knowledge capital is a significant factor contributing to performance heterogeneity among firms. Moreover, Lööf (2004) found out that innovation is to be a major contributor to productivity growth. The study confirmed a positive relationship between R&D, innovation, and productivity. According to Archibugi et al. (1991), food processors can be especially interested in the open innovation, because they are more dependent on economic resources outside the industry than the other branches. In line with

Chesbrough (2006) who mentioned that especially small and medium (SMEs) companies use resources outside the firm in order to encourage innovation activities, Tóth and Fortó (2017) found that open innovation is a natural practice of the agri-food SMEs. According to this study, innovations occur in the intense consultation with buyers, suppliers, and other business partners. Furthermore, Bröring and Cloutier (2008) confirmed that knowledge sourcing in food industry arises especially from related suppliers (e.g. ingredients, machinery, and packaging). Török et al. (2019) concluded that the innovation performance of food companies is determined by many factors such as economic resources outside the industry, knowledge capital, R&D, knowledge sharing, cooperation and networking with universities and other research institutions, absorptive capacity, and firms' cooperation with suppliers and customers.

Although, technological innovation has been seen as a driver of competition and productivity, since Schumpeter's study (1934), Meynard et al. (2017) highlights the need of marketing and organizational innovations in agri-food chain while taking into account synergies or antagonisms between upstream and downstream. Salavou and Avlonitis (2008) added that the most of innovation in the food industry are incremental and characterized by a low degree of novelty. Additionally, Török et al. (2019) concluded that the European food industry is seen less innovative compared to other branches of the economy.

The main innovations and key actors in analyzed food chains were presented in deliverable 5.1 of this project (Barling and Gresham, 2019). Our results complement their findings by the detail analysis of technical change estimate, its distribution, developments and relation to the size of the farm/firm. The brief summary of Barling and Gresham findings with relation to our results is as follow.

(1) Wheat-to-bread chain:

- main actors: wheat producers, storage organisations, millers, bakeries, and retailers;
- key actors: large millers;
- a very concentrated milling industry;
- a growing international competition in the context of CAP changes and crop protection regulations;
- a loss of competitiveness;
- a significant restructuring of farms under relatively difficult investment conditions;
- three main strategies: risk management strategy, production costs minimization strategy and value-added creation/capture strategy (especially through production contracts).

(2) Milk chain:

- main actors: farms, producers, producers' organizations, processors, and retailers;
- key actors: dairy processors and retailers;
- very concentrated dairy processors and retailers;
- a significant restructuring away from regulated price controls and quotas on production towards a more competitive market system;

- a structural change in market conditions, leading to increased price volatility for producers;
- high levels of subsidy dependence, mainly in the form of direct payments;
- two main strategies: the optimisation of the physical productivity of production systems (therefore focusing on volumes produced) and the maximisation of economic productivity by lowering the expenses (through developing autonomous practices; intend to avoid important investment);
- two main forms of ecologisation of practices leading to potential increase of segmentation: the low carbon-emission program and the promotion of grazing production systems.

(3) Salmon value chain:

- a producer driven global value chain;
- key actors: large vertically integrated aquaculture companies;
- structural changes - from an owner-operated industry of several hundred small single farm firms to a more integrated industry of fewer but larger firms - help companies take advantage of economies of scale and strengthen their position on global markets;
- key uncertainties: biomass development (production growth) and future prices;
- key investments: in technological and production competencies according to technical standards as part of the regulatory framework and industry initiatives.

(4) Tomato chain:

- main agents: growers, producer organisations, cooperatives, processing companies, and retailers;
- a cooperative culture (membership of local and/or interregional producer organisations);
- main characteristics: geographical proximity, long and consolidated relations between agricultural production and local industry, and a distinctive governance system influencing the economic performance at the local level;
- key investments: in processing plants and in line with increasing sustainability standards.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In the conclusion we will especially concentrate on the research questions raised in the introduction.

The stochastic frontier analysis of food processing industries, cereal and milk producers revealed significant differences in technology among the countries. Moreover, there is an indication of economies of scale for majority of the countries in cereal as well as milk production. The food processing industry is characterized by constant returns to scale, that is, the food processors are scale efficient and no indication of economies of scale were revealed by the estimate.

The overall efficiency is high in agriculture as well as in food processing. However, significant differences among the countries in the efficiency of inputs use were revealed. The overall technical efficiency estimates are between 77% and 95% in agriculture, 73 and 95% in food processing industry and about 84% in salmon production. The decomposition of overall technical efficiency reveals that many farmers are long-termly falling behind the most efficient ones in the majority of analyzed countries. The developments in technical efficiency are rather stochastic. Thus, idiosyncratic developments in technical efficiency are observed in agriculture as well as in food-processing industry. The technical efficiency fluctuations may result from shocks associated with the introduction of new technologies, changes in human capital as well as shocks connected with weather conditions and climatic changes.

The total factor productivity (TFP) estimates show significant differences among countries. However, the predominantly negative total factor productivity change is observed in the analyzed period in agriculture as well as food processing industry. The manufacture of bakery products, where the productivity is followed the positive development path in the majority of analyzed countries, is the exception. The scale effect represents the main source of the total factor productivity change in the majority of analyzed sectors and countries. Changes improving scale efficiency and bringing technological progress are required to change this negative TFP development and consequently to generate further economic growth and to increase consumers' welfare.

The meta-frontier analysis did not reveal any significant differences in overall technical efficiency among the countries. This holds for food processing as well as for agricultural level. That is, the most efficient farmers and food processors in the analyzed countries have similar level of technical efficiency. However, as far as TFP comparison among the countries is concerned, the analysis shows that TFP differences among the countries exist on both agricultural as well as food processing level. The scale efficiency component is the main source of these differences.

The technical change has positive impact on output quantities. Moreover, it reduces the average costs in food processing industry. The opposite is true for agriculture where the technological regress was estimated. However, the price developments and estimated figures on technical change in the analyzed food chains suggest that the total welfare effects increased in analyzed period. Finally, large companies were identified as the main actors of food chains development.

Since the adoption of innovation is an important factor determining TFP growth, the policy makers should focus their attention to support the spread of innovations and know-how in the way to support the productivity growth in less productive regions and thus to decrease the differences among the regions in terms of productivity. Moreover, the analysis finds the evidence for the orientation to support small and middle farmers/firms.

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ANNEX I

FOOD PROCESSING INDUSTRY: COUNTRY INPUT DISTANCE FUNCTION ESTIMATES

Table A1 – Food processing industry: Austria. (Source: Own calculation)

Austria	GTRE			GTRE with Mundlak			GMM		
	Coef.	Std.	P> z	Coef.	Std.	P> z	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_xC									
ln_y	-0.9063	0.0218	0.0000	-0.8826	0.0271	0.0000	-0.9509	0.0214	0.0000
ln_y_d101	-0.0261	0.0251	0.2990	-0.0446	0.0270	0.0980			
ln_y_d105	-0.1071	0.0363	0.0030	-0.1169	0.0351	0.0010			
ln_y_d106	-0.1235	0.0381	0.0010	-0.1638	0.0487	0.0010			
ln_y_d107	0.0007	0.0646	0.9910	0.0122	0.0591	0.8370			
ln_xL	0.3608	0.0264	0.0000	0.3834	0.0348	0.0000	0.2752	0.0221	0.0000
ln_xL_d101	-0.1243	0.0469	0.0080	-0.1526	0.0479	0.0010			
ln_xL_d105	-0.0660	0.0519	0.2040	-0.0926	0.0509	0.0690			
ln_xL_d106	0.0059	0.0819	0.9420	-0.0441	0.0900	0.6240			
ln_xL_d107	-0.0654	0.0503	0.1930	-0.0434	0.0481	0.3670			
ln_xM	0.5926	0.0247	0.0000	0.5746	0.0356	0.0000	0.6131	0.0222	0.0000
ln_xM_d101	0.1181	0.0398	0.0030	0.1421	0.0415	0.0010			
ln_xM_d105	0.0622	0.0586	0.2890	0.0869	0.0595	0.1440			
ln_xM_d106	-0.0377	0.0526	0.4740	0.0013	0.0565	0.9820			
ln_xM_d107	0.0781	0.0517	0.1310	0.0598	0.0467	0.2000			
t	-0.0085	0.0014	0.0000	-0.0089	0.0014	0.0000	-0.0083	0.0038	0.0300
t_d101	0.0085	0.0029	0.0040	0.0089	0.0030	0.0030			
t_d105	0.0025	0.0029	0.3850	0.0031	0.0028	0.2740			
t_d106	-0.0045	0.0070	0.5270	-0.0016	0.0071	0.8260			
t_d107	0.0009	0.0035	0.8010	0.0004	0.0033	0.9130			
ln_y_2	0.0601	0.0209	0.0040	-0.0006	0.0006	0.2790	0.0605	0.0350	0.0870
ln_xL_2	0.1284	0.0206	0.0000	0.0011	0.0009	0.2030	0.1997	0.0424	0.0000
ln_xM_2	0.1243	0.0084	0.0000	-0.0002	0.0022	0.9300	0.1748	0.0171	0.0000
ln_xLxM	-0.1210	0.0139	0.0000	-0.0004	0.0020	0.8540	-0.1547	0.0270	0.0000
t_2	-0.0005	0.0005	0.3000	0.0530	0.0189	0.0050	-0.0020	0.0015	0.1850
ln_yt	0.0011	0.0009	0.2500	0.1214	0.0199	0.0000	-0.0048	0.0049	0.3350
ln_xLt	-0.0010	0.0024	0.6580	0.1194	0.0093	0.0000	0.0095	0.0062	0.1300
ln_xMt	-0.0002	0.0020	0.9360	-0.1130	0.0131	0.0000	0.0057	0.0052	0.2700
ln_yxL	-0.0271	0.0144	0.0600	-0.0293	0.0122	0.0170	0.0087	0.0218	0.6900
ln_yxM	0.0088	0.0133	0.5060	0.0130	0.0114	0.2560	-0.0718	0.0215	0.0010
_cons	-0.0638	0.0208	0.0020	-0.0633	0.0188	0.0010	-0.0977	0.0237	0.0000
ln_y_gmean				-0.0401	0.0308	0.1930			
ln_xL_gmean				-0.0768	0.0392	0.0500			
ln_xM_gmean				0.0243	0.0368	0.5080			
t_gmean				-0.0196	0.0100	0.0510			
			p-value			p-value			p-value
R2	0.9844			0.9858					
Wald/F-test	48631.0	$\chi^2[30]$	0.000	7010000	$\chi^2[34]$	0.000	440.2	F[14,91],	0.000
AR(2)							-0.98		0.325
Hansen test							89.82	$\chi^2[308]$	1.000
N. instruments							323		
N. groups							92		

Table A2 – Food processing industry: Belgium. (Source: Own calculation)

Belgium	GTRE			GTRE with Mundlak			GMM		
	Coef.	Std.	P> z	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> z	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_xC									
ln_y	-0.9876	0.0337	0.0000	-0.9495	0.0531	0.0000	-0.9821	0.0179	0.0000
ln_y_d101	0.0372	0.0485	0.4440	0.0372	0.0477	0.4360	-0.0939	0.0600	0.1180
ln_y_d105	0.0155	0.0588	0.7920	0.0258	0.0554	0.6420	-0.0283	0.0370	0.4440
ln_y_d106	0.0588	0.0663	0.3750	0.0542	0.0663	0.4140	0.0420	0.0604	0.4870
ln_y_d107	-0.0160	0.0537	0.7650	-0.0324	0.0548	0.5540	-0.0385	0.0390	0.3240
ln_xL	0.3611	0.0341	0.0000	0.3821	0.0419	0.0000	0.3188	0.0301	0.0000
ln_xL_d101	0.0451	0.0500	0.3670	0.0451	0.0502	0.3690	-0.0195	0.0562	0.7290
ln_xL_d105	0.0911	0.0662	0.1690	0.0946	0.0665	0.1550	0.1100	0.0851	0.1970
ln_xL_d106	0.0806	0.0913	0.3770	0.0651	0.0896	0.4680	0.0994	0.0852	0.2440
ln_xL_d107	-0.1590	0.0669	0.0170	-0.1639	0.0679	0.0160	-0.0594	0.0572	0.3000
ln_xM	0.5753	0.0255	0.0000	0.5495	0.0331	0.0000	0.6137	0.0234	0.0000
ln_xM_d101	-0.0877	0.0389	0.0240	-0.0840	0.0395	0.0340	-0.0863	0.0484	0.0750
ln_xM_d105	-0.0013	0.0422	0.9750	-0.0037	0.0423	0.9310	-0.0105	0.0413	0.8000
ln_xM_d106	0.0032	0.0639	0.9600	0.0184	0.0634	0.7720	-0.0451	0.0693	0.5150
ln_xM_d107	0.1704	0.0901	0.0590	0.1765	0.0888	0.0470	0.1350	0.0650	0.0390
t	-0.0014	0.0036	0.7050	-0.0019	0.0040	0.6280	-0.0076	0.0027	0.0050
t_d101	-0.0025	0.0038	0.5180	-0.0016	0.0041	0.6950	0.0087	0.0056	0.1190
t_d105	0.0043	0.0039	0.2700	0.0047	0.0041	0.2470	0.0065	0.0064	0.3100
t_d106	-0.0046	0.0057	0.4260	-0.0040	0.0060	0.5030	-0.0006	0.0059	0.9140
t_d107	-0.0046	0.0046	0.3120	-0.0043	0.0043	0.3140	0.0068	0.0057	0.2380
ln_y_2	-0.0455	0.0413	0.2710	-0.0005	0.0005	0.3120	0.0031	0.0310	0.9210
ln_xL_2	0.1056	0.0137	0.0000	-0.0039	0.0025	0.1180	0.0995	0.0192	0.0000
ln_xM_2	0.0843	0.0106	0.0000	-0.0045	0.0029	0.1180	0.0928	0.0119	0.0000
ln_xLxM	-0.0890	0.0116	0.0000	0.0024	0.0020	0.2390	-0.0916	0.0144	0.0000
t_2	-0.0004	0.0005	0.4320	-0.0394	0.0392	0.3150	0.0002	0.0010	0.8590
ln_yt	-0.0038	0.0025	0.1300	0.1077	0.0135	0.0000	0.0002	0.0032	0.9400
ln_xLt	-0.0048	0.0028	0.0820	0.0828	0.0108	0.0000	-0.0068	0.0045	0.1320
ln_xMt	0.0024	0.0019	0.2100	-0.0888	0.0115	0.0000	0.0034	0.0034	0.3260
ln_yxL	0.0103	0.0292	0.7230	0.0148	0.0282	0.6000	0.0334	0.0329	0.3100
ln_yxM	-0.0111	0.0234	0.6350	-0.0139	0.0229	0.5440	-0.0145	0.0262	0.5800
_cons	-0.0535	0.0336	0.1110	-0.0594	0.0317	0.0610	-0.1317	0.0271	0.0000
ln_y_gmean				-0.0603	0.0358	0.0920			
ln_xL_gmean				-0.0484	0.0306	0.1140			
ln_xM_gmean				0.0473	0.0270	0.0800			
t_gmean				-0.0064	0.0089	0.4740			
			p-value			p-value			p-value
R2	0.9789			0.9790					
Wald/F-test	55559.7	$\chi^2[30]$	0.000	59758.1	$\chi^2[34]$	0.000	1458.66	F[30,491]	0.000
AR(2)							1.00		0.317
Hansen test							295.93	$\chi^2[336]$	0.944
N. instruments							367		
N. groups							492		

Table A3 – Food processing industry: Czechia. (Source: Own calculation)

Czechia	GTRE			GTRE with Mundlak			GMM		
	Coef.	Std.	P> z	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> z	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_y	-0.8876	0.0175	0.0000	-0.7769	0.0282	0.0000	-0.9556	0.0100	0.0000
ln_y_d101	-0.0165	0.0270	0.5410	-0.0334	0.0247	0.1770	-0.0048	0.0190	0.8030
ln_y_d105	0.0053	0.0451	0.9060	0.0161	0.0415	0.6980	0.0103	0.0196	0.6010
ln_y_d106	-0.0332	0.0822	0.6860	-0.0535	0.0783	0.4940	0.0023	0.0381	0.9520
ln_y_d107	-0.0365	0.0203	0.0720	-0.0460	0.0201	0.0220	-0.0234	0.0198	0.2400
ln_xL	0.3477	0.0162	0.0000	0.3640	0.0196	0.0000	0.3033	0.0244	0.0000
ln_xL_d101	-0.0237	0.0318	0.4560	-0.0298	0.0319	0.3510	-0.0331	0.0471	0.4830
ln_xL_d105	-0.0078	0.0469	0.8690	-0.0206	0.0466	0.6580	0.0205	0.0551	0.7100
ln_xL_d106	0.0568	0.0905	0.5300	0.0699	0.0936	0.4550	0.0263	0.0669	0.6940
ln_xL_d107	-0.0920	0.0294	0.0020	-0.0955	0.0308	0.0020	-0.1657	0.0546	0.0020
ln_xM	0.5806	0.0154	0.0000	0.5459	0.0185	0.0000	0.6271	0.0222	0.0000
ln_xM_d101	-0.0018	0.0313	0.9530	0.0034	0.0326	0.9160	-0.0289	0.0533	0.5880
ln_xM_d105	-0.0186	0.0739	0.8010	-0.0177	0.0700	0.8000	0.0492	0.0481	0.3070
ln_xM_d106	-0.0479	0.0712	0.5010	-0.0505	0.0751	0.5010	-0.0325	0.0436	0.4570
ln_xM_d107	0.0689	0.0345	0.0460	0.0713	0.0341	0.0360	0.1466	0.0514	0.0040
t	-0.0046	0.0017	0.0060	-0.0063	0.0017	0.0000	-0.0112	0.0022	0.0000
t_d101	0.0009	0.0024	0.6990	0.0033	0.0024	0.1820	0.0033	0.0043	0.4380
t_d105	0.0008	0.0043	0.8520	0.0004	0.0043	0.9220	0.0058	0.0055	0.2910
t_d106	0.0038	0.0054	0.4870	0.0052	0.0052	0.3170	0.0125	0.0060	0.0360
t_d107	-0.0024	0.0034	0.4710	-0.0013	0.0032	0.6740	0.0015	0.0052	0.7770
ln_y_2	-0.0380	0.0099	0.0000	-0.0013	0.0005	0.0080	-0.0184	0.0072	0.0110
ln_xL_2	0.1519	0.0121	0.0000	-0.0029	0.0008	0.0000	0.1770	0.0262	0.0000
ln_xM_2	0.1606	0.0112	0.0000	-0.0013	0.0020	0.5350	0.1679	0.0233	0.0000
ln_xLxM	-0.1396	0.0092	0.0000	-0.0001	0.0022	0.9730	-0.1494	0.0192	0.0000
t_2	-0.0011	0.0005	0.0350	-0.0281	0.0091	0.0020	-0.0012	0.0009	0.1650
ln_yt	-0.0034	0.0008	0.0000	0.1532	0.0118	0.0000	-0.0008	0.0013	0.5550
ln_xLt	-0.0029	0.0020	0.1360	0.1599	0.0107	0.0000	0.0009	0.0041	0.8200
ln_xMt	0.0005	0.0024	0.8340	-0.1362	0.0092	0.0000	0.0011	0.0043	0.7970
ln_yxL	0.0118	0.0064	0.0630	0.0133	0.0064	0.0360	0.0080	0.0113	0.4800
ln_yxM	-0.0196	0.0074	0.0080	-0.0198	0.0071	0.0050	-0.0114	0.0119	0.3370
_cons	0.0251	0.0168	0.1350	-0.0271	0.0172	0.1140	-0.0633	0.0249	0.0110
ln_y_gmean				-0.1637	0.0224	0.0000			
ln_xL_gmean				-0.0431	0.0202	0.0330			
ln_xM_gmean				0.0619	0.0201	0.0020			
t_gmean				-0.0005	0.0069	0.9370			
			p-value			p-value			p-value
R2	0.9825			0.9842					
Wald/F-test	70999.1	$\chi^2[30]$	0.000	145410.7	$\chi^2[34]$	0.000	5968.5	F[30,1244]	0.000
AR(2)							-1.30		0.192
Hansen test							563.71	$\chi^2[554]$	0.378
N. instruments							585		
N. groups							1245		

Table A4 – Food processing industry: Finland. (Source: Own calculation)

Finland	GTRE			GTRE with Mundlak			GMM		
	Coef.	Std.	P> z	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> z	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_y	-0.9331	0.0158	0.0000	-0.8528	0.0273	0.0000	-1.0245	0.0163	0.0000
ln_y_d101	-0.0306	0.0233	0.1890	-0.0264	0.0230	0.2520	0.0991	0.0459	0.0310
ln_y_d105	-0.0233	0.0238	0.3280	-0.0162	0.0275	0.5560	0.0356	0.0519	0.4920
ln_y_d106	-0.0102	0.0310	0.7430	0.0074	0.0314	0.8140	0.0027	0.0625	0.9660
ln_y_d107	-0.0513	0.0278	0.0650	-0.0505	0.0283	0.0750	0.0913	0.0411	0.0270
ln_xL	0.3834	0.0204	0.0000	0.3736	0.0233	0.0000	0.3572	0.0339	0.0000
ln_xL_d101	0.0004	0.0432	0.9930	-0.0051	0.0450	0.9090	0.0769	0.0660	0.2450
ln_xL_d105	-0.0177	0.0310	0.5670	-0.0286	0.0345	0.4070	0.0654	0.0692	0.3450
ln_xL_d106	-0.0406	0.0304	0.1810	-0.0491	0.0299	0.1000	0.0595	0.0820	0.4690
ln_xL_d107	-0.0594	0.0291	0.0410	-0.0686	0.0292	0.0190	0.0130	0.0612	0.8320
ln_xM	0.5193	0.0177	0.0000	0.5110	0.0221	0.0000	0.5732	0.0248	0.0000
ln_xM_d101	0.0247	0.0538	0.6460	0.0340	0.0545	0.5330	-0.1798	0.0895	0.0450
ln_xM_d105	0.0300	0.0416	0.4710	0.0433	0.0482	0.3690	-0.0771	0.0727	0.2900
ln_xM_d106	0.0447	0.0451	0.3220	0.0565	0.0440	0.1980	-0.0672	0.0766	0.3810
ln_xM_d107	0.0843	0.0299	0.0050	0.0991	0.0310	0.0010	-0.0427	0.0491	0.3840
t	-0.0075	0.0020	0.0000	-0.0095	0.0021	0.0000	0.0057	0.0103	0.5790
t_d101	0.0029	0.0035	0.4110	0.0037	0.0035	0.2970	-0.0377	0.0263	0.1520
t_d105	0.0032	0.0040	0.4260	0.0072	0.0036	0.0450	0.0143	0.0252	0.5710
t_d106	0.0060	0.0056	0.2910	0.0082	0.0058	0.1570	0.0335	0.0432	0.4390
t_d107	0.0042	0.0033	0.2040	0.0059	0.0035	0.0930	-0.0370	0.0221	0.0950
ln_y_2	-0.0184	0.0052	0.0000	-0.0041	0.0005	0.0000	-0.0138	0.0089	0.1200
ln_xL_2	0.1276	0.0092	0.0000	-0.0004	0.0007	0.5190	0.1165	0.0260	0.0000
ln_xM_2	0.1226	0.0103	0.0000	-0.0013	0.0016	0.4260	0.0972	0.0130	0.0000
ln_xLxM	-0.1099	0.0072	0.0000	0.0009	0.0018	0.6170	-0.0899	0.0174	0.0000
t_2	-0.0041	0.0005	0.0000	-0.0051	0.0047	0.2710	-0.0059	0.0010	0.0000
ln_yt	0.0002	0.0006	0.7520	0.1262	0.0096	0.0000	0.0035	0.0019	0.0730
ln_xLt	-0.0015	0.0016	0.3470	0.1241	0.0102	0.0000	0.0128	0.0073	0.0800
ln_xMt	0.0009	0.0018	0.6260	-0.1076	0.0074	0.0000	-0.0123	0.0072	0.0870
ln_yxL	0.0314	0.0096	0.0010	0.0315	0.0095	0.0010	-0.0159	0.0137	0.2450
ln_yxM	-0.0292	0.0112	0.0090	-0.0298	0.0110	0.0070	0.0233	0.0127	0.0680
_cons	-0.0131	0.0206	0.5240	-0.0521	0.0164	0.0010	-0.0820	0.0237	0.0010
ln_y_gmean				-0.1192	0.0218	0.0000			
ln_xL_gmean				0.0403	0.0194	0.0380			
ln_xM_gmean				-0.0217	0.0201	0.2810			
t_gmean				0.0012	0.0069	0.8610			
			p-value			p-value			p-value
R2	0.9853			0.9866					
Wald/F-test	77132.9	$\chi^2[30]$	0.000	112914.0	$\chi^2[34]$	0.000	2666.3	F[30,741]	0.000
AR(2)							-0.41		0.681
Hansen test							257.55	$\chi^2[242]$	0.235
N. instruments							273		
N. groups							742		

Table A5 – Food processing industry: France. (Source: Own calculation)

France	GTRE			GTRE with Mundlak			GMM		
	Coef.	Std.	P> z	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> z	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_y	-0.9483	0.0073	0.0000	-0.8972	0.0098	0.0000	-0.9766	0.0106	0.0000
ln_y_d101	-0.0124	0.0058	0.0330	-0.0134	0.0057	0.0190	0.0175	0.0192	0.3620
ln_y_d105	-0.0015	0.0113	0.8940	-0.0009	0.0112	0.9350	-0.0063	0.0171	0.7140
ln_y_d106	0.0117	0.0118	0.3210	0.0093	0.0117	0.4260	0.0039	0.0257	0.8790
ln_y_d107	-0.0156	0.0090	0.0830	-0.0210	0.0089	0.0190	0.0048	0.0241	0.8420
ln_xL	0.3985	0.0070	0.0000	0.3903	0.0084	0.0000	0.3826	0.0155	0.0000
ln_xL_d101	0.0013	0.0102	0.8950	-0.0013	0.0104	0.8990	0.0711	0.0533	0.1830
ln_xL_d105	0.0039	0.0192	0.8410	-0.0011	0.0191	0.9530	-0.0037	0.0326	0.9090
ln_xL_d106	0.0047	0.0203	0.8160	-0.0042	0.0206	0.8370	0.0240	0.0326	0.4620
ln_xL_d107	-0.0832	0.0102	0.0000	-0.0850	0.0104	0.0000	-0.0306	0.0369	0.4060
ln_xM	0.4969	0.0082	0.0000	0.5032	0.0096	0.0000	0.5073	0.0169	0.0000
ln_xM_d101	0.0278	0.0108	0.0100	0.0341	0.0110	0.0020	-0.0647	0.0415	0.1180
ln_xM_d105	0.0007	0.0200	0.9730	0.0084	0.0201	0.6760	-0.0017	0.0288	0.9520
ln_xM_d106	-0.0027	0.0207	0.8980	-0.0008	0.0217	0.9710	-0.0193	0.0447	0.6660
ln_xM_d107	0.1316	0.0127	0.0000	0.1354	0.0128	0.0000	0.1844	0.0343	0.0000
t	-0.0106	0.0007	0.0000	-0.0112	0.0007	0.0000	-0.0124	0.0014	0.0000
t_d101	0.0036	0.0007	0.0000	0.0038	0.0007	0.0000	0.0075	0.0017	0.0000
t_d105	0.0018	0.0014	0.1960	0.0013	0.0013	0.3490	0.0051	0.0024	0.0370
t_d106	0.0033	0.0014	0.0190	0.0034	0.0014	0.0170	0.0048	0.0028	0.0830
t_d107	0.0034	0.0009	0.0000	0.0037	0.0009	0.0000	0.0037	0.0025	0.1380
ln_y_2	-0.0016	0.0029	0.5840	-0.0026	0.0001	0.0000	0.0053	0.0048	0.2660
ln_xL_2	0.1144	0.0039	0.0000	-0.0004	0.0002	0.0920	0.1042	0.0150	0.0000
ln_xM_2	0.1269	0.0056	0.0000	-0.0026	0.0005	0.0000	0.1325	0.0151	0.0000
ln_xLxM	-0.1067	0.0043	0.0000	0.0026	0.0006	0.0000	-0.0857	0.0188	0.0000
t_2	-0.0025	0.0001	0.0000	0.0070	0.0027	0.0090	-0.0029	0.0003	0.0000
ln_yt	-0.0003	0.0002	0.1310	0.1143	0.0040	0.0000	0.0012	0.0007	0.0910
ln_xLt	-0.0029	0.0005	0.0000	0.1290	0.0057	0.0000	-0.0029	0.0013	0.0280
ln_xMt	0.0027	0.0006	0.0000	-0.1066	0.0044	0.0000	0.0000	0.0014	0.9850
ln_yxL	0.0287	0.0026	0.0000	0.0289	0.0026	0.0000	0.0105	0.0085	0.2190
ln_yxM	-0.0299	0.0034	0.0000	-0.0303	0.0033	0.0000	0.0143	0.0103	0.1640
_cons	-0.0234	0.0057	0.0000	-0.0431	0.0058	0.0000	-0.0789	0.0090	0.0000
ln_y_gmean				-0.0714	0.0056	0.0000			
ln_xL_gmean				0.0161	0.0060	0.0070			
ln_xM_gmean				-0.0306	0.0070	0.0000			
t_gmean				-0.0007	0.0013	0.6000			
			p-value			p-value			p-value
R2	0.9862			0.9871					
Wald/F-test	1090000	$\chi^2[30]$	0.000	1480000	$\chi^2[34]$	0.000	340256.1	$\chi^2[30]$	0.000
AR(2)							-0.91		0.361
Hansen test							730.67	$\chi^2[707]$	0.261
N. instruments							738		
N. groups							3048		

Table A6 – Food processing industry: Germany. (Source: Own calculation)

Germany	GTRE			GTRE with Mundlak			GMM		
	Coef.	Std.	P> z	Coef.	Std.	P> z	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_y	-0.9608	0.0165	0.0000	-0.8949	0.0369	0.0000	-0.9979	0.0139	0.0000
ln_y_d101	-0.0269	0.0189	0.1540	-0.0185	0.0185	0.3180	0.0101	0.0338	0.7660
ln_y_d105	-0.0340	0.0210	0.1050	-0.0437	0.0234	0.0620	-0.0345	0.0252	0.1720
ln_y_d106	0.4030	0.1956	0.0390	0.3830	0.1757	0.0290	0.0387	0.0304	0.2040
ln_y_d107	-0.0118	0.0216	0.5860	-0.0014	0.0210	0.9490	0.0050	0.0302	0.8690
ln_xL	0.3418	0.0346	0.0000	0.3673	0.0450	0.0000	0.2581	0.0309	0.0000
ln_xL_d101	-0.1446	0.0504	0.0040	-0.1540	0.0543	0.0050	0.0064	0.0726	0.9300
ln_xL_d105	-0.0535	0.0327	0.1020	-0.0612	0.0345	0.0760	-0.0298	0.0548	0.5860
ln_xL_d106	0.0797	0.1160	0.4920	0.0768	0.1054	0.4660	0.0280	0.0583	0.6310
ln_xL_d107	-0.0218	0.0548	0.6900	-0.0276	0.0548	0.6150	0.0126	0.0385	0.7440
ln_xM	0.5867	0.0347	0.0000	0.5516	0.0476	0.0000	0.6350	0.0239	0.0000
ln_xM_d101	0.1181	0.0475	0.0130	0.1198	0.0488	0.0140	0.0458	0.0521	0.3800
ln_xM_d105	0.0472	0.0362	0.1920	0.0530	0.0374	0.1560	0.0597	0.0352	0.0900
ln_xM_d106	0.0090	0.0833	0.9140	0.0126	0.0768	0.8700	0.0817	0.0823	0.3210
ln_xM_d107	0.0624	0.0405	0.1230	0.0637	0.0384	0.0970	0.0326	0.0386	0.4000
t	-0.0055	0.0013	0.0000	-0.0060	0.0014	0.0000	-0.0050	0.0025	0.0500
t_d101	-0.0006	0.0017	0.7150	-0.0012	0.0019	0.5080	-0.0039	0.0039	0.3190
t_d105	0.0029	0.0019	0.1240	0.0026	0.0021	0.2060	0.0066	0.0043	0.1290
t_d106	-0.0024	0.0030	0.4140	-0.0019	0.0032	0.5510	-0.0002	0.0052	0.9750
t_d107	-0.0038	0.0031	0.2210	-0.0042	0.0033	0.1970	0.0022	0.0061	0.7220
ln_y_2	0.0127	0.0059	0.0300	-0.0024	0.0005	0.0000	0.0136	0.0077	0.0780
ln_xL_2	0.0556	0.0065	0.0000	-0.0006	0.0006	0.3570	0.0338	0.0081	0.0000
ln_xM_2	0.1109	0.0067	0.0000	0.0013	0.0010	0.2090	0.0830	0.0131	0.0000
ln_xLxM	-0.0680	0.0074	0.0000	-0.0016	0.0009	0.0900	-0.0494	0.0107	0.0000
t_2	-0.0022	0.0004	0.0000	0.0137	0.0058	0.0190	-0.0025	0.0009	0.0030
ln_yt	-0.0007	0.0006	0.2200	0.0593	0.0074	0.0000	-0.0022	0.0015	0.1270
ln_xLt	0.0013	0.0010	0.1780	0.1081	0.0077	0.0000	0.0045	0.0018	0.0150
ln_xMt	-0.0015	0.0009	0.0920	-0.0667	0.0077	0.0000	-0.0013	0.0021	0.5280
ln_yxL	-0.0059	0.0081	0.4670	-0.0040	0.0080	0.6150	-0.0077	0.0102	0.4460
ln_yxM	0.0066	0.0082	0.4220	0.0060	0.0081	0.4620	0.0225	0.0140	0.1090
_cons	-0.1432	0.0151	0.0000	-0.1497	0.0155	0.0000	-0.1341	0.0140	0.0000
ln_y_gmean				-0.0938	0.0343	0.0060			
ln_xL_gmean				-0.0375	0.0290	0.1950			
ln_xM_gmean				0.0533	0.0321	0.0970			
t_gmean				0.0019	0.0045	0.6710			
			p-value			p-value			p-value
R2	0.9885			0.9891					
Wald/F-test	124618.9	$\chi^2[30]$	0.000	141358.1	$\chi^2[34]$	0.000	2742.83	F[30,662]	0.000
AR(2)							-0.67		0.504
Hansen test							517.20	$\chi^2[505]$	0.344
N. instruments							536		
N. groups							663		

Table A7 – Food processing industry: Ireland. (Source: Own calculation)

Ireland	GTRE		
	Coef.	Std.	P> z
ln_xC			
ln_y	-0.9817	0.0223	0.0000
ln_xL	0.2766	0.0291	0.0000
ln_xM	0.7002	0.0213	0.0000
t	-0.0028	0.0021	0.1830
ln_y_2	0.0088	0.0093	0.3420
ln_xL_2	0.2008	0.0217	0.0000
ln_xM_2	0.1823	0.0190	0.0000
ln_xLxM	-0.1776	0.0177	0.0000
t_2	0.0017	0.0009	0.0510
ln_yt	0.0003	0.0034	0.9170
ln_xLt	-0.0018	0.0037	0.6270
ln_xMt	0.0017	0.0029	0.5490
ln_yxL	0.0362	0.0139	0.0090
ln_yxM	-0.0129	0.0115	0.2630
_cons	-0.1600	0.0255	0.0000
			p-value
R2	0.9947		
Wald	22776.3	$\chi^2[14]$	0.000
AR(2)			
Hansen test			
N. instruments			
N. groups			

Table A8 – Food processing industry: Italy. (Source: Own calculation)

Italy	GTRE			GTRE with Mundlak			GMM		
	Coef.	Std.	P> z	Coef.	Std.	P> z	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_y	-0.9172	0.0059	0.0000	-0.8439	0.0088	0.0000	-0.9619	0.0070	0.0000
ln_y_d101	-0.0061	0.0121	0.6120	-0.0153	0.0115	0.1840	-0.0503	0.0158	0.0010
ln_y_d105	-0.0129	0.0094	0.1710	-0.0143	0.0093	0.1230	-0.0257	0.0165	0.1200
ln_y_d106	0.0471	0.0242	0.0520	0.0425	0.0234	0.0690	0.0331	0.0239	0.1660
ln_y_d107	-0.0755	0.0088	0.0000	-0.0656	0.0085	0.0000	-0.0058	0.0211	0.7850
ln_xL	0.3187	0.0061	0.0000	0.3173	0.0069	0.0000	0.2873	0.0138	0.0000
ln_xL_d101	0.0074	0.0107	0.4910	0.0023	0.0107	0.8320	-0.1557	0.0376	0.0000
ln_xL_d105	-0.0158	0.0117	0.1780	-0.0174	0.0116	0.1340	0.0174	0.0357	0.6250
ln_xL_d106	-0.0025	0.0242	0.9190	-0.0032	0.0240	0.8940	0.0723	0.0454	0.1120
ln_xL_d107	-0.0943	0.0091	0.0000	-0.1054	0.0092	0.0000	0.0667	0.0373	0.0740
ln_xM	0.5929	0.0066	0.0000	0.5771	0.0077	0.0000	0.6039	0.0116	0.0000
ln_xM_d101	-0.0060	0.0128	0.6420	-0.0027	0.0127	0.8290	0.1464	0.0278	0.0000
ln_xM_d105	0.0200	0.0119	0.0930	0.0181	0.0121	0.1330	0.1240	0.0300	0.0000
ln_xM_d106	0.0212	0.0360	0.5550	0.0186	0.0349	0.5930	0.0162	0.0343	0.6370
ln_xM_d107	0.1086	0.0110	0.0000	0.1147	0.0111	0.0000	0.2024	0.0332	0.0000
t	-0.0109	0.0006	0.0000	-0.0126	0.0006	0.0000	-0.0087	0.0009	0.0000
t_d101	0.0003	0.0009	0.7480	0.0012	0.0009	0.1940	0.0045	0.0018	0.0110
t_d105	0.0033	0.0009	0.0000	0.0035	0.0009	0.0000	0.0033	0.0031	0.2860
t_d106	-0.0008	0.0016	0.6220	-0.0007	0.0016	0.6630	0.0004	0.0028	0.8800
t_d107	0.0047	0.0010	0.0000	0.0034	0.0010	0.0010	-0.0027	0.0034	0.4270
ln_y_2	-0.0254	0.0032	0.0000	-0.0011	0.0001	0.0000	0.0116	0.0035	0.0010
ln_xL_2	0.1314	0.0031	0.0000	0.0000	0.0003	0.9810	0.2221	0.0299	0.0000
ln_xM_2	0.1502	0.0041	0.0000	-0.0032	0.0005	0.0000	0.2073	0.0127	0.0000
ln_xLxM	-0.1228	0.0032	0.0000	0.0014	0.0005	0.0070	-0.1574	0.0185	0.0000
t_2	-0.0009	0.0001	0.0000	-0.0148	0.0031	0.0000	-0.0003	0.0004	0.5370
ln_yt	0.0002	0.0003	0.5300	0.1309	0.0032	0.0000	0.0023	0.0006	0.0000
ln_xLt	-0.0034	0.0005	0.0000	0.1505	0.0040	0.0000	0.0039	0.0016	0.0130
ln_xMt	0.0019	0.0005	0.0000	-0.1198	0.0032	0.0000	-0.0014	0.0011	0.2110
ln_yxL	0.0197	0.0025	0.0000	0.0213	0.0025	0.0000	0.0425	0.0097	0.0000
ln_yxM	-0.0244	0.0030	0.0000	-0.0263	0.0030	0.0000	-0.0390	0.0075	0.0000
_cons	-0.0690	0.0061	0.0000	-0.0951	0.0057	0.0000	-0.1605	0.0086	0.0000
ln_y_gmean				-0.1201	0.0072	0.0000			
ln_xL_gmean				0.0177	0.0063	0.0050			
ln_xM_gmean				0.0178	0.0068	0.0090			
t_gmean				0.0176	0.0023	0.0000			
			p-value			p-value			p-value
R2	0.9819			0.9831					
Wald/F-test	427117.5	$\chi^2[30]$	0.000	754565.5	$\chi^2[34]$	0.000	151287.0	$\chi^2[30]$	0.000
AR(2)							-1.16		0.247
Hansen test							712.45	$\chi^2[695]$	0.315
N. instruments							726		
N. groups							1698		

Table A9 – Food processing industry: Romania. (Source: Own calculation)

Romania	GTRE			GTRE with Mundlak			GMM		
	Coef.	Std.	P> z	Coef.	Std.	P> z	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_y	-0.7891	0.0076	0.0000	-0.6083	0.0095	0.0000	-0.9152	0.0127	0.0000
ln_y_d101	0.0034	0.0135	0.8020	-0.0131	0.0121	0.2800	-0.0524	0.0211	0.0130
ln_y_d105	-0.0020	0.0130	0.8780	0.0065	0.0109	0.5460	-0.0262	0.0214	0.2210
ln_y_d106	0.0007	0.0150	0.9610	0.0052	0.0115	0.6530	-0.0261	0.0197	0.1870
ln_y_d107	-0.0563	0.0092	0.0000	-0.0605	0.0079	0.0000	-0.0584	0.0182	0.0010
ln_xL	0.4778	0.0103	0.0000	0.4923	0.0107	0.0000	0.3817	0.0350	0.0000
ln_xL_d101	0.0115	0.0240	0.6320	-0.0154	0.0227	0.4990	-0.0238	0.0565	0.6730
ln_xL_d105	0.0686	0.0186	0.0000	0.0572	0.0174	0.0010	-0.0090	0.0582	0.8770
ln_xL_d106	0.0260	0.0201	0.1970	0.0183	0.0176	0.2970	0.0222	0.0589	0.7060
ln_xL_d107	-0.0050	0.0126	0.6910	-0.0354	0.0117	0.0020	-0.1610	0.0493	0.0010
ln_xM	0.3995	0.0106	0.0000	0.3059	0.0098	0.0000	0.5826	0.0347	0.0000
ln_xM_d101	-0.0231	0.0223	0.3000	-0.0066	0.0195	0.7350	-0.0354	0.0463	0.4450
ln_xM_d105	-0.0628	0.0188	0.0010	-0.0436	0.0151	0.0040	-0.0398	0.0571	0.4850
ln_xM_d106	-0.0533	0.0207	0.0100	-0.0424	0.0160	0.0080	-0.0319	0.0546	0.5590
ln_xM_d107	-0.0467	0.0132	0.0000	-0.0142	0.0111	0.2020	0.0891	0.0572	0.1190
t	-0.0220	0.0021	0.0000	-0.0229	0.0022	0.0000	-0.0351	0.0045	0.0000
t_d101	-0.0046	0.0033	0.1640	-0.0020	0.0034	0.5690	-0.0200	0.0075	0.0070
t_d105	-0.0034	0.0036	0.3440	0.0000	0.0037	0.9960	-0.0054	0.0067	0.4220
t_d106	0.0030	0.0036	0.4070	0.0045	0.0036	0.2120	-0.0010	0.0077	0.8980
t_d107	0.0057	0.0025	0.0230	0.0053	0.0026	0.0370	0.0032	0.0055	0.5570
ln_y_2	-0.0465	0.0029	0.0000	0.0058	0.0005	0.0000	-0.0239	0.0038	0.0000
ln_xL_2	0.1914	0.0100	0.0000	-0.0041	0.0005	0.0000	0.2712	0.0326	0.0000
ln_xM_2	0.1800	0.0086	0.0000	-0.0040	0.0011	0.0000	0.2403	0.0317	0.0000
ln_xLxM	-0.1628	0.0093	0.0000	0.0056	0.0011	0.0000	-0.2355	0.0331	0.0000
t_2	0.0084	0.0005	0.0000	-0.0245	0.0027	0.0000	0.0318	0.0020	0.0000
ln_yt	-0.0040	0.0005	0.0000	0.1809	0.0087	0.0000	-0.0049	0.0013	0.0000
ln_xLt	-0.0077	0.0012	0.0000	0.1583	0.0080	0.0000	-0.0073	0.0044	0.0940
ln_xMt	0.0121	0.0012	0.0000	-0.1364	0.0084	0.0000	0.0169	0.0045	0.0000
ln_yxL	0.0288	0.0046	0.0000	0.0261	0.0043	0.0000	-0.0018	0.0129	0.8920
ln_yxM	-0.0492	0.0043	0.0000	-0.0436	0.0039	0.0000	0.0105	0.0129	0.4170
_cons	-0.0320	0.0072	0.0000	-0.0940	0.0063	0.0000	-0.2434	0.0110	0.0000
ln_y_gmean				-0.3091	0.0086	0.0000			
ln_xL_gmean				-0.1955	0.0095	0.0000			
ln_xM_gmean				0.3312	0.0096	0.0000			
t_gmean				-0.0117	0.0035	0.0010			
			p-value			p-value			p-value
R2	0.9646			0.9742					
Wald/F-test	202429.2	$\chi^2[30]$	0.000	435406.0	$\chi^2[34]$	0.000	10005.2	F[30,4558]	0.000
AR(3)							-1.54		0.123
Hansen test							1361.21	$\chi^2[591]$	0.000
N. instruments							622		
N. groups							4559		

Table A10 – Food processing industry: Spain. (Source: Own calculation)

Spain	GTRE			GTRE with Mundlak			GMM		
	Coef.	Std.	P> z	Coef.	Std.	P> z	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_y	-0.8401	0.0055	0.0000	-0.6975	0.0089	0.0000	-0.9816	0.0066	0.0000
ln_y_d101	-0.0380	0.0081	0.0000	-0.0431	0.0077	0.0000	0.0116	0.0137	0.3960
ln_y_d105	-0.0659	0.0101	0.0000	-0.0598	0.0094	0.0000	-0.0525	0.0313	0.0930
ln_y_d106	-0.0243	0.0123	0.0490	-0.0172	0.0139	0.2150	0.0491	0.0226	0.0290
ln_y_d107	-0.1033	0.0089	0.0000	-0.0928	0.0079	0.0000	0.0294	0.0201	0.1430
ln_xL	0.3837	0.0050	0.0000	0.3985	0.0059	0.0000	0.3101	0.0161	0.0000
ln_xL_d101	-0.0148	0.0080	0.0660	-0.0065	0.0080	0.4160	-0.0649	0.0291	0.0260
ln_xL_d105	-0.0357	0.0169	0.0350	-0.0289	0.0160	0.0710	-0.1729	0.0790	0.0290
ln_xL_d106	-0.0353	0.0293	0.2290	-0.0251	0.0270	0.3530	0.0069	0.0435	0.8750
ln_xL_d107	-0.0554	0.0082	0.0000	-0.0676	0.0079	0.0000	-0.0124	0.0397	0.7540
ln_xM	0.5093	0.0046	0.0000	0.4499	0.0056	0.0000	0.6239	0.0105	0.0000
ln_xM_d101	0.0183	0.0085	0.0300	0.0073	0.0079	0.3570	0.0080	0.0273	0.7680
ln_xM_d105	0.0625	0.0161	0.0000	0.0618	0.0147	0.0000	0.1729	0.0588	0.0030
ln_xM_d106	0.0325	0.0153	0.0340	0.0270	0.0151	0.0750	-0.0351	0.0263	0.1820
ln_xM_d107	0.0732	0.0084	0.0000	0.0794	0.0079	0.0000	0.1033	0.0337	0.0020
t	-0.0061	0.0005	0.0000	-0.0058	0.0006	0.0000	-0.0107	0.0008	0.0000
t_d101	0.0015	0.0007	0.0260	0.0029	0.0008	0.0000	0.0046	0.0015	0.0020
t_d105	-0.0005	0.0013	0.6860	-0.0011	0.0013	0.4090	0.0084	0.0039	0.0300
t_d106	0.0003	0.0014	0.8260	0.0027	0.0015	0.0670	-0.0021	0.0023	0.3450
t_d107	0.0002	0.0008	0.7790	0.0010	0.0009	0.2650	0.0004	0.0031	0.9040
ln_y_2	-0.0579	0.0034	0.0000	-0.0014	0.0002	0.0000	0.0033	0.0037	0.3740
ln_xL_2	0.1272	0.0040	0.0000	-0.0003	0.0002	0.2820	0.1020	0.0310	0.0010
ln_xM_2	0.1472	0.0036	0.0000	0.0005	0.0004	0.2110	0.1677	0.0117	0.0000
ln_xLxM	-0.1142	0.0038	0.0000	-0.0019	0.0004	0.0000	-0.1169	0.0200	0.0000
t_2	-0.0006	0.0002	0.0000	-0.0364	0.0029	0.0000	-0.0006	0.0003	0.0680
ln_yt	0.0003	0.0002	0.2340	0.1293	0.0038	0.0000	0.0005	0.0005	0.3170
ln_xLt	-0.0008	0.0004	0.0660	0.1409	0.0035	0.0000	-0.0012	0.0016	0.4470
ln_xMt	-0.0010	0.0004	0.0200	-0.1068	0.0036	0.0000	0.0015	0.0011	0.1470
ln_yxL	-0.0065	0.0029	0.0260	0.0012	0.0027	0.6560	0.0006	0.0101	0.9530
ln_yxM	-0.0080	0.0031	0.0100	-0.0137	0.0029	0.0000	-0.0138	0.0090	0.1230
_cons	-0.0411	0.0049	0.0000	-0.0790	0.0043	0.0000	-0.0927	0.0083	0.0000
ln_y_gmean				-0.2178	0.0073	0.0000			
ln_xL_gmean				-0.0417	0.0050	0.0000			
ln_xM_gmean				0.1272	0.0057	0.0000			
t_gmean				0.0116	0.0020	0.0000			
			p-value			p-value			p-value
R2	0.9816			0.9845					
Wald/F-test	668679.6	$\chi^2[30]$	0.000	968031.9	$\chi^2[34]$	0.000	294500.9	$\chi^2[30]$	0.000
AR(3)							-1.01		0.313
Hansen test							716.75	$\chi^2[674]$	0.123
N. instruments							705		
N. groups							1937		

Table A11 – Food processing industry: Sweden. (Source: Own calculation)

Sweden	GTRE			GTRE with Mundlak			GMM		
	Coef.	Std.	P> z	Coef.	Std.	P> z	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_y	-0.9383	0.0170	0.0000	-0.8954	0.0237	0.0000	-1.0288	0.0105	0.0000
ln_y_d101	0.0259	0.0173	0.1340	0.0218	0.0165	0.1850	0.0129	0.0176	0.4630
ln_y_d105	-0.0006	0.0288	0.9830	-0.0028	0.0301	0.9260	0.0492	0.0404	0.2240
ln_y_d106	-0.0814	0.0325	0.0120	-0.0790	0.0333	0.0180	0.0144	0.0194	0.4580
ln_y_d107	-0.0974	0.0243	0.0000	-0.0984	0.0251	0.0000	0.0133	0.0162	0.4120
ln_xL	0.3624	0.0144	0.0000	0.3587	0.0173	0.0000	0.3582	0.0214	0.0000
ln_xL_d101	0.0513	0.0243	0.0350	0.0479	0.0244	0.0490	0.0540	0.0395	0.1720
ln_xL_d105	-0.0042	0.0293	0.8860	-0.0047	0.0292	0.8720	0.1026	0.0449	0.0230
ln_xL_d106	0.0439	0.0403	0.2750	0.0442	0.0417	0.2900	0.0311	0.0371	0.4020
ln_xL_d107	-0.0284	0.0191	0.1370	-0.0337	0.0190	0.0770	0.0253	0.0295	0.3920
ln_xM	0.5485	0.0146	0.0000	0.5461	0.0186	0.0000	0.5688	0.0220	0.0000
ln_xM_d101	-0.0356	0.0236	0.1310	-0.0332	0.0236	0.1590	-0.0090	0.0345	0.7930
ln_xM_d105	-0.0040	0.0338	0.9070	-0.0002	0.0340	0.9960	-0.0927	0.0415	0.0260
ln_xM_d106	-0.0758	0.0395	0.0550	-0.0760	0.0403	0.0590	0.0053	0.0432	0.9030
ln_xM_d107	0.0418	0.0204	0.0410	0.0478	0.0202	0.0180	-0.0026	0.0328	0.9360
t	-0.0066	0.0020	0.0010	-0.0079	0.0021	0.0000	-0.0117	0.0028	0.0000
t_d101	0.0001	0.0027	0.9600	0.0004	0.0026	0.8780	-0.0002	0.0035	0.9530
t_d105	0.0012	0.0061	0.8410	-0.0007	0.0063	0.9130	-0.0074	0.0080	0.3530
t_d106	0.0087	0.0055	0.1150	0.0102	0.0057	0.0720	-0.0021	0.0054	0.6990
t_d107	0.0055	0.0030	0.0610	0.0064	0.0030	0.0320	0.0086	0.0043	0.0450
ln_y_2	-0.0350	0.0086	0.0000	-0.0044	0.0005	0.0000	0.0102	0.0065	0.1180
ln_xL_2	0.1221	0.0080	0.0000	0.0003	0.0007	0.7070	0.1050	0.0104	0.0000
ln_xM_2	0.1418	0.0071	0.0000	-0.0012	0.0014	0.3940	0.1362	0.0154	0.0000
ln_xLxM	-0.1090	0.0073	0.0000	0.0005	0.0015	0.7500	-0.1009	0.0137	0.0000
t_2	-0.0044	0.0004	0.0000	-0.0262	0.0080	0.0010	-0.0048	0.0007	0.0000
ln_yt	0.0006	0.0007	0.3440	0.1204	0.0081	0.0000	0.0037	0.0012	0.0020
ln_xLt	-0.0013	0.0014	0.3590	0.1416	0.0069	0.0000	0.0018	0.0027	0.5140
ln_xMt	0.0004	0.0015	0.8070	-0.1072	0.0073	0.0000	-0.0007	0.0025	0.7660
ln_yxL	0.0238	0.0069	0.0010	0.0238	0.0072	0.0010	-0.0053	0.0079	0.5000
ln_yxM	-0.0264	0.0069	0.0000	-0.0271	0.0073	0.0000	0.0024	0.0093	0.7930
_cons	-0.0584	0.0153	0.0000	-0.0735	0.0137	0.0000	-0.1401	0.0128	0.0000
ln_y_gmean				-0.0656	0.0159	0.0000			
ln_xL_gmean				0.0113	0.0159	0.4790			
ln_xM_gmean				0.0011	0.0172	0.9490			
t_gmean				-0.0050	0.0058	0.3910			
			p-value			p-value			p-value
R2	0.9814			0.9860					
Wald/F-test	544157.3	χ^2 [30]	0.000	137106.3	χ^2 [34]	0.000	6626.1	F[30,846]	0.000
AR(2)							-0.25		0.802
Hansen test							562.46	χ^2 [599]	0.855
N. instruments							630		
N. groups							847		

Table A12 – Food processing industry: United Kingdom. (Source: Own calculation)

UK	GTRE			GTRE with Mundlak			GMM		
	Coef.	Std.	P> z	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> z	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_y	-0.9777	0.0085	0.0000	-0.9469	0.0133	0.0000	-0.9902	0.0093	0.0000
ln_y_d101	-0.0374	0.0123	0.0020	-0.0379	0.0115	0.0010	-0.0336	0.0172	0.0520
ln_y_d105	0.0853	0.0620	0.1690	0.0766	0.0581	0.1870	0.0011	0.0217	0.9610
ln_y_d106	-0.0139	0.0332	0.6760	-0.0211	0.0330	0.5230	-0.0823	0.0419	0.0500
ln_y_d107	-0.0445	0.0185	0.0160	-0.0363	0.0162	0.0250	-0.0421	0.0305	0.1670
ln_xL	0.3672	0.0111	0.0000	0.3713	0.0116	0.0000	0.3356	0.0197	0.0000
ln_xL_d101	-0.0443	0.0165	0.0070	-0.0492	0.0171	0.0040	-0.0566	0.0408	0.1650
ln_xL_d105	0.0065	0.0250	0.7950	0.0010	0.0248	0.9680	-0.0509	0.0464	0.2720
ln_xL_d106	0.0387	0.0336	0.2490	0.0360	0.0326	0.2700	-0.0558	0.0646	0.3880
ln_xL_d107	-0.0137	0.0228	0.5490	-0.0140	0.0226	0.5350	0.0004	0.0474	0.9930
ln_xM	0.6061	0.0111	0.0000	0.6025	0.0126	0.0000	0.5974	0.0155	0.0000
ln_xM_d101	0.0429	0.0157	0.0060	0.0464	0.0165	0.0050	0.0288	0.0314	0.3590
ln_xM_d105	-0.0071	0.0240	0.7670	-0.0041	0.0239	0.8650	0.0619	0.0255	0.0150
ln_xM_d106	-0.0637	0.0345	0.0650	-0.0618	0.0339	0.0680	-0.1036	0.0632	0.1010
ln_xM_d107	0.0017	0.0207	0.9340	0.0016	0.0202	0.9350	0.0643	0.0274	0.0190
t	-0.0088	0.0009	0.0000	-0.0099	0.0010	0.0000	-0.0089	0.0017	0.0000
t_d101	0.0039	0.0012	0.0020	0.0043	0.0012	0.0000	0.0014	0.0027	0.6060
t_d105	0.0041	0.0025	0.1020	0.0045	0.0025	0.0660	0.0060	0.0045	0.1840
t_d106	0.0026	0.0027	0.3320	0.0033	0.0027	0.2130	-0.0009	0.0047	0.8440
t_d107	0.0057	0.0020	0.0050	0.0061	0.0020	0.0020	0.0032	0.0038	0.4050
ln_y_2	-0.0142	0.0119	0.2310	-0.0013	0.0003	0.0000	-0.0137	0.0123	0.2650
ln_xL_2	0.1348	0.0132	0.0000	0.0013	0.0006	0.0260	0.0636	0.0177	0.0000
ln_xM_2	0.1465	0.0105	0.0000	0.0011	0.0012	0.3810	0.1192	0.0128	0.0000
ln_xLxM	-0.1362	0.0111	0.0000	0.0006	0.0009	0.5160	-0.0816	0.0129	0.0000
t_2	-0.0012	0.0003	0.0000	-0.0144	0.0112	0.1970	-0.0026	0.0007	0.0000
ln_yt	0.0013	0.0006	0.0330	0.1354	0.0130	0.0000	0.0040	0.0014	0.0040
ln_xLt	0.0011	0.0012	0.3920	0.1472	0.0103	0.0000	0.0050	0.0033	0.1310
ln_xMt	0.0006	0.0009	0.5220	-0.1362	0.0110	0.0000	-0.0013	0.0025	0.5890
ln_yxL	0.0001	0.0071	0.9860	0.0010	0.0069	0.8870	-0.0173	0.0159	0.2790
ln_yxM	-0.0043	0.0056	0.4460	-0.0054	0.0054	0.3240	0.0109	0.0107	0.3050
_cons	-0.0638	0.0132	0.0000	-0.0672	0.0123	0.0000	-0.0682	0.0124	0.0000
ln_y_gmean				-0.0654	0.0139	0.0000			
ln_xL_gmean				-0.0244	0.0135	0.0710			
ln_xM_gmean				-0.0020	0.0110	0.8520			
t_gmean				-0.0079	0.0033	0.0180			
			p-value			p-value			p-value
R2	0.9898			0.9905					
Wald/F-test	190395.5	$\chi^2[30]$	0.000	245212.5	$\chi^2[34]$	0.000	3873.1	F[30,801]	0.000
AR(2)							-1.40		0.162
Hansen test							562.47	$\chi^2[567]$	0.546
N. instruments							598		
N. groups							802		

FOOD PROCESSING INDUSTRY: COUNTRY SPECIFIC RETURNS TO SCALE

Table B1 – Food processing industry: Returns to scale. (Source: Own calculation)

Country	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Austria	1.0615	0.1063	0.8274	1.5078
Belgium	0.9957	0.0484	0.7867	1.3229
Czechia	1.0416	0.0460	0.9125	1.3072
Finland	1.0229	0.0523	0.8041	1.2216
France	1.0303	0.0328	0.8761	1.2387
Germany	1.0026	0.0432	0.7484	1.1974
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	1.0278	0.0493	0.8822	1.4654
Romania	1.0486	0.0563	0.8672	1.4324
Spain	1.0258	0.0267	0.9314	1.1670
Sweden	0.9877	0.0247	0.9300	1.1229
United Kingdom	0.9947	0.0303	0.9001	1.1098

FOOD PROCESSING INDUSTRY: OVERALL TECHNICAL EFFICIENCY AND ITS DECOMPOSITION

Table C1 – Food processing industry: Overall technical efficiency and its decomposition. (Source: Own calculation)

Country	Overall technical efficiency				Transient technical efficiency				Persistent technical efficiency			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Austria	0.7690	0.0703	0.0026	0.9228	0.8411	0.0591	0.0045	0.9835	0.9135	0.0463	0.5897	0.9757
Belgium	0.9291	0.0242	0.4939	0.9916	0.9303	0.0242	0.4945	0.9928	0.9988	0.0000	0.9988	0.9988
Czechia	0.9107	0.0285	0.2990	0.9911	0.9110	0.0285	0.2991	0.9913	0.9997	0.0000	0.9997	0.9997
Finland	0.9006	0.0352	0.4403	0.9839	0.9008	0.0352	0.4404	0.9842	0.9997	0.0000	0.9997	0.9997
France	0.9315	0.0279	0.1178	0.9948	0.9322	0.0279	0.1179	0.9956	0.9992	0.0000	0.9992	0.9993
Germany	0.9302	0.0274	0.2017	0.9930	0.9306	0.0274	0.2018	0.9934	0.9995	0.0000	0.9995	0.9995
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	0.8325	0.0496	0.1848	0.9633	0.9213	0.0339	0.2208	0.9910	0.9035	0.0398	0.5952	0.9795
Romania	0.7974	0.0360	0.2897	0.9284	0.8665	0.0314	0.3546	0.9669	0.9201	0.0204	0.6639	0.9757
Spain	0.9265	0.0309	0.2028	0.9920	0.9266	0.0309	0.2028	0.9922	0.9998	0.0000	0.9998	0.9998
Sweden	0.9481	0.0140	0.7377	0.9894	0.9498	0.0141	0.7390	0.9912	0.9982	0.0000	0.9980	0.9983
United Kingdom	0.9440	0.0221	0.5400	0.9911	0.9446	0.0222	0.5404	0.9918	0.9993	0.0000	0.9993	0.9993

Table C2 – Food processing industry: Overall technical efficiency in selected sectors. (Source: Own calculation)

Country	10.1				10.5			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Austria	0.7592	0.0483	0.6104	0.8876	0.7548	0.0541	0.5414	0.8577
Belgium	0.9291	0.0197	0.7677	0.9803	0.9297	0.0158	0.7940	0.9684
Czechia	0.9112	0.0260	0.3838	0.9911	0.9121	0.0185	0.7230	0.9686
Finland	0.9008	0.0342	0.4452	0.9732	0.9028	0.0219	0.7840	0.9635
France	0.9318	0.0208	0.5627	0.9843	0.9320	0.0243	0.3968	0.9947
Germany	0.9311	0.0149	0.7980	0.9847	0.9303	0.0271	0.4859	0.9846
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	0.8272	0.0453	0.2907	0.9603	0.8393	0.0345	0.5913	0.9398
Romania	0.7985	0.0396	0.3775	0.9245	0.7947	0.0382	0.3371	0.9241
Spain	0.9266	0.0274	0.4190	0.9870	0.9267	0.0249	0.6573	0.9806
Sweden	0.9485	0.0109	0.8185	0.9880	0.9466	0.0192	0.8194	0.9892
United Kingdom	0.9449	0.0173	0.7293	0.9799	0.9427	0.0266	0.7332	0.9847
Country	10.6				10.7			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Austria	0.7285	0.0468	0.6601	0.8232	0.7483	0.0344	0.6643	0.8191
Belgium	0.9307	0.0163	0.7657	0.9653	0.9280	0.0341	0.4939	0.9874
Czechia	0.9103	0.0288	0.5547	0.9867	0.9110	0.0226	0.5535	0.9852
Finland	0.8969	0.0476	0.5466	0.9680	0.9031	0.0217	0.4784	0.9839
France	0.9321	0.0222	0.7243	0.9811	0.9332	0.0206	0.1881	0.9948
Germany	0.9296	0.0551	0.2017	0.9778	0.9311	0.0246	0.5374	0.9860
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	0.8355	0.0426	0.5820	0.9207	0.8331	0.0684	0.1953	0.9633
Romania	0.7936	0.0432	0.3580	0.9119	0.7972	0.0296	0.3416	0.9220
Spain	0.9274	0.0272	0.7253	0.9822	0.9274	0.0331	0.2028	0.9904
Sweden	0.9481	0.0134	0.8849	0.9765	0.9487	0.0097	0.8439	0.9847
United Kingdom	0.9418	0.0317	0.6321	0.9805	0.9441	0.0176	0.8546	0.9827

FOOD PROCESSING INDUSTRY: DEVELOPMENT OF TRANSIENT TECHNICAL EFFICIENCY

Figure A1a –Food processing industry: Development of transient technical efficiency (part 1). (Source: Own calculation)

Figure A1b - Food processing industry: Development of transient technical efficiency (part 2). (Source: Own calculation)

FOOD PROCESSING INDUSTRY: TOTAL FACTOR PRODUCTIVITY DEVELOPMENT

Figure B1a - Food processing industry: TFP development (part 1). (Source: Own calculation)

Figure B1b - Food processing industry: TFP development (part 2). (Source: Own calculation)

FOOD PROCESSING INDUSTRY: TOTAL FACTOR PRODUCTIVITY COMPONENTS

Table D1 – Food processing: Scale effects in selected sectors. (Source: Own calculation)

Country	10.1				10.5			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Austria	0.0077	0.0371	-0.0417	0.1031	-0.0225	0.0718	-0.2231	0.1346
Belgium	-0.0009	0.0569	-0.2606	0.1084	-0.0015	0.0337	-0.1780	0.1549
Czechia	-0.0218	0.0751	-0.1013	0.5784	-0.0452	0.0795	-0.0999	0.4982
Finland	-0.0206	0.1121	-0.3991	0.4215	-0.0319	0.0562	-0.1552	0.1429
France	-0.0079	0.1040	-0.6672	0.0725	-0.0328	0.1311	-0.6981	0.0542
Germany	0.0026	0.0639	-0.3969	0.0493	0.0184	0.0440	-0.3058	0.0508
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	-0.0056	0.0423	-0.3881	0.2873	-0.0125	0.0695	-0.3997	0.1192
Romania	-0.0309	0.0613	-0.1201	0.5395	-0.0211	0.0881	-0.1667	0.6104
Spain	-0.0112	0.0385	-0.1203	0.2256	0.0071	0.0382	-0.0222	0.1756
Sweden	0.0068	0.0204	-0.1034	0.0438	-0.0048	0.0352	-0.1699	0.0212
United Kingdom	0.0023	0.0402	-0.0486	0.1960	0.0015	0.0327	-0.0333	0.1915
Country	10.6				10.7			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Austria	-0.0407	0.0802	-0.1607	0.0854	0.0494	0.0797	-0.0611	0.2117
Belgium	-0.0049	0.0355	-0.1553	0.0696	0.0041	0.0237	-0.1052	0.0710
Czechia	-0.0206	0.1240	-0.0927	0.5585	0.0078	0.0858	-0.0875	0.7694
Finland	-0.0007	0.0452	-0.0917	0.2388	0.0117	0.0564	-0.1703	0.2756
France	-0.0080	0.0905	-0.5324	0.0583	0.0336	0.0503	-0.6790	0.0698
Germany	0.0084	0.0547	-0.1738	0.0684	-0.0267	0.0915	-0.3592	0.0488
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	-0.0111	0.0724	-0.2505	0.3661	0.0326	0.0851	-0.3853	0.2191
Romania	0.0269	0.1140	-0.1657	0.6956	0.0083	0.0652	-0.1045	0.8964
Spain	-0.0313	0.0625	-0.1218	0.2413	0.0330	0.0686	-0.1051	0.2524
Sweden	0.0034	0.0192	-0.0586	0.0389	-0.0057	0.0213	-0.1303	0.0510
United Kingdom	-0.0026	0.0473	-0.1465	0.1367	-0.0108	0.0477	-0.0691	0.2251

Table D2 – Food processing: Technical efficiency effects in selected sectors. (Source: Own calculation)

Country	10.1				10.5			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Austria	0.0003	0.0455	-0.1964	0.1078	-0.0043	0.0542	-0.2568	0.0926
Belgium	0.0001	0.0217	-0.1904	0.0540	-0.0061	0.0094	-0.0385	0.0305
Czechia	0.0005	0.0343	-0.8387	0.0806	0.0016	0.0184	-0.1992	0.0558
Finland	0.0003	0.0433	-0.7035	0.0784	0.0030	0.0247	-0.1378	0.0684
France	0.0006	0.0235	-0.5035	0.0557	0.0008	0.0304	-0.8528	0.0662
Germany	0.0014	0.0162	-0.1527	0.0576	0.0002	0.0344	-0.6487	0.0575
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	-0.0001	0.0391	-0.9174	0.0684	0.0019	0.0320	-0.3774	0.0609
Romania	-0.0005	0.0433	-0.5735	0.0991	-0.0010	0.0454	-0.8089	0.1044
Spain	0.0003	0.0322	-0.7929	0.0640	0.0006	0.0281	-0.3425	0.0575
Sweden	0.0005	0.0118	-0.1468	0.0413	-0.0017	0.0210	-0.1457	0.0426
United Kingdom	0.0011	0.0191	-0.2577	0.0377	-0.0014	0.0297	-0.2524	0.0425
Country	10.6				10.7			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Austria	-0.0222	0.0441	-0.0845	0.0636	-0.0047	0.0364	-0.1074	0.0688
Belgium	0.0019	0.0185	-0.1931	0.0385	-0.0017	0.0440	-0.6315	0.0612
Czechia	-0.0008	0.0336	-0.4694	0.0778	0.0005	0.0249	-0.4607	0.0757
Finland	-0.0048	0.0587	-0.4985	0.0730	0.0034	0.0271	-0.6316	0.0894
France	0.0010	0.0247	-0.2510	0.0525	0.0021	0.0278	-1.5992	0.0664
Germany	-0.0039	0.1104	-1.5278	0.0505	0.0011	0.0309	-0.5480	0.0589
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	0.0004	0.0346	-0.2910	0.0644	-0.0016	0.0617	-1.4277	0.0738
Romania	-0.0023	0.0495	-0.7897	0.1006	0.0009	0.0310	-0.6378	0.1094
Spain	0.0012	0.0307	-0.2441	0.0591	0.0007	0.0501	-1.5187	0.0674
Sweden	0.0000	0.0143	-0.0689	0.0296	0.0007	0.0103	-0.1164	0.0380
United Kingdom	-0.0027	0.0368	-0.4007	0.0383	0.0003	0.0189	-0.0991	0.0405

Table D3 – Food processing: Technical change effects in selected sectors. (Source: Own calculation)

Country	10.1				10.5			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Austria	0.0009	0.0099	-0.0170	0.0326	-0.0012	0.0114	-0.0280	0.0238
Belgium	-0.0061	0.0094	-0.0385	0.0305	-0.0052	0.0108	-0.0662	0.0214
Czechia	-0.0019	0.0039	-0.0122	0.0093	-0.0050	0.0039	-0.0136	0.0059
Finland	0.0276	0.0191	-0.0319	0.0992	-0.0197	0.0214	-0.0742	0.0391
France	-0.0034	0.0088	-0.0306	0.0238	-0.0011	0.0095	-0.0237	0.0266
Germany	0.0049	0.0067	-0.0100	0.0239	0.0005	0.0127	-0.0201	0.0672
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	-0.0040	0.0068	-0.0352	0.0154	-0.0026	0.0081	-0.0316	0.0159
Romania	-0.0030	0.0957	-0.2410	0.2294	-0.0066	0.0888	-0.2520	0.2072
Spain	-0.0035	0.0025	-0.0127	0.0060	-0.0070	0.0027	-0.0159	-0.0004
Sweden	0.0017	0.0137	-0.0403	0.0306	0.0135	0.0128	-0.0265	0.0404
United Kingdom	0.0012	0.0126	-0.0408	0.0278	-0.0036	0.0137	-0.0494	0.0283
Country	10.6				10.7			
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min.	Max.
Austria	0.0019	0.0143	-0.0169	0.0245	-0.0010	0.0091	-0.0214	0.0191
Belgium	-0.0007	0.0079	-0.0564	0.0129	-0.0001	0.0073	-0.0335	0.0576
Czechia	-0.0111	0.0041	-0.0190	0.0011	0.0006	0.0035	-0.0103	0.0109
Finland	-0.0452	0.0255	-0.1607	0.0017	0.0121	0.0168	-0.0357	0.0713
France	-0.0010	0.0089	-0.0186	0.0237	-0.0004	0.0079	-0.0256	0.0266
Germany	0.0014	0.0076	-0.0140	0.0179	-0.0049	0.0071	-0.0207	0.0150
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	0.0008	0.0057	-0.0170	0.0129	0.0040	0.0068	-0.0211	0.0248
Romania	0.0032	0.0864	-0.2614	0.2055	0.0017	0.0829	-0.2499	0.2109
Spain	0.0025	0.0027	-0.0043	0.0124	0.0032	0.0024	-0.0052	0.0107
Sweden	0.0028	0.0155	-0.0366	0.0328	-0.0052	0.0128	-0.0477	0.0336
United Kingdom	0.0039	0.0116	-0.0235	0.0303	-0.0007	0.0122	-0.0448	0.0260

FOOD PROCESSING INDUSTRY: META-FRONTIER TRANSIENT TECHNICAL EFFICIENCY

Table E1 – Food processing: Meta-frontier transient technical efficiency (10.1). (Source: Own calculation)

Country	GTRE		GTRE with Mundlak		GMM	
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.
Austria	0.9591	0.0058	0.9718	0.0025	0.9443	0.0087
Belgium	0.9582	0.0183	0.9714	0.0084	0.9424	0.0300
Czechia	0.9575	0.0201	0.9710	0.0084	0.9407	0.0365
Finland	0.9579	0.0218	0.9708	0.0129	0.9407	0.0349
France	0.9592	0.0079	0.9717	0.0041	0.9438	0.0147
Germany	0.9595	0.0075	0.9721	0.0029	0.9444	0.0150
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	0.9587	0.0116	0.9715	0.0059	0.9431	0.0192
Romania	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE
Spain	0.9585	0.0122	0.9713	0.0062	0.9426	0.0201
Sweden	0.9588	0.0103	0.9714	0.0054	0.9429	0.0195
United Kingdom	0.9580	0.0094	0.9711	0.0042	0.9419	0.0140

Note: LNO means low number of observation, EE is excluded from estimation

Table E2 – Food processing: Meta-frontier transient technical efficiency (10.5). (Source: Own calculation)

Country	GTRE		GTRE with Mundlak		GMM	
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.
Austria	0.9566	0.0077	0.9634	0.0051	0.9511	0.0093
Belgium	0.9558	0.0116	0.9628	0.0086	0.9495	0.0155
Czechia	0.9555	0.0183	0.9626	0.0123	0.9492	0.0220
Finland	0.9559	0.0156	0.9627	0.0113	0.9498	0.0181
France	0.9566	0.0123	0.9633	0.0088	0.9506	0.0153
Germany	0.9562	0.0163	0.9631	0.0117	0.9494	0.0249
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	0.9564	0.0115	0.9631	0.0083	0.9505	0.0141
Romania	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE
Spain	0.9562	0.0120	0.9629	0.0085	0.9503	0.0147
Sweden	0.9521	0.0261	0.9596	0.0211	0.9454	0.0317
United Kingdom	0.9554	0.0155	0.9627	0.0102	0.9495	0.0191

Note: LNO means low number of observation, EE is excluded from estimation

Table E3 – Food processing: Meta-frontier transient technical efficiency (10.6). (Source: Own calculation)

Country	GTRE		GTRE with Mundlak		GMM	
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.
Austria	0.9342	0.0070	0.9426	0.0074	0.9264	0.0092
Belgium	0.9334	0.0172	0.9420	0.0128	0.9279	0.0144
Czechia	0.9311	0.0323	0.9388	0.0281	0.9238	0.0371
Finland	0.9307	0.0393	0.9375	0.0354	0.9242	0.0441
France	0.9344	0.0149	0.9423	0.0140	0.9285	0.0156
Germany	0.9325	0.0481	0.9425	0.0385	0.9263	0.0526
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	0.9335	0.0174	0.9419	0.0146	0.9274	0.0186
Romania	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE
Spain	0.9331	0.0184	0.9415	0.0149	0.9269	0.0199
Sweden	0.9322	0.0221	0.9394	0.0204	0.9267	0.0238
United Kingdom	0.9330	0.0196	0.9416	0.0153	0.9266	0.0232

Note: LNO means low number of observation, EE is excluded from estimation

Table E4 – Food processing: Meta-frontier transient technical efficiency (10.7). (Source: Own calculation)

Country	GTRE		GTRE with Mundlak		GMM	
	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.	Mean	Std.Dev.
Austria	0.9514	0.0063	0.9539	0.0054	0.9423	0.0081
Belgium	0.9512	0.0149	0.9538	0.0135	0.9424	0.0221
Czechia	0.9485	0.0239	0.9506	0.0220	0.9384	0.0329
Finland	0.9511	0.0200	0.9532	0.0187	0.9416	0.0263
France	0.9517	0.0112	0.9537	0.0104	0.9429	0.0155
Germany	0.9522	0.0150	0.9548	0.0139	0.9434	0.0230
Ireland	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO	LNO
Italy	0.9511	0.0183	0.9532	0.0169	0.9422	0.0233
Romania	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE	EE
Spain	0.9504	0.0223	0.9526	0.0205	0.9414	0.0280
Sweden	0.9512	0.0148	0.9532	0.0139	0.9418	0.0192
United Kingdom	0.9510	0.0118	0.9533	0.0113	0.9421	0.0151

Note: LNO means low number of observation, EE is excluded from estimation

ANNEX II

AGRICULTURE - CEREALS: COUNTRY INPUT DISTANCE FUNCTION ESTIMATES

Table F1 – Cereals: Austria. (Source: Own calculation)

Austria	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_xM			
ln_yC	-0.1124	0.0122	0.0000
ln_yAOC	-0.1149	0.0087	0.0000
ln_yAOO	-0.4294	0.0132	0.0000
ln_xL	0.1331	0.0243	0.0000
ln_xW	0.2474	0.0229	0.0000
ln_xK	0.1893	0.0253	0.0000
ln_yC_2	-0.0520	0.0178	0.0040
ln_yAOC_2	-0.0390	0.0059	0.0000
ln_yAOO_2	-0.0631	0.0119	0.0000
ln_yCyAOC	-0.0003	0.0081	0.9700
ln_yCyAOO	0.0735	0.0121	0.0000
ln_yAOCyAOO	0.0275	0.0074	0.0000
ln_xL_2	0.0456	0.0768	0.5530
ln_xW_2	0.0762	0.0879	0.3860
ln_xK_2	0.0882	0.1093	0.4200
ln_xLxW	0.0572	0.0693	0.4090
ln_xLxK	-0.0960	0.0727	0.1870
ln_xWxK	0.0399	0.0728	0.5830
t	-0.0003	0.0015	0.8400
t_2	0.0041	0.0006	0.0000
ln_yCt	-0.0086	0.0029	0.0030
ln_yAOCt	0.0075	0.0018	0.0000
ln_yAOOt	0.0007	0.0019	0.6940
ln_xLt	0.0072	0.0048	0.1370
ln_xWt	-0.0073	0.0046	0.1120
ln_xKt	-0.0034	0.0049	0.4880
ln_yCxL	-0.0356	0.0290	0.2200
ln_yAOCxL	0.0381	0.0163	0.0190
ln_yAOOxL	-0.0095	0.0311	0.7590
ln_yCxW	0.0529	0.0326	0.1050
ln_yAOCxW	-0.0480	0.0169	0.0050
ln_yAOOxW	0.0460	0.0202	0.0230
ln_yCxK	0.0763	0.0341	0.0260
ln_yAOCxK	0.0163	0.0208	0.4350
ln_yAOOxK	-0.0035	0.0247	0.8860
D2008	0.0094	0.0080	0.2410
_cons	0.2375	0.0212	0.0000
			p-value
F-test	267.61	F[36,846]	0.000
AR(2)	-0.05		0.956
Hansen test	816.12	χ^2 [831]	0.637
Significance of technical change	13.8	F[8,846]	0.000
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE	6.28		0.005
N. instruments	868		
N. groups	847		

Table F2 – Cereals: Belgium. (Source: Own calculation)

Belgium	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_xM			
ln_yC	-0.1121	0.0198	0.0000
ln_yAOC	-0.0619	0.0156	0.0000
ln_yAOC	-0.4103	0.0388	0.0000
ln_xL	0.1508	0.0696	0.0310
ln_xW	0.3639	0.0500	0.0000
ln_xK	0.1243	0.0652	0.0580
ln_yC_2	-0.0378	0.0199	0.0580
ln_yAOC_2	-0.0253	0.0176	0.1510
ln_yAOC_2	-0.0703	0.0212	0.0010
ln_yCyAOC	-0.0125	0.0189	0.5090
ln_yCyAOC	0.0279	0.0242	0.2500
ln_yAOCyAOC	0.0463	0.0238	0.0520
ln_xL_2	-0.0437	0.2335	0.8510
ln_xW_2	0.1650	0.1774	0.3530
ln_xK_2	0.0222	0.1214	0.8550
ln_xLxW	-0.1257	0.1449	0.3860
ln_xLxK	0.0916	0.1531	0.5500
ln_xWxK	0.1550	0.0946	0.1020
t	-0.0170	0.0031	0.0000
t_2	0.0046	0.0011	0.0000
ln_yCt	-0.0037	0.0050	0.4560
ln_yAOCt	0.0041	0.0038	0.2920
ln_yAOCt	0.0056	0.0044	0.2040
ln_xLt	-0.0024	0.0091	0.7950
ln_xWt	0.0109	0.0083	0.1900
ln_xKt	0.0067	0.0072	0.3560
ln_yCxL	0.0410	0.0542	0.4500
ln_yAOCxL	0.0659	0.0480	0.1710
ln_yAOCxL	-0.0451	0.0504	0.3710
ln_yCxW	0.0194	0.0545	0.7220
ln_yAOCxW	-0.0451	0.0468	0.3370
ln_yAOCxW	0.0539	0.0425	0.2050
ln_yCxK	0.0247	0.0519	0.6340
ln_yAOCxK	0.0253	0.0490	0.6070
ln_yAOCxK	0.0865	0.0401	0.0320
D2008	-0.1969	0.0523	0.0000
D2009	-0.0629	0.0255	0.0140
DLFA	0.0421	0.0298	0.1580
_cons	0.1953	0.0381	0.0000
			p-value
F-test	82.57	F[38,348]	0.000
AR(2)	-0.90		0.370
Hansen test	189.44	χ^2 [465]	1.000
Significance of technical change	4.73	F[8,348]	0.000
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE	26.68		0.000
N. instruments	504		
N. groups	349		

Table F3 – Cereals: Czechia. (Source: Own calculation)

Czechia	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_xM			
ln_yC	-0.3321	0.0149	0.0000
ln_yAOC	-0.3040	0.0136	0.0000
ln_yAOO	-0.3083	0.0158	0.0000
ln_xL	0.1268	0.0474	0.0080
ln_xW	0.1500	0.0345	0.0000
ln_xK	0.0875	0.0187	0.0000
ln_yC_2	-0.1490	0.0288	0.0000
ln_yAOC_2	-0.0850	0.0131	0.0000
ln_yAOO_2	-0.0780	0.0082	0.0000
ln_yCyAOC	0.0785	0.0169	0.0000
ln_yCyAOO	0.0760	0.0130	0.0000
ln_yAOCyAOO	0.0022	0.0105	0.8330
ln_xL_2	-0.3965	0.1984	0.0460
ln_xW_2	-0.2673	0.1123	0.0180
ln_xK_2	0.0749	0.0344	0.0300
ln_xLxW	0.2249	0.1291	0.0820
ln_xLxK	-0.0412	0.0727	0.5710
ln_xWxK	0.0388	0.0563	0.4920
t	-0.0006	0.0024	0.8160
t_2	0.0096	0.0010	0.0000
ln_yCt	0.0075	0.0041	0.0680
ln_yAOCt	-0.0047	0.0033	0.1490
ln_yAOOt	0.0051	0.0017	0.0030
ln_xLt	0.0174	0.0075	0.0210
ln_xWt	0.0137	0.0075	0.0680
ln_xKt	-0.0058	0.0041	0.1560
ln_yCxL	0.1006	0.0652	0.1230
ln_yAOCxL	-0.0638	0.0513	0.2140
ln_yAOOxL	-0.0175	0.0346	0.6120
ln_yCxW	-0.0480	0.0473	0.3110
ln_yAOCxW	0.0033	0.0373	0.9290
ln_yAOOxW	0.0252	0.0285	0.3770
ln_yCxK	0.0525	0.0293	0.0730
ln_yAOCxK	-0.0221	0.0251	0.3790
ln_yAOOxK	-0.0089	0.0168	0.5970
D2008	-0.1643	0.0182	0.0000
D2009	0.0574	0.0094	0.0000
DLFA	-0.1834	0.0351	0.0000
_cons	0.2152	0.0308	0.0000
			p-value
F-test	1925.86	F[38,632]	0.000
AR(2)	-0.69		0.490
Hansen test	567.44	χ^2 [532]	0.139
Significance of technical change	32.37	F[8,632]	0.000
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE	12.92		0.000
N. instruments	571		
N. groups	633		

Table F4 – Cereals: Finland. (Source: Own calculation)

Finland	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
In_xM			
In_yC	-0.2247	0.0141	0.0000
In_yAOC	-0.1337	0.0086	0.0000
In_yAOO	-0.2766	0.0121	0.0000
In_xL	0.1763	0.0435	0.0000
In_xW	0.2824	0.0257	0.0000
In_xK	0.0694	0.0298	0.0200
In_yC_2	-0.0722	0.0224	0.0010
In_yAOC_2	-0.0371	0.0041	0.0000
In_yAOO_2	-0.0710	0.0076	0.0000
In_yCyAOC	0.0171	0.0072	0.0180
In_yCyAOO	0.0430	0.0101	0.0000
In_yAOCyAOO	0.0136	0.0041	0.0010
In_xL_2	0.0643	0.1821	0.7240
In_xW_2	0.1657	0.0713	0.0210
In_xK_2	0.1584	0.0731	0.0310
In_xLxW	-0.0075	0.0683	0.9130
In_xLxK	0.0692	0.0845	0.4130
In_xWxK	-0.0652	0.0555	0.2410
t	0.0136	0.0027	0.0000
t_2	0.0040	0.0010	0.0000
In_yCt	-0.0079	0.0039	0.0440
In_yAOCt	-0.0021	0.0016	0.1960
In_yAOOt	0.0026	0.0021	0.2190
In_xLt	-0.0123	0.0091	0.1740
In_xWt	0.0099	0.0071	0.1650
In_xKt	0.0121	0.0072	0.0940
In_yCxL	-0.0326	0.0500	0.5140
In_yAOCxL	0.0110	0.0193	0.5690
In_yAOOxL	0.0186	0.0340	0.5850
In_yCxW	0.0641	0.0292	0.0290
In_yAOCxW	-0.0059	0.0145	0.6830
In_yAOOxW	0.0196	0.0154	0.2050
In_yCxK	0.0148	0.0287	0.6070
In_yAOCxK	0.0114	0.0116	0.3280
In_yAOOxK	0.0031	0.0184	0.8660
D2008	-0.0934	0.0274	0.0010
DLFA	-0.3539	0.0725	0.0000
_cons	0.5840	0.0761	0.0000
			p-value
F-test	353.95	F[37,385]	
AR(2)	-1.39		0.164
Hansen test	369.1	χ^2 [1606]	1.000
Significance of technical change	11.79	F[8,385]	0.000
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE	23.18		0.000
N. instruments	1644		
N. groups	386		

Table F5 – Cereals: France. (Source: Own calculation)

France	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_xM			
ln_yC	-0.3162	0.0109	0.0000
ln_yAOC	-0.1175	0.0078	0.0000
ln_yAOC	-0.2996	0.0069	0.0000
ln_xL	0.1574	0.0215	0.0000
ln_xW	0.2132	0.0172	0.0000
ln_xK	0.1415	0.0163	0.0000
ln_yC_2	-0.1171	0.0161	0.0000
ln_yAOC_2	-0.0342	0.0064	0.0000
ln_yAOC_2	-0.0674	0.0038	0.0000
ln_yCyAOC	-0.0019	0.0072	0.7870
ln_yCyAOC	0.0227	0.0078	0.0040
ln_yAOCyAOC	0.0390	0.0047	0.0000
ln_xL_2	-0.0076	0.0713	0.9160
ln_xW_2	-0.1165	0.0800	0.1460
ln_xK_2	0.0449	0.0460	0.3290
ln_xLxW	0.0645	0.0553	0.2430
ln_xLxK	-0.0494	0.0406	0.2240
ln_xWxK	0.0230	0.0433	0.5950
t	-0.0043	0.0009	0.0000
t_2	0.0020	0.0003	0.0000
ln_yCt	0.0009	0.0019	0.6480
ln_yAOCt	-0.0019	0.0013	0.1490
ln_yAOCt	-0.0020	0.0009	0.0250
ln_xLt	-0.0037	0.0033	0.2730
ln_xWt	0.0055	0.0037	0.1340
ln_xKt	0.0029	0.0033	0.3740
ln_yCxL	-0.0173	0.0264	0.5120
ln_yAOCxL	0.0816	0.0158	0.0000
ln_yAOCxL	0.0222	0.0144	0.1240
ln_yCxW	-0.0959	0.0319	0.0030
ln_yAOCxW	-0.0186	0.0174	0.2850
ln_yAOCxW	-0.0086	0.0138	0.5360
ln_yCxK	0.0339	0.0257	0.1880
ln_yAOCxK	-0.0350	0.0155	0.0240
ln_yAOCxK	-0.0006	0.0109	0.9570
_cons	0.2044	0.0125	0.0000
			p-value
F-test	599.87	F[35,1348]	0.000
AR(2)	-0.01		0.993
Hansen test	1328.49	χ^2 [1298]	0.272
Significance of technical change	8.98	F[8,1348]	0.000
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE	25.28		0.000
N. instruments	1334		
N. groups	1349		

Table F6 – Cereals: West Germany. (Source: Own calculation)

West Germany	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_xM			
ln_yC	-0.2435	0.0152	0.0000
ln_yAOC	-0.0957	0.0083	0.0000
ln_yAOO	-0.4084	0.0126	0.0000
ln_xL	0.1108	0.0233	0.0000
ln_xW	0.2697	0.0252	0.0000
ln_xK	0.0719	0.0174	0.0000
ln_yC_2	-0.1365	0.0148	0.0000
ln_yAOC_2	-0.0566	0.0069	0.0000
ln_yAOO_2	-0.0764	0.0087	0.0000
ln_yCyAOC	0.0126	0.0074	0.0880
ln_yCyAOO	0.0616	0.0135	0.0000
ln_yAOCyAOO	0.0424	0.0076	0.0000
ln_xL_2	-0.3066	0.0791	0.0000
ln_xW_2	0.1530	0.0620	0.0140
ln_xK_2	0.0449	0.0399	0.2600
ln_xLxW	0.0811	0.0498	0.1040
ln_xLxK	0.0963	0.0419	0.0220
ln_xWxK	-0.0119	0.0372	0.7500
t	-0.0319	0.0054	0.0000
t_2	0.0164	0.0016	0.0000
ln_yCt	-0.0033	0.0033	0.3080
ln_yAOCt	-0.0001	0.0017	0.9520
ln_yAOOt	0.0038	0.0020	0.0490
ln_xLt	0.0014	0.0049	0.7720
ln_xWt	-0.0011	0.0052	0.8400
ln_xKt	-0.0003	0.0039	0.9380
ln_yCxL	0.0768	0.0247	0.0020
ln_yAOCxL	0.0472	0.0156	0.0030
ln_yAOOxL	-0.0425	0.0255	0.0960
ln_yCxW	0.0078	0.0288	0.7880
ln_yAOCxW	-0.0121	0.0146	0.4060
ln_yAOOxW	0.0890	0.0195	0.0000
ln_yCxK	-0.0360	0.0222	0.1060
ln_yAOCxK	-0.0019	0.0115	0.8650
ln_yAOOxK	-0.0055	0.0184	0.7640
D2009	0.0778	0.0129	0.0000
DLFA	-0.0458	0.0102	0.0000
_cons	0.2274	0.0156	0.0000
			p-value
F-test	441.24	F[38,1258]	0.000
AR(2)	-1.43		0.154
Hansen test	1004.96	χ^2 [918]	1.000
Significance of technical change	32.73	F[8,1258]	0.000
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE	0.048		1.000
N. instruments	1252		
N. groups	1259		

Table F7 – Cereals: East Germany. (Source: Own calculation)

East Germany	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_xM			
ln_yC	-0.3405	0.0276	0.0000
ln_yAOC	-0.1771	0.0166	0.0000
ln_yAOC	-0.3524	0.0164	0.0000
ln_xL	0.1085	0.0608	0.0750
ln_xW	0.1231	0.0413	0.0030
ln_xK	0.1670	0.0452	0.0000
ln_yC_2	-0.1425	0.0309	0.0000
ln_yAOC_2	-0.0648	0.0078	0.0000
ln_yAOC_2	-0.0594	0.0045	0.0000
ln_yCyAOC	-0.0049	0.0121	0.6850
ln_yCyAOC	0.0126	0.0138	0.3630
ln_yAOCyAOC	0.0503	0.0080	0.0000
ln_xL_2	0.0151	0.1961	0.9390
ln_xW_2	-0.1255	0.0817	0.1260
ln_xK_2	0.1338	0.0706	0.0590
ln_xLxW	0.3492	0.1080	0.0010
ln_xLxK	-0.1084	0.0952	0.2560
ln_xWxK	-0.0372	0.0609	0.5410
t	0.0060	0.0029	0.0410
t_2	0.0101	0.0008	0.0000
ln_yCt	-0.0086	0.0035	0.0150
ln_yAOCt	-0.0014	0.0021	0.5030
ln_yAOCt	0.0072	0.0017	0.0000
ln_xLt	0.0250	0.0084	0.0030
ln_xWt	-0.0131	0.0069	0.0570
ln_xKt	-0.0102	0.0056	0.0670
ln_yCxL	-0.0548	0.0579	0.3450
ln_yAOCxL	0.1234	0.0294	0.0000
ln_yAOCxL	0.1339	0.0354	0.0000
ln_yCxW	-0.1287	0.0362	0.0000
ln_yAOCxW	-0.0447	0.0194	0.0220
ln_yAOCxW	-0.0080	0.0212	0.7070
ln_yCxK	0.0341	0.0326	0.2970
ln_yAOCxK	0.0020	0.0202	0.9200
ln_yAOCxK	-0.0403	0.0224	0.0730
D2008	-0.0045	0.0151	0.7680
D2009	0.2223	0.0149	0.0000
DLFA	-0.0708	0.0168	0.0000
_cons	0.2542	0.0219	0.0000
			p-value
F-test	225.05	F[38,345]	0.000
AR(2)	-1.08		0.308
Hansen test	320.59	χ^2 [786]	1.000
Significance of technical change	22.54	F[8,345]	0.000
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE	0.3535		0.500
N. instruments	825		
N. groups	346		

Table F8 – Cereals: Ireland. (Source: Own calculation)

Ireland	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_xM			
ln_yC	-0.1388	0.0310	0.0000
ln_yAOC	-0.1053	0.0346	0.0030
ln_yAOO	-0.3400	0.0306	0.0000
ln_xL	0.2591	0.0826	0.0020
ln_xW	0.2926	0.0708	0.0000
ln_xK	0.0517	0.0528	0.3290
ln_yC_2	-0.0599	0.0409	0.1450
ln_yAOC_2	-0.0089	0.0273	0.7450
ln_yAOO_2	-0.1020	0.0260	0.0000
ln_yCyAOC	0.0387	0.0252	0.1270
ln_yCyAOO	0.0050	0.0309	0.8710
ln_yAOCyAOO	0.0473	0.0320	0.1410
ln_xL_2	-0.1785	0.3964	0.6530
ln_xW_2	0.1028	0.3487	0.7690
ln_xK_2	0.0467	0.1399	0.7390
ln_xLxW	0.1973	0.3847	0.6090
ln_xLxK	-0.0001	0.1933	1.0000
ln_xWxK	-0.0602	0.1468	0.6820
t	-0.0087	0.0049	0.0770
t_2	0.0052	0.0032	0.1060
ln_yCt	0.0018	0.0075	0.8060
ln_yAOCt	0.0108	0.0077	0.1590
ln_yAOOt	0.0111	0.0086	0.2010
ln_xLt	0.0133	0.0249	0.5940
ln_xWt	0.0251	0.0202	0.2170
ln_xKt	0.0039	0.0151	0.7980
ln_yCxL	-0.0484	0.0912	0.5960
ln_yAOCxL	0.0210	0.0823	0.7990
ln_yAOOxL	0.1165	0.1057	0.2720
ln_yCxW	0.0875	0.0845	0.3020
ln_yAOCxW	0.0991	0.0792	0.2120
ln_yAOOxW	-0.0643	0.0531	0.2280
ln_yCxK	0.0093	0.0649	0.8860
ln_yAOCxK	0.0104	0.0720	0.8860
ln_yAOOxK	0.0177	0.0524	0.7360
D2008	-0.1655	0.0568	0.0040
_cons	0.1159	0.0545	0.0350
			p-value
F-test	95.72	F[36,159]	0.000
AR(2)	-0.87		0.386
Hansen test	128.5	χ^2 [1226]	1.000
Significance of technical change	1.18	F[8,159]	0.316
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE	0.57		0.250
N. instruments	1263		
N. groups	160		

Table F9 – Cereals: Italy. (Source: Own calculation)

Italy	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
In_xM			
In_yC	-0.2247	0.0146	0.0000
In_yAOC	-0.2504	0.0132	0.0000
In_yAOO	-0.3547	0.0136	0.0000
In_xL	0.2087	0.0270	0.0000
In_xW	0.2452	0.0232	0.0000
In_xK	0.0748	0.0209	0.0000
In_yC_2	-0.1507	0.0171	0.0000
In_yAOC_2	-0.0783	0.0175	0.0000
In_yAOO_2	-0.0931	0.0128	0.0000
In_yCyAOC	0.0326	0.0134	0.0150
In_yCyAOO	0.0501	0.0148	0.0010
In_yAOCyAOO	0.0425	0.0137	0.0020
In_xL_2	-0.1024	0.0510	0.0450
In_xW_2	-0.0780	0.0676	0.2490
In_xK_2	0.0410	0.0299	0.1700
In_xLxW	0.0435	0.0413	0.2930
In_xLxK	0.0252	0.0267	0.3450
In_xWxK	0.0890	0.0280	0.0020
t	0.0012	0.0027	0.6450
t_2	0.0008	0.0011	0.4580
In_yCt	0.0042	0.0038	0.2750
In_yAOCt	0.0014	0.0028	0.6120
In_yAOOt	0.0097	0.0034	0.0040
In_xLt	-0.0032	0.0056	0.5680
In_xWt	0.0300	0.0063	0.0000
In_xKt	-0.0046	0.0044	0.2970
In_yCxL	0.0872	0.0209	0.0000
In_yAOCxL	-0.0228	0.0225	0.3120
In_yAOOxL	-0.0087	0.0235	0.7120
In_yCxW	-0.0526	0.0281	0.0620
In_yAOCxW	0.0246	0.0242	0.3100
In_yAOOxW	0.0015	0.0234	0.9500
In_yCxK	-0.0062	0.0163	0.7030
In_yAOCxK	0.0054	0.0164	0.7410
In_yAOOxK	0.0488	0.0200	0.0150
_cons	0.1394	0.0232	0.0000
			p-value
F-test	347.4	F[35,525]	0.000
AR(2)	0.29		0.771
Hansen test	510.02	χ^2 [1490]	1.000
Significance of technical change	3.31	F[8,525]	0.001
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE	7.24		0.003
N. instruments	1526		
N. groups	526		

Table F10 – Cereals: Romania. (Source: Own calculation)

Romania	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
In_xM			
In_yC	-0.2627	0.0132	0.0000
In_yAOC	-0.2378	0.0127	0.0000
In_yAOO	-0.2045	0.0124	0.0000
In_xL	0.2474	0.0237	0.0000
In_xW	0.2912	0.0209	0.0000
In_xK	0.0887	0.0108	0.0000
In_yC_2	-0.1236	0.0211	0.0000
In_yAOC_2	-0.0394	0.0136	0.0040
In_yAOO_2	-0.0339	0.0105	0.0010
In_yCyAOC	0.0506	0.0114	0.0000
In_yCyAOO	0.0568	0.0111	0.0000
In_yAOCyAOO	-0.0060	0.0091	0.5110
In_xL_2	-0.0043	0.0615	0.9450
In_xW_2	0.1813	0.0540	0.0010
In_xK_2	0.0174	0.0157	0.2670
In_xLxW	-0.0479	0.0454	0.2920
In_xLxK	0.0218	0.0272	0.4240
In_xWxK	0.0105	0.0215	0.6250
t	-0.0092	0.0040	0.0230
t_2	0.0126	0.0020	0.0000
In_yCt	-0.0063	0.0043	0.1420
In_yAOCt	0.0014	0.0037	0.6970
In_yAOOt	0.0080	0.0036	0.0260
In_xLt	0.0077	0.0076	0.3170
In_xWt	0.0219	0.0082	0.0080
In_xKt	0.0009	0.0046	0.8440
In_yCxL	0.0225	0.0278	0.4190
In_yAOCxL	-0.0088	0.0190	0.6430
In_yAOOxL	-0.0026	0.0191	0.8910
In_yCxW	0.0261	0.0261	0.3170
In_yAOCxW	0.0472	0.0174	0.0070
In_yAOOxW	0.0464	0.0188	0.0140
In_yCxK	0.0170	0.0109	0.1190
In_yAOCxK	-0.0171	0.0108	0.1150
In_yAOOxK	-0.0087	0.0115	0.4490
D2008	-0.2875	0.0467	0.0000
DLFA	-0.0453	0.0394	0.2500
_cons	0.1098	0.0167	0.0000
			p-value
F-test	515.06	F[37,452]	0.000
AR(2)	-1.63		0.104
Hansen test	435.75	χ^2 [703]	1.000
Significance of technical change	6.58	F[8,452]	0.000
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE	7.95		0.001
N. instruments	741		
N. groups	453		

Table F11 – Cereals: Spain. (Source: Own calculation)

Spain	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
In_xM			
In_yC	-0.2524	0.0232	0.0000
In_yAOC	-0.0894	0.0202	0.0000
In_yAOO	-0.3231	0.0245	0.0000
In_xL	0.1507	0.0296	0.0000
In_xW	0.2703	0.0336	0.0000
In_xK	0.0757	0.0257	0.0040
In_yC_2	-0.0867	0.0236	0.0000
In_yAOC_2	-0.0344	0.0224	0.1270
In_yAOO_2	-0.1039	0.0198	0.0000
In_yCyAOC	-0.0144	0.0240	0.5470
In_yCyAOO	0.0367	0.0217	0.0910
In_yAOCyAOO	0.0267	0.0209	0.2030
In_xL_2	-0.1129	0.0619	0.0690
In_xW_2	-0.0466	0.1183	0.6940
In_xK_2	0.0506	0.0275	0.0670
In_xLxW	0.0436	0.0521	0.4040
In_xLxK	0.1007	0.0342	0.0030
In_xWxK	0.0136	0.0366	0.7110
t	-0.0046	0.0037	0.2140
t_2	0.0050	0.0012	0.0000
In_yCt	0.0087	0.0050	0.0860
In_yAOCt	-0.0017	0.0039	0.6640
In_yAOOt	0.0010	0.0033	0.7530
In_xLt	-0.0032	0.0058	0.5840
In_xWt	-0.0013	0.0085	0.8800
In_xKt	0.0101	0.0066	0.1300
In_yCxL	0.0502	0.0252	0.0470
In_yAOCxL	0.0178	0.0244	0.4670
In_yAOOxL	0.0134	0.0291	0.6460
In_yCxW	-0.0393	0.0375	0.2960
In_yAOCxW	-0.0252	0.0397	0.5260
In_yAOOxW	-0.0579	0.0315	0.0670
In_yCxK	0.0066	0.0265	0.8040
In_yAOCxK	0.0046	0.0166	0.7830
In_yAOOxK	0.0598	0.0217	0.0060
D2008	0.0300	0.0238	0.2080
DLFA	0.0796	0.0236	0.0010
_cons	0.1172	0.0394	0.0030
			p-value
F-test	87.89	F[37,274]	0.000
AR(2)	-1.90		0.057
Hansen test	248.88	χ^2 [285]	0.940
Significance of technical change	4.77	F[8,274]	0.000
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE			
N. instruments	323		
N. groups	275		

Table F12 – Cereals: Sweden. (Source: Own calculation)

Sweden	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_xM			
ln_yC	-0.1910	0.0107	0.0000
ln_yAOC	-0.2461	0.0126	0.0000
ln_yAOO	-0.3333	0.0115	0.0000
ln_xL	0.1496	0.0230	0.0000
ln_xW	0.2867	0.0282	0.0000
ln_xK	0.0895	0.0137	0.0000
ln_yC_2	-0.1216	0.0150	0.0000
ln_yAOC_2	-0.0728	0.0074	0.0000
ln_yAOO_2	-0.0845	0.0070	0.0000
ln_yCyAOC	0.0535	0.0102	0.0000
ln_yCyAOO	0.0459	0.0093	0.0000
ln_yAOCyAOO	-0.0075	0.0068	0.2720
ln_xL_2	-0.2413	0.0832	0.0040
ln_xW_2	-0.0414	0.0756	0.5840
ln_xK_2	-0.0133	0.0420	0.7510
ln_xLxW	0.1531	0.0586	0.0090
ln_xLxK	0.0437	0.0451	0.3330
ln_xWxK	-0.0084	0.0309	0.7860
t	0.0111	0.0018	0.0000
t_2	0.0029	0.0008	0.0000
ln_yCt	0.0002	0.0019	0.9170
ln_yAOCt	-0.0073	0.0022	0.0010
ln_yAOOt	0.0065	0.0020	0.0010
ln_xLt	0.0069	0.0057	0.2240
ln_xWt	-0.0047	0.0050	0.3520
ln_xKt	-0.0090	0.0040	0.0230
ln_yCxL	0.0930	0.0266	0.0010
ln_yAOCxL	-0.0759	0.0223	0.0010
ln_yAOOxL	-0.0405	0.0226	0.0740
ln_yCxW	-0.0408	0.0259	0.1160
ln_yAOCxW	0.0128	0.0189	0.5000
ln_yAOOxW	0.0730	0.0174	0.0000
ln_yCxK	0.0040	0.0139	0.7730
ln_yAOCxK	0.0151	0.0159	0.3430
ln_yAOOxK	0.0032	0.0152	0.8330
D2008	-0.0347	0.0147	0.0180
DLFA	-0.1861	0.0231	0.0000
_cons	0.2463	0.0184	0.0000
			p-value
F-test	421.87	F[37,544]	0.000
AR(2)	-1.15		0.252
Hansen test	513.63	χ^2 [1370]	1.000
Significance of technical change	15.14	F[8,544]	0.000
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE	0.444		0.300
N. instruments	1408		
N. groups	545		

Table F13 – Cereals: United Kingdom. (Source: Own calculation)

United Kingdom	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_xM			
ln_yC	-0.1954	0.0209	0.0000
ln_yAOC	-0.1546	0.0184	0.0000
ln_yAOO	-0.3798	0.0244	0.0000
ln_xL	0.1122	0.0420	0.0080
ln_xW	0.2821	0.0499	0.0000
ln_xK	0.0920	0.0314	0.0040
ln_yC_2	-0.0576	0.0265	0.0310
ln_yAOC_2	-0.0591	0.0172	0.0010
ln_yAOO_2	-0.0651	0.0186	0.0010
ln_yCyAOC	-0.0108	0.0198	0.5860
ln_yCyAOO	0.0920	0.0220	0.0000
ln_yAOCyAOO	0.0345	0.0198	0.0830
ln_xL_2	-0.0556	0.0947	0.5570
ln_xW_2	-0.0036	0.1505	0.9810
ln_xK_2	0.0642	0.0665	0.3350
ln_xLxW	0.1762	0.0924	0.0570
ln_xLxK	0.0285	0.0694	0.6820
ln_xWxK	-0.0058	0.0828	0.9440
t	-0.0014	0.0026	0.5910
t_2	0.0042	0.0012	0.0000
ln_yCt	0.0087	0.0036	0.0170
ln_yAOCt	-0.0026	0.0044	0.5580
ln_yAOOt	0.0038	0.0044	0.3900
ln_xLt	0.0097	0.0073	0.1840
ln_xWt	-0.0031	0.0076	0.6850
ln_xKt	0.0017	0.0058	0.7650
ln_yCxL	0.0166	0.0423	0.6940
ln_yAOCxL	0.0337	0.0343	0.3270
ln_yAOOxL	0.0485	0.0475	0.3080
ln_yCxW	0.0321	0.0480	0.5040
ln_yAOCxW	-0.0096	0.0485	0.8430
ln_yAOOxW	0.0089	0.0420	0.8330
ln_yCxK	0.0082	0.0313	0.7940
ln_yAOCxK	0.0320	0.0299	0.2850
ln_yAOOxK	-0.0334	0.0307	0.2770
D2008	-0.0771	0.0304	0.0120
DLFA	-0.1252	0.0511	0.0150
_cons	0.1436	0.0280	0.0000
			p-value
F-test	1925.86	F[37,341]	0.000
AR(2)	-1.30		0.192
Hansen test	269.26	χ^2 [265]	0.416
Significance of technical change	6.93	F[8,341]	0.000
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE	12.87		0.000
N. instruments	303		
N. groups	342		

AGRICULTURE - CEREALS: DEVELOPMENT OF TRANSIENT TECHNICAL EFFICIENCY

Figure C1a – Cereals: Development of transient technical efficiency (part 1). (Source: Own calculation)

Figure C1b – Cereals: Development of transient technical efficiency (part 2). (Source: Own calculation)

AGRICULTURE - CEREALS: META-FRONTIER MODEL ESTIMATES

Table G1 – Cereals: Meta-frontier model estimates. (Source: Own calculation)

ln_xM	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t	
ln_yC	-0.2556	0.0063	0.0000	
ln_yAOC	-0.0900	0.0035	0.0000	
ln_yAOC	-0.3036	0.0047	0.0000	
ln_xL	0.1958	0.0112	0.0000	
ln_xW	0.2219	0.0089	0.0000	
ln_xK	0.0826	0.0066	0.0000	
ln_yC_2	-0.1120	0.0121	0.0000	
ln_yAOC_2	-0.0215	0.0034	0.0000	
ln_yAOC_2	-0.0767	0.0037	0.0000	
ln_yCyAOC	0.0047	0.0050	0.3460	
ln_yCyAOC	0.0214	0.0053	0.0000	
ln_yAOCyAOC	0.0156	0.0027	0.0000	
ln_xL_2	-0.1412	0.0361	0.0000	
ln_xW_2	-0.0561	0.0322	0.0820	
ln_xK_2	0.0237	0.0150	0.1140	
ln_xLxW	0.0862	0.0289	0.0030	
ln_xLxK	0.0693	0.0171	0.0000	
ln_xWxK	-0.0279	0.0168	0.0970	
t	0.0043	0.0005	0.0000	
t_2	0.0037	0.0002	0.0000	
ln_yCt	-0.0003	0.0008	0.6690	
ln_yAOCt	-0.0009	0.0005	0.0520	
ln_yAOCt	0.0019	0.0005	0.0000	
ln_xLt	0.0004	0.0016	0.8210	
ln_xWt	0.0052	0.0015	0.0010	
ln_xKt	-0.0023	0.0013	0.0860	
ln_yCxL	0.0696	0.0180	0.0000	
ln_yAOCxL	0.0165	0.0095	0.0830	
ln_yAOCxL	-0.0598	0.0106	0.0000	
ln_yCxW	-0.0566	0.0154	0.0000	
ln_yAOCxW	-0.0277	0.0082	0.0010	
ln_yAOCxW	0.0288	0.0089	0.0010	
ln_yCxK	-0.0179	0.0094	0.0570	
ln_yAOCxK	0.0041	0.0072	0.5720	
ln_yAOCxK	0.0227	0.0072	0.0020	
D2015	0.0308	0.0025	0.0000	
DLFA	-0.1302	0.0162	0.0000	
_cons	0.2034	0.0107	0.0000	
			p-value	
F-test	1408.32	F[37,8102]	0.000	
Technical efficiency				
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Overall	0.9471	0.0123	0.7850	0.9889
Persistent	0.9985	0.0000	0.9984	0.9985
Transient	0.9486	0.0124	0.7863	0.9904

AGRICULTURE - CEREALS: META-FRONTIER TRANSIENT TECHNICAL EFFICIENCY

Table H1 – Cereals: Meta-frontier transient technical efficiency. (Source: Own calculation)

Country	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max
Austria	0.9486	0.0120	0.8511	0.9891
Belgium	0.9489	0.0116	0.8669	0.9763
Czechia	0.9492	0.0111	0.8465	0.9853
Finland	0.9478	0.0177	0.8122	0.9860
France	0.9488	0.0112	0.8473	0.9904
West Germany	0.9491	0.0110	0.8010	0.9871
East Germany	0.9485	0.0100	0.8731	0.9798
Ireland	0.9485	0.0113	0.8502	0.9758
Italy	0.9470	0.0164	0.8382	0.9829
Romania	0.9472	0.0167	0.7863	0.9819
Spain	0.9477	0.0159	0.8225	0.9786
Sweden	0.9486	0.0115	0.8239	0.9826
United Kingdom	0.9490	0.0092	0.8870	0.9755

AGRICULTURE - MILK: COUNTRY INPUT DISTANCE FUNCTION ESTIMATES

Table 11 – Milk: Austria. (Source: Own calculation)

Austria	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_xM			
ln_yC	-0.3037	0.0137	0.0000
ln_yAOC	-0.1564	0.0109	0.0000
ln_yAOC	-0.1645	0.0068	0.0000
ln_xL	0.1435	0.0262	0.0000
ln_xW	0.3351	0.0211	0.0000
ln_xK	0.1995	0.0226	0.0000
ln_yC_2	-0.0891	0.0135	0.0000
ln_yAOC_2	-0.0666	0.0141	0.0000
ln_yAOC_2	-0.0534	0.0096	0.0000
ln_yCyAOC	0.0570	0.0122	0.0000
ln_yCyAOC	0.0382	0.0105	0.0000
ln_yAOCyAOC	-0.0032	0.0106	0.7670
ln_xL_2	-0.2012	0.0583	0.0010
ln_xW_2	0.1302	0.0610	0.0330
ln_xK_2	0.1295	0.0866	0.1350
ln_xLxW	0.1095	0.0593	0.0650
ln_xLxK	0.0582	0.0455	0.2010
ln_xWxK	-0.0753	0.0656	0.2520
t	-0.0009	0.0009	0.3100
t_2	0.0018	0.0004	0.0000
ln_yCt	-0.0021	0.0016	0.1990
ln_yAOCt	0.0017	0.0017	0.3090
ln_yAOCt	0.0009	0.0010	0.3720
ln_xLt	-0.0129	0.0045	0.0040
ln_xWt	0.0009	0.0029	0.7620
ln_xKt	0.0110	0.0032	0.0010
ln_yCxL	0.0490	0.0277	0.0770
ln_yAOCxL	-0.0093	0.0283	0.7430
ln_yAOCxL	0.0157	0.0221	0.4780
ln_yCxW	0.0173	0.0205	0.3980
ln_yAOCxW	0.0127	0.0217	0.5580
ln_yAOCxW	0.0194	0.0181	0.2820
ln_yCxK	-0.0005	0.0304	0.9880
ln_yAOCxK	-0.0107	0.0316	0.7360
ln_yAOCxK	0.0251	0.0203	0.2160
D2014	-0.0119	0.0049	0.0140
D2010	0.0100	0.0048	0.0360
DLFA	-0.0745	0.0157	0.0000
_cons	0.1236	0.0179	0.0000
			p-value
F-test	463.95	F[38,1085]	0.000
AR(2)	-1.52		0.128
Hansen test	915.71	χ^2 [848]	0.053
Significance of technical change	7.52	F[8,1085]	0.000
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE	0.17		1.000
N. instruments	887		
N. groups	1086		

Table I2 – Milk: Belgium. (Source: Own calculation)

Belgium	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
In_xM			
In_yC	-0.3194	0.0168	0.0000
In_yAOC	-0.2057	0.0116	0.0000
In_yAOC	-0.1585	0.0084	0.0000
In_xL	0.0704	0.0303	0.0200
In_xW	0.3691	0.0320	0.0000
In_xK	0.1707	0.0240	0.0000
In_yC_2	-0.1052	0.0131	0.0000
In_yAOC_2	-0.1120	0.0155	0.0000
In_yAOC_2	-0.0470	0.0051	0.0000
In_yCyAOC	0.0569	0.0148	0.0000
In_yCyAOC	0.0166	0.0078	0.0330
In_yAOCyAOC	0.0237	0.0074	0.0010
In_xL_2	-0.0453	0.0773	0.5580
In_xW_2	-0.0858	0.0821	0.2970
In_xK_2	0.0496	0.0876	0.5720
In_xLxW	0.0456	0.0610	0.4560
In_xLxK	0.0498	0.0678	0.4630
In_xWxK	-0.0500	0.0769	0.5160
t	-0.0076	0.0014	0.0000
t_2	0.0038	0.0006	0.0000
In_yCt	0.0022	0.0027	0.4090
In_yAOCt	-0.0015	0.0020	0.4610
In_yAOCt	0.0018	0.0011	0.1030
In_xLt	0.0018	0.0037	0.6230
In_xWt	-0.0043	0.0054	0.4320
In_xKt	-0.0093	0.0049	0.0590
In_yCxL	0.0169	0.0423	0.6900
In_yAOCxL	0.0178	0.0281	0.5270
In_yAOCxL	-0.0410	0.0123	0.0010
In_yCxW	0.0184	0.0320	0.5650
In_yAOCxW	-0.0016	0.0324	0.9600
In_yAOCxW	0.0217	0.0160	0.1770
In_yCxK	0.0250	0.0355	0.4810
In_yAOCxK	-0.0140	0.0319	0.6620
In_yAOCxK	0.0086	0.0158	0.5890
D2008	-0.0602	0.0129	0.0000
D2009	0.0793	0.0091	0.0000
DLFA	-0.1598	0.0247	0.0000
_cons	0.1488	0.0166	0.0000
			p-value
F-test	225.09	F[38,404]	0.000
AR(3)	-1.59		0.112
Hansen test	373.14	χ^2 [1205]	1.000
Significance of technical change	11.27	F[8,404]	0.000
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE	97.21		0.000
N. instruments	1244		
N. groups	405		

Table 13 – Milk: Czechia. (Source: Own calculation)

Czechia	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_xM			
ln_yC	-0.3328	0.0199	0.0000
ln_yAOC	-0.1632	0.0147	0.0000
ln_yAOO	-0.4583	0.0157	0.0000
ln_xL	0.1184	0.0496	0.0170
ln_xW	0.3195	0.0466	0.0000
ln_xK	0.0759	0.0215	0.0000
ln_yC_2	-0.1004	0.0174	0.0000
ln_yAOC_2	-0.0579	0.0202	0.0040
ln_yAOO_2	-0.1244	0.0181	0.0000
ln_yCyAOC	-0.0023	0.0188	0.9030
ln_yCyAOO	0.0543	0.0110	0.0000
ln_yAOCyAOO	0.0750	0.0152	0.0000
ln_xL_2	-0.1068	0.0805	0.1850
ln_xW_2	0.2139	0.1421	0.1330
ln_xK_2	-0.0247	0.0473	0.6020
ln_xLxW	-0.0993	0.1268	0.4340
ln_xLxK	-0.1134	0.0651	0.0820
ln_xWxK	0.1481	0.0613	0.0160
t	0.0125	0.0023	0.0000
t_2	0.0053	0.0010	0.0000
ln_yCt	-0.0032	0.0030	0.2810
ln_yAOCt	-0.0019	0.0029	0.5080
ln_yAOOt	0.0062	0.0030	0.0400
ln_xLt	-0.0187	0.0083	0.0250
ln_xWt	0.0015	0.0077	0.8450
ln_xKt	-0.0008	0.0035	0.8150
ln_yCxL	0.0225	0.0481	0.6390
ln_yAOCxL	-0.0830	0.0572	0.1470
ln_yAOOxL	0.0315	0.0429	0.4640
ln_yCxW	-0.0487	0.0373	0.1920
ln_yAOCxW	0.0440	0.0448	0.3260
ln_yAOOxW	-0.0061	0.0469	0.8970
ln_yCxK	-0.0254	0.0235	0.2810
ln_yAOCxK	-0.0228	0.0204	0.2630
ln_yAOOxK	0.0546	0.0208	0.0090
D2010	0.1191	0.0086	0.0000
D2014	-0.0243	0.0076	0.0010
DLFA	-0.0932	0.0186	0.0000
_cons	0.0860	0.0248	0.0010
			p-value
F-test	1482.64	F[38,499]	0.000
AR(2)	-0.02		0.983
Hansen test	484.69	χ^2 [672]	0.139
Significance of technical change	45.79	F[8,499]	0.000
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE	79.47		0.000
N. instruments	711		
N. groups	500		

Table 14 – Milk: Finland. (Source: Own calculation)

Finland	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
In_xM			
In_yC	-0.5298	0.0217	0.0000
In_yAOC	-0.0873	0.0159	0.0000
In_yAOC	-0.1447	0.0088	0.0000
In_xL	0.0994	0.0238	0.0000
In_xW	0.2554	0.0246	0.0000
In_xK	0.0741	0.0174	0.0000
In_yC_2	-0.0961	0.0549	0.0810
In_yAOC_2	-0.0886	0.0226	0.0000
In_yAOC_2	-0.0562	0.0094	0.0000
In_yCyAOC	0.0236	0.0281	0.4020
In_yCyAOC	-0.0172	0.0276	0.5340
In_yAOCyAOC	0.0321	0.0161	0.0470
In_xL_2	-0.1600	0.0945	0.0910
In_xW_2	-0.0737	0.0866	0.3960
In_xK_2	-0.0177	0.0512	0.7290
In_xLxW	0.1378	0.0664	0.0390
In_xLxK	0.0126	0.0575	0.8270
In_xWxK	-0.0521	0.0475	0.2730
t	0.0132	0.0017	0.0000
t_2	0.0030	0.0007	0.0000
In_yCt	0.0132	0.0051	0.0090
In_yAOCt	-0.0022	0.0033	0.4950
In_yAOCt	-0.0032	0.0021	0.1320
In_xLt	0.0093	0.0054	0.0850
In_xWt	-0.0060	0.0052	0.2510
In_xKt	-0.0082	0.0047	0.0840
In_yCxL	0.0400	0.0588	0.4960
In_yAOCxL	-0.0167	0.0319	0.6020
In_yAOCxL	-0.0615	0.0183	0.0010
In_yCxW	-0.0003	0.0519	0.9950
In_yAOCxW	-0.0453	0.0329	0.1700
In_yAOCxW	0.0050	0.0184	0.7870
In_yCxK	-0.0628	0.0654	0.3370
In_yAOCxK	0.0690	0.0312	0.0280
In_yAOCxK	0.0494	0.0184	0.0070
D2015	0.0319	0.0074	0.0000
D2010	0.0936	0.0108	0.0000
D2006	0.0287	0.0093	0.0020
DLFA	-0.0552	0.1653	0.7390
_cons	0.1078	0.1664	0.5170
			p-value
F-test	330.79	F[39,384]	
AR(2)	0.91		0.363
Hansen test	367.13	χ^2 [1480]	1.000
Significance of technical change	19.03	F[8,384]	0.000
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE	19.16		0.000
N. instruments	1520		
N. groups	385		

Table 15 – Milk: France. (Source: Own calculation)

France	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
In_xM			
In_yC	-0.4922	0.0088	0.0000
In_yAOC	-0.1710	0.0054	0.0000
In_yAOC	-0.1760	0.0047	0.0000
In_xL	0.0531	0.0126	0.0000
In_xW	0.2168	0.0103	0.0000
In_xK	0.2477	0.0109	0.0000
In_yC_2	-0.1846	0.0121	0.0000
In_yAOC_2	-0.0884	0.0082	0.0000
In_yAOC_2	-0.0413	0.0022	0.0000
In_yCyAOC	0.0353	0.0116	0.0020
In_yCyAOC	0.0249	0.0046	0.0000
In_yAOCyAOC	0.0130	0.0041	0.0020
In_xL_2	-0.0278	0.0570	0.6260
In_xW_2	0.0239	0.0578	0.6790
In_xK_2	0.1634	0.0450	0.0000
In_xLxW	0.0821	0.0352	0.0200
In_xLxK	-0.0829	0.0375	0.0270
In_xWxK	-0.0438	0.0362	0.2270
t	-0.0009	0.0006	0.1140
t_2	0.0020	0.0002	0.0000
In_yCt	0.0023	0.0011	0.0420
In_yAOCt	0.0030	0.0008	0.0000
In_yAOCt	-0.0008	0.0005	0.0750
In_xLt	-0.0026	0.0016	0.1080
In_xWt	0.0017	0.0020	0.3860
In_xKt	0.0038	0.0020	0.0590
In_yCxL	0.0368	0.0305	0.2270
In_yAOCxL	0.0010	0.0179	0.9560
In_yAOCxL	-0.0074	0.0095	0.4360
In_yCxW	-0.0473	0.0248	0.0570
In_yAOCxW	-0.0306	0.0175	0.0820
In_yAOCxW	0.0318	0.0098	0.0010
In_yCxK	-0.0136	0.0225	0.5460
In_yAOCxK	0.0601	0.0163	0.0000
In_yAOCxK	-0.0079	0.0076	0.3010
D2015	0.0341	0.0035	0.0000
D2010	0.0771	0.0034	0.0000
DLFA	-0.1500	0.0158	0.0000
_cons	0.1299	0.0078	0.0000
			p-value
F-test	917.01	F[38,1701]	0.000
AR(3)	0.55		0.579
Hansen test	1573.33	χ^2 [1500]	0.092
Significance of technical change	16.08	F[8,1701]	0.000
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE	262.02		0.000
N. instruments	1539		
N. groups	1702		

Table 16 – Milk: West Germany. (Source: Own calculation)

West Germany	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
ln_xM			
ln_yC	-0.3985	0.0111	0.0000
ln_yAOC	-0.1603	0.0106	0.0000
ln_yAOO	-0.1800	0.0083	0.0000
ln_xL	0.0827	0.0283	0.0040
ln_xW	0.2991	0.0262	0.0000
ln_xK	0.0994	0.0156	0.0000
ln_yC_2	-0.1138	0.0090	0.0000
ln_yAOC_2	-0.1046	0.0140	0.0000
ln_yAOO_2	-0.0645	0.0089	0.0000
ln_yCyAOC	-0.0043	0.0125	0.7330
ln_yCyAOO	0.0284	0.0118	0.0160
ln_yAOCyAOO	0.0054	0.0107	0.6140
ln_xL_2	-0.3493	0.1143	0.0020
ln_xW_2	0.1668	0.0893	0.0620
ln_xK_2	0.0342	0.0327	0.2960
ln_xLxW	0.0453	0.0796	0.5690
ln_xLxK	0.0739	0.0543	0.1730
ln_xWxK	-0.0574	0.0466	0.2190
t	0.0288	0.0076	0.0000
t_2	0.0022	0.0019	0.2310
ln_yCt	-0.0054	0.0023	0.0200
ln_yAOCt	-0.0019	0.0024	0.4290
ln_yAOOt	-0.0009	0.0015	0.5610
ln_xLt	0.0015	0.0072	0.8330
ln_xWt	-0.0053	0.0047	0.2610
ln_xKt	0.0052	0.0037	0.1600
ln_yCxL	0.0226	0.0331	0.4940
ln_yAOCxL	0.0141	0.0360	0.6950
ln_yAOOxL	-0.0050	0.0164	0.7580
ln_yCxW	0.0422	0.0307	0.1700
ln_yAOCxW	-0.0623	0.0350	0.0750
ln_yAOOxW	0.0225	0.0202	0.2660
ln_yCxK	-0.0031	0.0220	0.8860
ln_yAOCxK	0.0112	0.0202	0.5790
ln_yAOOxK	0.0073	0.0127	0.5680
D2014	-0.0504	0.0076	0.0000
D2010	0.1197	0.0111	0.0000
D2009	0.2093	0.0199	0.0000
_cons	0.0317	0.0174	0.0680
			p-value
F-test	772.56	F[38,1517]	0.000
AR(2)	-0.36		0.722
Hansen test	959.22	χ^2 [897]	0.073
Significance of technical change	43.27	F[8,1517]	0.000
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE	1.763		0.100
N. instruments	936		
N. groups	1518		

Table 17 – Milk: East Germany. (Source: Own calculation)

East Germany	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
In_xM			
In_yC	-0.4385	0.0240	0.0000
In_yAOC	-0.1333	0.0131	0.0000
In_yAOO	-0.3804	0.0167	0.0000
In_xL	0.0536	0.0528	0.3110
In_xW	0.1827	0.0503	0.0000
In_xK	0.1871	0.0265	0.0000
In_yC_2	-0.1517	0.0291	0.0000
In_yAOC_2	-0.0837	0.0169	0.0000
In_yAOO_2	-0.1217	0.0223	0.0000
In_yCyAOC	0.0689	0.0204	0.0010
In_yCyAOO	0.0679	0.0220	0.0020
In_yAOCyAOO	0.0297	0.0181	0.1010
In_xL_2	-0.1197	0.1609	0.4570
In_xW_2	0.1229	0.1185	0.3000
In_xK_2	0.1470	0.1159	0.2060
In_xLxW	-0.0137	0.1142	0.9050
In_xLxK	-0.0209	0.1054	0.8430
In_xWxK	-0.0568	0.1072	0.5960
t	-0.0487	0.0066	0.0000
t_2	0.0200	0.0020	0.0000
In_yCt	0.0024	0.0045	0.5970
In_yAOCt	-0.0013	0.0030	0.6640
In_yAOOt	0.0014	0.0031	0.6460
In_xLt	-0.0076	0.0086	0.3740
In_xWt	0.0186	0.0086	0.0310
In_xKt	-0.0041	0.0071	0.5580
In_yCxL	0.0247	0.0559	0.6590
In_yAOCxL	0.0463	0.0390	0.2350
In_yAOOxL	-0.0788	0.0536	0.1420
In_yCxW	-0.0554	0.0530	0.2970
In_yAOCxW	-0.1017	0.0437	0.0200
In_yAOOxW	0.1301	0.0436	0.0030
In_yCxK	0.1476	0.0504	0.0040
In_yAOCxK	0.0012	0.0339	0.9710
In_yAOOxK	-0.0779	0.0360	0.0310
D2010	-0.0290	0.0101	0.0040
D2011	-0.1200	0.0105	0.0000
DLFA	-0.1055	0.0157	0.0000
_cons	0.2156	0.0201	0.0000
			p-value
F-test	1314.68	F[39,413]	0.000
AR(2)	0.720		0.468
Hansen test	353.36	χ^2 [465]	1.000
Significance of technical change	17.08	F[8,413]	0.000
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE	-0.001		1.000
N. instruments	505		
N. groups	414		

Table 18 – Milk: Ireland. (Source: Own calculation)

Ireland	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
In_xM			
In_yC	-0.4135	0.0193	0.0000
In_yAOC	-0.2236	0.0128	0.0000
In_yAOO	-0.1309	0.0114	0.0000
In_xL	0.2208	0.0214	0.0000
In_xW	0.1785	0.0217	0.0000
In_xK	0.0746	0.0166	0.0000
In_yC_2	-0.1531	0.0484	0.0020
In_yAOC_2	-0.1036	0.0163	0.0000
In_yAOO_2	-0.0402	0.0075	0.0000
In_yCyAOC	0.0603	0.0241	0.0130
In_yCyAOO	-0.0010	0.0178	0.9560
In_yAOCyAOO	0.0101	0.0121	0.4040
In_xL_2	-0.1967	0.1023	0.0550
In_xW_2	0.0410	0.0975	0.6740
In_xK_2	-0.0476	0.0538	0.3780
In_xLxW	0.1743	0.0726	0.0170
In_xLxK	0.0789	0.0553	0.1540
In_xWxK	-0.0568	0.0564	0.3150
t	0.0095	0.0016	0.0000
t_2	0.0045	0.0007	0.0000
In_yCt	0.0036	0.0037	0.3340
In_yAOCt	0.0066	0.0027	0.0140
In_yAOOt	-0.0052	0.0024	0.0320
In_xLt	-0.0049	0.0056	0.3830
In_xWt	0.0106	0.0054	0.0490
In_xKt	0.0050	0.0051	0.3270
In_yCxL	0.1072	0.0532	0.0450
In_yAOCxL	0.0307	0.0295	0.2980
In_yAOOxL	0.0168	0.0224	0.4550
In_yCxW	-0.0467	0.0495	0.3460
In_yAOCxW	-0.0045	0.0344	0.8950
In_yAOOxW	-0.0176	0.0206	0.3930
In_yCxK	-0.0216	0.0427	0.6130
In_yAOCxK	0.0058	0.0238	0.8070
In_yAOOxK	-0.0215	0.0212	0.3110
D2015	0.0974	0.0065	0.0000
D2010	0.0110	0.0081	0.1760
D2006	-0.0202	0.0131	0.1240
DLFA	-0.0657	0.0141	0.0000
_cons	0.0863	0.0140	0.0000
			p-value
F-test	395.65	F[39,362]	0.000
AR(2)	-0.62		0.536
Hansen test	370.8	χ^2 [1570]	1.000
Significance of technical change	15.68	F[8,362]	0.000
Log-Likelihood test: $\sigma_{\eta} = 0$ for PTE	58.69		0.000
N. instruments	1610		
N. groups	363		

Table 19 – Milk: Italy. (Source: Own calculation)

Italy	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
In_xM			
In_yC	-0.3715	0.0145	0.0000
In_yAOC	-0.0871	0.0133	0.0000
In_yAOO	-0.2763	0.0177	0.0000
In_xL	0.1536	0.0182	0.0000
In_xW	0.3197	0.0239	0.0000
In_xK	0.1112	0.0163	0.0000
In_yC_2	-0.1160	0.0141	0.0000
In_yAOC_2	-0.0384	0.0110	0.0000
In_yAOO_2	-0.0654	0.0221	0.0030
In_yCyAOC	0.0567	0.0121	0.0000
In_yCyAOO	0.0188	0.0154	0.2240
In_yAOCyAOO	0.0034	0.0116	0.7670
In_xL_2	-0.0730	0.0268	0.0070
In_xW_2	0.1534	0.0608	0.0120
In_xK_2	0.0402	0.0129	0.0020
In_xLxW	-0.0254	0.0311	0.4140
In_xLxK	-0.0066	0.0124	0.5940
In_xWxK	0.0175	0.0243	0.4700
t	0.0044	0.0018	0.0160
t_2	0.0005	0.0008	0.5100
In_yCt	0.0013	0.0030	0.6770
In_yAOCt	-0.0053	0.0025	0.0350
In_yAOOt	0.0091	0.0028	0.0010
In_xLt	-0.0130	0.0035	0.0000
In_xWt	0.0189	0.0051	0.0000
In_xKt	-0.0066	0.0025	0.0070
In_yCxL	-0.0412	0.0164	0.0120
In_yAOCxL	-0.0088	0.0139	0.5270
In_yAOOxL	0.0176	0.0158	0.2670
In_yCxW	0.0063	0.0277	0.8190
In_yAOCxW	0.0510	0.0210	0.0150
In_yAOOxW	-0.0352	0.0328	0.2820
In_yCxK	0.0207	0.0140	0.1400
In_yAOCxK	0.0036	0.0126	0.7740
In_yAOOxK	-0.0048	0.0134	0.7210
D2015	0.0226	0.0116	0.0520
D2010	0.1005	0.0097	0.0000
D2006	-0.0651	0.0149	0.0000
DLFA	-0.1349	0.0157	0.0000
_cons	0.1165	0.0158	0.0000
			p-value
F-test	677.62	F[39,1054]	0.000
AR(2)	-0.37		0.712
Hansen test	1035.43	χ^2 [1019]	0.353
Significance of technical change	5.22	F[8,1054]	0.000
Log-Likelihood test: $\sigma_{\eta} = 0$ for PTE	4.06		0.025
N. instruments	1059		
N. groups	1055		

Table I10 – Milk: Romania. (Source: Own calculation)

Romania	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
In_xM			
In_yC	-0.1349	0.0244	0.0000
In_yAOC	-0.1002	0.0228	0.0000
In_yAOC	-0.4258	0.0309	0.0000
In_xL	0.2160	0.0358	0.0000
In_xW	0.3259	0.0364	0.0000
In_xK	0.1031	0.0213	0.0000
In_yC_2	-0.0347	0.0293	0.2370
In_yAOC_2	-0.0260	0.0156	0.0970
In_yAOC_2	0.0013	0.0525	0.9810
In_yCyAOC	0.0185	0.0155	0.2340
In_yCyAOC	-0.0233	0.0271	0.3920
In_yAOCyAOC	0.0046	0.0285	0.8720
In_xL_2	0.0945	0.1021	0.3560
In_xW_2	0.1738	0.0866	0.0460
In_xK_2	0.0266	0.0288	0.3560
In_xLxW	-0.0800	0.0787	0.3110
In_xLxK	0.0431	0.0346	0.2140
In_xWxK	-0.0225	0.0382	0.5570
t	-0.0015	0.0079	0.8510
t_2	0.0085	0.0041	0.0380
In_yCt	0.0036	0.0065	0.5800
In_yAOCt	0.0072	0.0072	0.3190
In_yAOCt	-0.0149	0.0087	0.0870
In_xLt	0.0083	0.0142	0.5560
In_xWt	0.0024	0.0120	0.8440
In_xKt	0.0014	0.0076	0.8510
In_yCxL	0.0685	0.0299	0.0230
In_yAOCxL	-0.0311	0.0322	0.3360
In_yAOCxL	-0.0677	0.0579	0.2440
In_yCxW	0.0164	0.0331	0.6210
In_yAOCxW	0.0120	0.0360	0.7390
In_yAOCxW	0.0664	0.0568	0.2430
In_yCxK	-0.0151	0.0191	0.4300
In_yAOCxK	0.0243	0.0213	0.2570
In_yAOCxK	-0.0276	0.0241	0.2540
D2014	0.1228	0.0241	0.0000
D2009	0.0441	0.0601	0.4640
_cons	0.0232	0.0279	0.4060
			p-value
F-test	251.87	F[37,218]	0.000
AR(2)	-1.59		0.112
Hansen test	193.41	χ^2 [924]	1.000
Significance of technical change	1.68	F[8,218]	0.106
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE	0.41		0.300
N. instruments	962		
N. groups	219		

Table III – Milk: Spain. (Source: Own calculation)

Spain	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
In_xM			
In_yC	-0.6928	0.0170	0.0000
In_yAOC	-0.0564	0.0093	0.0000
In_yAOC	-0.0880	0.0108	0.0000
In_xL	0.1155	0.0146	0.0000
In_xW	0.2531	0.0157	0.0000
In_xK	0.0698	0.0136	0.0000
In_yC_2	-0.0903	0.0255	0.0000
In_yAOC_2	-0.0614	0.0106	0.0000
In_yAOC_2	-0.0231	0.0060	0.0000
In_yCyAOC	0.0674	0.0153	0.0000
In_yCyAOC	-0.0072	0.0147	0.6240
In_yAOCyAOC	-0.0142	0.0097	0.1440
In_xL_2	0.0598	0.0180	0.0010
In_xW_2	0.0578	0.0629	0.3590
In_xK_2	0.0541	0.0135	0.0000
In_xLxW	0.1000	0.0282	0.0000
In_xLxK	-0.0181	0.0145	0.2120
In_xWxK	0.0039	0.0242	0.8720
t	-0.0139	0.0017	0.0000
t_2	0.0048	0.0007	0.0000
In_yCt	-0.0080	0.0037	0.0330
In_yAOCt	-0.0004	0.0023	0.8690
In_yAOCt	-0.0020	0.0023	0.3910
In_xLt	-0.0076	0.0029	0.0100
In_xWt	-0.0243	0.0038	0.0000
In_xKt	-0.0091	0.0026	0.0000
In_yCxL	0.1219	0.0233	0.0000
In_yAOCxL	-0.0329	0.0129	0.0110
In_yAOCxL	-0.0088	0.0130	0.4980
In_yCxW	0.0336	0.0359	0.3500
In_yAOCxW	0.0072	0.0183	0.6930
In_yAOCxW	-0.0130	0.0174	0.4550
In_yCxK	-0.0108	0.0179	0.5480
In_yAOCxK	-0.0013	0.0105	0.9020
In_yAOCxK	0.0061	0.0101	0.5470
D2015	-0.0165	0.0087	0.0580
D2008	0.0388	0.0209	0.0640
D2006	-0.0627	0.0282	0.0260
_cons	-0.0063	0.0128	0.6220
			p-value
F-test	551.66	F[38,654]	0.000
AR(2)	-0.80		0.426
Hansen test	623.75	χ^2 [960]	1.000
Significance of technical change	21.18	F[8,654]	0.000
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE	5.93		0.010
N. instruments	999		
N. groups	655		

Table I12 – Milk: Sweden. (Source: Own calculation)

Sweden	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
In_xM			
In_yC	-0.4092	0.0182	0.0000
In_yAOC	-0.0926	0.0108	0.0000
In_yAOO	-0.3078	0.0148	0.0000
In_xL	0.0605	0.0238	0.0110
In_xW	0.2651	0.0216	0.0000
In_xK	0.0809	0.0149	0.0000
In_yC_2	-0.0980	0.0094	0.0000
In_yAOC_2	-0.0415	0.0072	0.0000
In_yAOO_2	-0.0799	0.0482	0.0990
In_yCyAOC	-0.0108	0.0131	0.4090
In_yCyAOO	0.0550	0.0299	0.0670
In_yAOCyAOO	0.0066	0.0136	0.6290
In_xL_2	-0.0018	0.0945	0.9850
In_xW_2	-0.1731	0.1090	0.1130
In_xK_2	0.0163	0.0314	0.6040
In_xLxW	0.0548	0.0885	0.5360
In_xLxK	-0.0914	0.0366	0.0130
In_xWxK	0.0862	0.0378	0.0230
t	0.0017	0.0021	0.4160
t_2	0.0021	0.0010	0.0310
In_yCt	0.0097	0.0030	0.0010
In_yAOCt	0.0033	0.0025	0.1840
In_yAOOt	-0.0098	0.0042	0.0180
In_xLt	0.0081	0.0062	0.1940
In_xWt	-0.0024	0.0060	0.6900
In_xKt	-0.0099	0.0043	0.0220
In_yCxL	0.0573	0.0324	0.0780
In_yAOCxL	-0.0130	0.0206	0.5270
In_yAOOxL	-0.0544	0.0496	0.2740
In_yCxW	-0.0154	0.0277	0.5770
In_yAOCxW	-0.0638	0.0226	0.0050
In_yAOOxW	0.0293	0.0468	0.5310
In_yCxK	0.0233	0.0279	0.4040
In_yAOCxK	-0.0062	0.0141	0.6620
In_yAOOxK	0.0369	0.0261	0.1590
D2010	0.0294	0.0100	0.0030
D2006	0.0486	0.0094	0.0000
DLFA	-0.0755	0.0126	0.0000
_cons	0.1079	0.0160	0.0000
			p-value
F-test	519.22	F[38,379]	0.000
AR(2)	0.36		0.718
Hansen test	353.59	χ^2 [1179]	1.000
Significance of technical change	7.04	F[8,379]	0.000
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE	0.21		0.500
N. instruments	1218		
N. groups	380		

Table I13 – Milk: United Kingdom. (Source: Own calculation)

United Kingdom	GMM		
	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t
In_xM			
In_yC	-0.5249	0.0163	0.0000
In_yAOC	-0.1640	0.0113	0.0000
In_yAOO	-0.1690	0.0079	0.0000
In_xL	0.1122	0.0302	0.0000
In_xW	0.2801	0.0290	0.0000
In_xK	0.1234	0.0270	0.0000
In_yC_2	-0.1983	0.0384	0.0000
In_yAOC_2	-0.0820	0.0173	0.0000
In_yAOO_2	-0.0942	0.0116	0.0000
In_yCyAOC	0.0547	0.0208	0.0090
In_yCyAOO	0.0921	0.0202	0.0000
In_yAOCyAOO	0.0237	0.0118	0.0440
In_xL_2	-0.1617	0.0941	0.0870
In_xW_2	0.1005	0.1487	0.5000
In_xK_2	0.0644	0.0624	0.3030
In_xLxW	-0.0013	0.0874	0.9890
In_xLxK	0.0757	0.0606	0.2120
In_xWxK	0.0768	0.0705	0.2770
t	-0.0141	0.0025	0.0000
t_2	0.0076	0.0010	0.0000
In_yCt	-0.0082	0.0042	0.0500
In_yAOCt	-0.0032	0.0027	0.2480
In_yAOOt	0.0098	0.0027	0.0000
In_xLt	-0.0157	0.0083	0.0600
In_xWt	-0.0008	0.0073	0.9120
In_xKt	0.0046	0.0072	0.5190
In_yCxL	-0.0247	0.0511	0.6280
In_yAOCxL	0.0144	0.0261	0.5810
In_yAOOxL	-0.0039	0.0358	0.9140
In_yCxW	0.0816	0.0584	0.1630
In_yAOCxW	-0.0018	0.0303	0.9530
In_yAOOxW	0.0384	0.0353	0.2780
In_yCxK	-0.0204	0.0382	0.5930
In_yAOCxK	0.0376	0.0279	0.1780
In_yAOOxK	-0.0098	0.0226	0.6650
D2015	0.0414	0.0094	0.0000
D2010	0.0312	0.0118	0.0090
DLFA	-0.1570	0.0308	0.0000
_cons	0.0844	0.0130	0.0000
			p-value
F-test	443.80	F[38,414]	0.000
AR(2)	-1.84		0.066
Hansen test	378.89	χ^2 [513]	1.000
Significance of technical change	10.74	F[8,414]	0.000
Log-Likelihood test: sigma_η = 0 for PTE	-2147.81		0.000
N. instruments	552		
N. groups	415		

AGRICULTURE - MILK: DEVELOPMENT OF TRANSIENT TECHNICAL EFFICIENCY

Figure D1a – Milk: Development of transient technical efficiency (part 1). (Source: Own calculation)

Figure D1b – Milk: Development of transient technical efficiency (part 2). (Source: Own calculation)

AGRICULTURE - MILK: META-FRONTIER MODEL ESTIMATES

Table J1 – Milk: Meta-frontier model estimates. (Source: Own calculation)

	Coef.	Std. Err.	P> t	
ln_xM				
ln_yC	-0.4009	0.0071	0.0000	
ln_yAOC	-0.1688	0.0057	0.0000	
ln_yAOO	-0.1833	0.0039	0.0000	
ln_xL	0.0485	0.0089	0.0000	
ln_xW	0.2399	0.0116	0.0000	
ln_xK	0.1189	0.0092	0.0000	
ln_yC_2	-0.1279	0.0076	0.0000	
ln_yAOC_2	-0.0666	0.0094	0.0000	
ln_yAOO_2	-0.0512	0.0036	0.0000	
ln_yCyAOC	0.0139	0.0099	0.1620	
ln_yCyAOO	0.0188	0.0074	0.0110	
ln_yAOCyAOO	0.0020	0.0069	0.7710	
ln_xL_2	-0.0898	0.0236	0.0000	
ln_xW_2	-0.0216	0.0541	0.6890	
ln_xK_2	0.0264	0.0120	0.0280	
ln_xLxW	0.0026	0.0314	0.9330	
ln_xLxK	0.0207	0.0140	0.1410	
ln_xWxK	0.0286	0.0238	0.2300	
t	-0.0040	0.0029	0.1620	
t_2	0.0052	0.0007	0.0000	
ln_yCt	0.0022	0.0012	0.0680	
ln_yAOCt	-0.0003	0.0010	0.7800	
ln_yAOOt	0.0012	0.0007	0.0910	
ln_xLt	0.0024	0.0018	0.1860	
ln_xWt	0.0029	0.0023	0.1990	
ln_xKt	-0.0049	0.0019	0.0080	
ln_yCxL	0.0149	0.0188	0.4280	
ln_yAOCxL	-0.0422	0.0181	0.0200	
ln_yAOOxL	0.0234	0.0119	0.0500	
ln_yCxW	-0.0700	0.0214	0.0010	
ln_yAOCxW	-0.0177	0.0191	0.3530	
ln_yAOOxW	-0.0259	0.0151	0.0860	
ln_yCxK	0.0328	0.0142	0.0210	
ln_yAOCxK	-0.0520	0.0128	0.0000	
ln_yAOOxK	0.0177	0.0079	0.0250	
D2015	0.0271	0.0026	0.0000	
D2011	0.0662	0.0054	0.0000	
D2010	0.0613	0.0090	0.0000	
_cons	0.0750	0.0074	0.0000	
			p-value	
F-test	1389.94	F[38,8095]	0.000	
Technical efficiency				
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Overall	0.9470	0.0129	0.7694	0.9891
Persistent	0.9482	0.0129	0.7704	0.9904
Transient	0.9987	0.0000	0.9987	0.9987

AGRICULTURE - MILK: META-FRONTIER TRANSIENT TECHNICAL EFFICIENCY

Table K1 – Milk: Meta-frontier transient technical efficiency. (Source: Own calculation)

Country	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max
Austria	0.9484	0.0112	0.8612	0.9843
Belgium	0.9487	0.0108	0.8547	0.9785
Czechia	0.9489	0.0115	0.8420	0.9889
Finland	0.9474	0.0153	0.8477	0.9876
France	0.9488	0.0100	0.8505	0.9863
West Germany	0.9492	0.0097	0.8643	0.9871
East Germany	0.9482	0.0099	0.8842	0.9824
Ireland	0.9478	0.0137	0.8390	0.9737
Italy	0.9462	0.0193	0.7876	0.9891
Romania	0.9454	0.0232	0.7704	0.9904
Spain	0.9468	0.0170	0.7872	0.9861
Sweden	0.9482	0.0119	0.8197	0.9888
United Kingdom	0.9485	0.0116	0.8447	0.9775

ANNEX III

IMPACT OF TECHNICAL CHANGE ON OUTPUT: REGRESSION

Table L1 - Regression: impact of technical change on output in food processing industry (sectors). (Source: Own calculation)

Austria	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	Belgium	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	Czechia	Coeff.	Std.	P> z
TC	0.1248	1.5815	0.9370	TC	-8.1288	4.4623	0.0690	TC	-17.0886	2.4165	0.0000
TC_101	-5.1062	3.0304	0.0920	TC_101	-22.4347	9.5873	0.0190	TC_101	-8.3639	4.6260	0.0710
TC_105	6.3783	2.3685	0.0070	TC_105	-26.7419	12.7399	0.0360	TC_105	51.4736	10.2755	0.0000
TC_106	18.2621	18.2553	0.3170	TC_106	-14.6231	15.3022	0.3390	TC_106	-163.6056	44.2090	0.0000
TC_107	4.4198	4.3320	0.3080	TC_107	40.9951	8.4828	0.0000	TC_107	-18.6393	3.6483	0.0000
_cons	10.8902	0.0930	0.0000	_cons	10.0794	0.0654	0.0000	_cons	7.4883	0.0469	0.0000
sigma_u	0.8186			sigma_u	1.2977			sigma_u	1.3772		
sigma_e	0.2111			sigma_e	0.2251			sigma_e	0.3434		
rho	0.9376			rho	0.9708			rho	0.9415		
R ²	0.1055	Wald	0.0015	R ²	0.0344	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.1342	Wald	0.0000
Finland	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	France	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	Germany	Coeff.	Std.	P> z
TC	1.1542	0.5841	0.0480	TC	2.8216	0.3493	0.0000	TC	4.4302	1.2161	0.0000
TC_101	0.8502	1.5822	0.5910	TC_101	0.0557	0.6099	0.9270	TC_101	-5.6862	2.6544	0.0320
TC_105	-3.7196	1.9170	0.0520	TC_105	6.3588	0.9108	0.0000	TC_105	1.5959	2.5391	0.5300
TC_106	-1.5086	4.2573	0.7230	TC_106	-1.0083	1.0840	0.3520	TC_106	-5.9150	3.7434	0.1140
TC_107	-3.7989	0.8841	0.0000	TC_107	-4.4302	0.4999	0.0000	TC_107	1.0609	3.2211	0.7420
_cons	6.9031	0.0719	0.0000	_cons	7.8851	0.0227	0.0000	_cons	10.2353	0.0657	0.0000
sigma_u	1.8931			sigma_u	1.1769			sigma_u	1.6521		
sigma_e	0.3241			sigma_e	0.1775			sigma_e	0.2262		
rho	0.9715			rho	0.9778			rho	0.9816		
R ²	0.0083	Wald	0.0003	R ²	0.1307	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.0264	Wald	0.0002
Italy	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	Romania	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	Spain	Coeff.	Std.	P> z
TC	-115.7158	2.1967	0.0000	TC	0.5007	0.1036	0.0000	TC	-16.7719	1.8175	0.0000
TC_101	-18.7347	3.4082	0.0000	TC_101	-0.4823	0.1781	0.0070	TC_101	6.8449	3.3940	0.0440
TC_105	-55.0082	5.8950	0.0000	TC_105	0.6777	0.2025	0.0010	TC_105	-25.3116	13.5948	0.0630
TC_106	24.1267	6.7831	0.0000	TC_106	-0.1477	0.1957	0.4500	TC_106	7.7203	5.9704	0.1960
TC_107	-15.5879	3.9317	0.0000	TC_107	0.1829	0.1215	0.1320	TC_107	-10.0442	3.4568	0.0040
_cons	9.2175	0.0233	0.0000	_cons	5.2364	0.0268	0.0000	_cons	8.3461	0.0295	0.0000
sigma_u	0.6598			sigma_u	1.7824			sigma_u	1.0312		
sigma_e	0.2186			sigma_e	0.4619			sigma_e	0.2463		
rho	0.9011			rho	0.9371			rho	0.9460		
R ²	0.6437	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.0013	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.0923	Wald	0.0000
Sweden	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	United Kingdom	Coeff.	Std.	P> z				
TC	6.0364	0.6970	0.0000	TC	1.4286	1.0884	0.1890				
TC_101	2.5859	1.1296	0.0220	TC_101	2.6057	2.0763	0.2090				
TC_105	5.0165	3.8750	0.1950	TC_105	2.7763	2.6846	0.3010				
TC_106	-3.2205	2.9555	0.2760	TC_106	3.9734	3.1447	0.2060				
TC_107	-5.8107	1.0381	0.0000	TC_107	0.8413	2.2651	0.7100				
_cons	7.3042	0.0529	0.0000	_cons	10.5545	0.0299	0.0000				
sigma_u	1.4958			sigma_u	0.6680						
sigma_e	0.2454			sigma_e	0.2403						
rho	0.9738			rho	0.8854						
R ²	0.0004	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.1963	Wald	0.0149				

Table L2 - Regression: impact of technical change on output in food processing industry (size_dummy). (Source: Own calculation)

Austria	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	Belgium	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	Czechia	Coeff.	Std.	P> z
TC_small				TC_small	-5.4877	21.4718	0.7980	TC_small	-116.6973	4.2003	0.0000
TC	-119.1000	12.2939	0.0000	TC	-21.4091	6.7354	0.0010	TC	-31.7656	2.2700	0.0000
TC_large	118.8602	12.3796	0.0000	TC_large	15.8719	7.3275	0.0300	TC_large	63.1723	3.5976	0.0000
TC_v_large	123.1983	12.3502	0.0000	TC_v_large	46.8605	9.0674	0.0000	TC_v_large	130.5258	9.6916	0.0000
_cons	10.8754	0.0918	0.0000	_cons	10.0556	0.0557	0.0000	_cons	7.7832	0.0365	0.0000
sigma_u	0.8036			sigma_u	1.0707			sigma_u	0.9486		
sigma_e	0.1920			sigma_e	0.2274			sigma_e	0.3348		
rho	0.9460			rho	0.9568			rho	0.8892		
R ²	0.0040	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.3220	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.5893	Wald	0.0000
Finland	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	France	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	Germany	Coeff.	Std.	P> z
TC_small	-10.9881	0.9171	0.0000	TC_small	-13.1522	0.5994	0.0000	TC_small	0.3254	8.8582	0.9710
TC	4.0019	0.7044	0.0000	TC	3.2369	0.3354	0.0000	TC	-2.1641	2.9108	0.4570
TC_large	3.3391	1.1749	0.0040	TC_large	7.4684	0.6770	0.0000	TC_large	1.1505	3.1893	0.7180
TC_v_large	0.5737	2.1317	0.7880	TC_v_large	20.0540	1.4952	0.0000	TC_v_large	13.1667	3.2602	0.0000
_cons	6.9213	0.0691	0.0000	_cons	7.8757	0.0158	0.0000	_cons	10.2375	0.0570	0.0000
sigma_u	1.8144			sigma_u	0.6810			sigma_u	1.3687		
sigma_e	0.3156			sigma_e	0.1754			sigma_e	0.2250		
Rho	0.9706			rho	0.9378			rho	0.9737		
R ²	0.1172	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.5551	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.1497	Wald	0.0000
Italy	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	Romania	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	Spain	Coeff.	Std.	P> z
TC_small	-53.4940	3.2543	0.0000	TC_small	1.9326	0.1029	0.0000	TC_small	-104.9597	3.3781	0.0000
TC	-129.0866	1.8908	0.0000	TC	-0.4309	0.0780	0.0000	TC	-45.0810	1.7795	0.0000
TC_large	61.5884	2.9989	0.0000	TC_large	-0.9769	0.2152	0.0000	TC_large	89.9567	2.2162	0.0000
TC_v_large	-82.3377	16.1017	0.0000	TC_v_large	2.6494	0.4284	0.0000	TC_v_large	153.9935	4.9021	0.0000
_cons	9.3016	0.0215	0.0000	_cons	5.2304	0.0217	0.0000	_cons	8.5722	0.0233	0.0000
sigma_u	0.5926			sigma_u	1.3446			sigma_u	0.7341		
sigma_e	0.2177			sigma_e	0.4543			sigma_e	0.2385		
Rho	0.8811			rho	0.8975			rho	0.9045		
R ²	0.6955	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.0726	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.6996	Wald	0.0000
Sweden	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	United Kingdom	Coeff.	Std.	P> z				
TC_small	-13.1852	1.0629	0.0000	TC_small	2.6570	10.0589	0.7920				
TC	8.5061	0.6500	0.0000	TC	-45.7314	4.1354	0.0000				
TC_large	0.3156	1.2360	0.7980	TC_large	48.1652	4.2100	0.0000				
TC_v_large	-1.6526	3.1916	0.6050	TC_v_large	54.3803	4.4041	0.0000				
_cons	7.3286	0.0441	0.0000	_cons	10.6041	0.0293	0.0000				
sigma_u	1.1756			sigma_u	0.6486						
sigma_e	0.2429			sigma_e	0.2386						
rho	0.9591			rho	0.8808						
R ²	0.1247	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.0377	Wald	0.0000				

Table M1 - Regression: impact of technical change on cereals output (econ_size). (Source: Own calculation)

Austria	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	Belgium	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	Czechia	Coeff.	Std.	P> z
TC	-12.1339	1.6108	0.0000	TC	0.1680	2.2059	0.9390	TC	-1.0927	0.2636	0.0000
TC_ES	0.0758	0.0213	0.0000	TC_ES	0.0036	0.0102	0.7250	TC_ES	0.0002	0.0002	0.3960
_cons	8.6992	0.0469	0.0000	_cons	9.3126	0.0594	0.0000	_cons	11.3692	0.0598	0.0000
sigma_u	1.2545			sigma_u	0.8832			sigma_u	1.6572		
sigma_e	0.3513			sigma_e	0.4199			sigma_e	0.3068		
Rho	0.9273			rho	0.8157			rho	0.9669		
R ²	0.0280	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.1208	Wald	0.7715	R ²	0.0001	Wald	0.0000
Finland	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	France	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	West Germany	Coeff.	Std.	P> z
TC	11.6214	1.1254	0.0000	TC	-11.4983	1.1508	0.0000	TC	-0.7966	0.1314	0.0000
TC_ES	-0.0391	0.0065	0.0000	TC_ES	0.0303	0.0055	0.0000	TC_ES	-0.0004	0.0005	0.5210
_cons	9.6302	0.0355	0.0000	_cons	10.4661	0.0261	0.0000	_cons	9.7478	0.0217	0.0000
sigma_u	0.5806			sigma_u	0.9399			sigma_u	0.8771		
sigma_e	0.3703			sigma_e	0.2698			sigma_e	0.2977		
Rho	0.7109			rho	0.9239			rho	0.8967		
R ²	0.2530	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.0097	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.0001	Wald	0.0000
East Germany	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	Ireland	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	Italy	Coeff.	Std.	P> z
TC	-2.8496	0.3285	0.0000	TC	-3.4247	1.6149	0.0340	TC	-5.7739	1.7024	0.0010
TC_ES	0.0004	0.0002	0.0080	TC_ES	0.0210	0.0174	0.2260	TC_ES	-0.0006	0.0156	0.9690
_cons	11.6106	0.0523	0.0000	_cons	9.4574	0.0922	0.0000	_cons	8.6392	0.0455	0.0000
sigma_u	1.2176			sigma_u	1.1324			sigma_u	0.9986		
sigma_e	0.2688			sigma_e	0.3709			sigma_e	0.4643		
Rho	0.9535			rho	0.9031			Rho	0.8223		
R ²	0.0063	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.0047	Wald	0.0669	R ²	0.0008	Wald	0.0000
Romania	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	Spain	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	Sweden	Coeff.	Std.	P> z
TC	2.0253	0.5801	0.0000	TC	-10.9509	0.8796	0.0000	TC	-9.1318	1.0401	0.0000
TC_ES	0.0080	0.0030	0.0080	TC_ES	0.0029	0.0022	0.1870	TC_ES	-0.0086	0.0036	0.0160
_cons	7.7154	0.0583	0.0000	_cons	9.8276	0.0519	0.0000	_cons	9.4101	0.0499	0.0000
sigma_u	1.1850			sigma_u	0.8032			sigma_u	1.1107		
sigma_e	0.4711			sigma_e	0.3513			sigma_e	0.3941		
rho	0.8635			rho	0.8394			Rho	0.8882		
R ²	0.1326	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.1701	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.0118	Wald	0.0000
United Kingdom	Coeff.	Std.	P> z								
TC	-6.5104	1.2040	0.0000								
TC_ES	-0.0018	0.0058	0.7570								
_cons	10.0231	0.0463	0.0000								
sigma_u	0.7878										
sigma_e	0.2808										
rho	0.8872										
R ²	0.2272	Wald	0.0000								

Table N1 - Regression: impact of technical change on milk output (econ_size). (Source: Own calculation)

Austria	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	Belgium	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	Czechia	Coeff.	Std.	P> z
TC	1.8186	0.8446	0.0310	TC	-5.1580	1.2919	0.0000	TC	1.7006	0.5730	0.0030
TC_ES	-0.1916	0.0108	0.0000	TC_ES	-0.0063	0.0049	0.2030	TC_ES	-0.0026	0.0003	0.0000
_cons	10.2626	0.0295	0.0000	_cons	11.3498	0.0351	0.0000	_cons	12.2192	0.0630	0.0000
sigma_u	0.9573			sigma_u	0.6778			sigma_u	1.3676		
sigma_e	0.2207			sigma_e	0.3416			sigma_e	0.3218		
Rho	0.9495			Rho	0.7974			Rho	0.9475		
R ²	0.0151	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.0340	Wald	0.7715	R ²	0.2108	Wald	0.0000
Finland	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	France	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	West Germany	Coeff.	Std.	P> z
TC	0.9418	0.6149	0.1260	TC	-11.7049	0.6620	0.0000	TC	-10.4074	0.4390	0.0000
TC_ES	-0.0653	0.0024	0.0000	TC_ES	-0.0079	0.0029	0.0060	TC_ES	-0.0022	0.0014	0.0000
_cons	11.3754	0.0212	0.0000	_cons	11.5112	0.0123	0.0000	_cons	11.5353	0.0166	0.0000
sigma_u	0.3812			sigma_u	0.5386			sigma_u	0.5438		
sigma_e	0.1653			sigma_e	0.1981			sigma_e	0.1834		
rho	0.8417			rho	0.8808			rho	0.8979		
R ²	0.4758	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.0676	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.4583	Wald	0.0000
East Germany	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	Ireland	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	Italy	Coeff.	Std.	P> z
TC	0.3502	0.7478	0.6400	TC	0.8820	0.8419	0.2950	TC	-0.6060	1.1348	0.5930
TC_ES	-0.0012	0.0003	0.0000	TC_ES	-0.0658	0.0052	0.0000	TC_ES	-0.0486	0.0075	0.0000
_cons	12.9309	0.0434	0.0000	_cons	11.2559	0.0288	0.0000	_cons	10.7328	0.0345	0.0000
sigma_u	0.9227			sigma_u	0.5192			sigma_u	1.0590		
sigma_e	0.2036			sigma_e	0.2023			sigma_e	0.3650		
Rho	0.9536			rho	0.8683			Rho	0.8938		
R ²	0.1365	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.2114	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.1174	Wald	0.0000
Romania	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	Spain	Coeff.	Std.	P> z	Sweden	Coeff.	Std.	P> z
TC	-2.3863	0.6832	0.0000	TC	-4.0210	0.3437	0.0000	TC	-2.1842	1.0032	0.0290
TC_ES	0.0256	0.0051	0.0000	TC_ES	-0.0023	0.0017	0.1810	TC_ES	-0.0186	0.0031	0.0000
_cons	8.2015	0.0574	0.0000	_cons	11.5473	0.0263	0.0000	_cons	11.5639	0.0391	0.0000
sigma_u	1.1528			sigma_u	0.6405			sigma_u	0.7353		
sigma_e	0.3925			sigma_e	0.2114			sigma_e	0.2311		
rho	0.8961			rho	0.9017			rho	0.9101		
R ²	0.0629	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.0495	Wald	0.0000	R ²	0.1190	Wald	0.0000
United Kingdom	Coeff.	Std.	P> z								
TC	0.5382	0.3815	0.1580								
TC_ES	-0.0026	0.0012	0.0410								
_cons	12.0781	0.0331	0.0000								
sigma_u	0.6548										
sigma_e	0.2051										
rho	0.9106										
R ²	0.0757	Wald	0.1023								

TECHNICAL CHANGE AND PRICE CHANGE DYNAMICS

Figure E1a – Food processing industry: Technical change dynamics (part 1). (Source: Own calculation)

Figure E1b – Food processing industry: Technical change dynamics (part 2). (Source: Own calculation)

Figure F1 – Cereals production: Technical change and price change dynamics. (Source: Own calculation)

Note: AT_Austria, BE_Belgium, CZ_Czechia, FI_Finland, FR_France, EDE_East Germany, WDE_West Germany, IR_Ireland, IT_Italy, RO_Romania, ES_Spain, SW_Sweden, UK_United Kingdom.

Figure G1 – Milk production: Technical change and price change dynamics. (Source: Own calculation)

Note: AT_Austria, BE_Belgium, CZ_Czechia, FI_Finland, FR_France, EDE_East Germany, WDE_West Germany, IR_Ireland, IT_Italy, RO_Romania, ES_Spain, SW_Sweden, UK_United Kingdom.

Figure H1 – Food processing industry: Price change dynamics (sectors: 10.1, 10.5, 10.6, 10.7). (Source: Own calculation)